

**Open Neuroscience:
Challenging scientific barriers with open source hardware**

Dissertation zur Erlangung des Grades eines
Doktors der Naturwissenschaften
der Mathematisch-Naturwissenschaftlichen Fakultät
und
der Medizinischen Fakultät
der Eberhard-Karls-Universität Tübingen
vorgelegt
von
André Maia Chagas
aus São Paulo, Brasilien

April 2020

Tag der mündlichen Prüfung: 19.10.2020

Dekan der Med. Fakultät: Prof. Dr. Bernd Pichler

Stellv. Dekan der Math.-Nat. Fakultät: Prof. Dr. József Fortágh

1. Berichterstatter: Prof. Dr. Thomas Euler

2. Berichterstatter: Prof. Dr. Aristides Arrenberg

Prüfungskommission: Prof. Dr. Thomas Euler

Prof. Dr. Aristides Arrenberg

Prof. Dr. Jan Benda

Prof. Dr. Philipp Berens

Ich erkläre, dass ich die zur Promotion eingereichte Arbeit mit dem Titel: **“Open Neuroscience: Challenging scientific barriers with open source hardware”** selbständig verfasst, nur die angegebenen Quellen und Hilfsmittel benutzt und wörtlich oder inhaltlich übernommene Stellen als solche gekennzeichnet habe.

Ich versichere an Eides statt, dass diese Angaben wahr sind und dass ich nichts verschwiegen habe. Mir ist bekannt, dass die falsche Abgabe einer Versicherung an Eides statt mit Freiheitsstrafe bis zu drei Jahren oder mit Geldstrafe bestraft wird

*I hereby declare that I have produced the work entitled **“Open Neuroscience: Challenging scientific barriers with open source hardware”**, submitted for the award of a doctorate, on my own (without external help), have used only the sources and aids indicated and have marked passages included from other works, whether verbatim or in content, as such.*

I swear upon oath that these statements are true and that I have not concealed anything. I am aware that making a false declaration under oath is punishable by a term of imprisonment of up to three years or by a fine.

Tübingen, den 25. April 2020

Dedicated to

Sofia

Table of contents	
Acknowledgements	8
Abstract / Summary	10
Synopsis	12
Definition of Open Source Hardware	14
Open Labware (Summary of Open Labware paper [12])	15
Open Sourcing existing tools (Summary of 100€ lab paper [13])	19
Building tools that perform new functions (Summary of Arbitrary spectrum visual stimulator paper [14])	21
Challenges for Open Source Hardware adoption in academia	22
Outlook	25
References	27
List of appended manuscripts contributions	32
Open Labware: 3-D Printing Your Own Lab Equipment	33
Abstract	33
Contributions	33
The €100 lab: A 3D-printable open-source platform for fluorescence microscopy, optogenetics, and accurate temperature control during behaviour of zebrafish, Drosophila, and Caenorhabditis elegans	35
Abstract	35
Contributions	35
Haves and have nots must find a better way: The case for open scientific hardware	37
Abstract	37
Contributions	37
An arbitrary-spectrum spatial visual stimulator for vision research	38
Abstract	38
Contributions	38
Appended Manuscripts	40

Acknowledgements

None of this work would be possible without the support of many wonderful people. Some part of my professional path and/or part of my personal life, they've helped me with questions, discussion, suggestions, sometimes just listening. Some of this was done a long time ago, and some more recently. In any case, I'm forever in debt.

I would like to especially thank the following people:

My family. My parents Helena Schargel Maia, Jose Francisco de Salles Chagas and my brother Rafael Maia Chagas for all their nurture and care, for teaching by example the value of hard work and honesty. I guess I'll soon understand how you feel as parents, and I can only hope that my actions are enough to make you proud.

My oldest friends, Lucas Delgado de Oliveira, Amanda Boccato, Maurício Motta, Roberta Toth, Rafael Oliveira Lima, Nathalia Toretta Moraes, Rafael Pereira da Silva and Stefanie Jordan, thank you for all the discussions, travels, and for "sticking around" for more than 20 years, a lot of what I am today is thanks to you.

The Tuebingen brunch family, Pooja Viswanathan, Sudarshan Sekhar and Lena Veit, thanks for the chats, different points of view, witty sense of humor and for your support during some rough patches in life. I hope I've been as good of a friend to you, as you have been to me.

Fernando Miranda, who I also got to know in Tuebingen, I'm thankful for our debates on politics, relationships, sports. But most importantly, thanks for bringing the perspective from humanities into our conversation.

Thomas Euler and Tom Baden, for being both excellent mentors, colleagues and friends, but most importantly for seeing (maybe even before I did) my professional strengths and giving me time and space to expand them. I'm extremely lucky and grateful for it.

Euler and Baden Lab members, thanks for all the discussions, support and lunches together. I hope my work with all of you has been, and will continue to be useful and helpful towards a more open, equitable science. My special thanks to Valeska Botzenhardt, Gordon Eske and Natasha Pouchkina-Stantcheva, always making sure things in the labs are running as they should.

Last, but not least, to my wife, Samyra Cury Salek, who is in my life for longer than she is not. I owe you more than I could ever repay and I'm forever thankful. You believed in our relationship when it was fainter than a whisper, and supported my dreams when they were nothing but ghosts. I can't imagine having been able to reach this point without you and the care and love you give me. I know these few lines won't do it justice, but thank you for everything.

Abstract / Summary

To answer scientific questions, researchers have to collect data by performing experiments that employ a range of different equipments. Currently their development and distribution has been relegated mostly to a small number of specialised companies. They sell these devices as “black boxes”, which are fairly expensive and not readily available worldwide. This in turn hinders research in a lot of institutions/labs. Moreover, due to the proprietary nature of their licensing, users are not allowed to open, repair and/or customise their tools, slowing the pace of research and making it even more costly.

One possible solution for these issues is for researchers to build their own scientific instruments and distribute their designs using open source licenses. Fortunately, current prototyping tools, high computing power in affordable electronic components and digital infrastructure make it easier than ever to build complex systems and share detailed documentation on how to reproduce them. Producing equipment in this way reduces research costs, allows for better experimental setup control, and has the potential to truly democratize science, as designs can be replicated globally.

This thesis summarizes my work developing these tools, teaching others how to build them and analysing their potential long term impact for research and education around the globe.

Synopsis

To gather information about the natural world, researchers have to rely on the use of different measurement instruments. These instruments, normally provided by specialised companies, perform one specific task and a single lab usually requires dozens of different instruments to tackle questions in one field. As these instruments are used for data gathering and new knowledge is formed, more questions arise and different versions/improvements of the current instruments are necessary to answer them, creating an equipment cycle: New instruments → new data → new answers → new questions requiring newer instruments.

Two examples of the impressive benefits new instruments can bring to the field of neuroscience, include the “behavioural box” by Skinner [1], and the bioamplifier recording system by Hodgkin and Huxley [2]. The first was an automated system for delivering sensory stimuli and positive/negative reinforcers to animals, with great temporal precision (on the range of milliseconds), so as to automatically and systematically assess animal behaviour. The second was a system to record electrical responses from individual neurons, which enabled the investigation of the electro-chemical properties of neurons in the giant squid, and led to a very detailed characterisation of how action potentials are elicited and propagated through neurons. Hodgkin and Huxley won the Nobel Prize in 1963 [3] for their discoveries. Moreover, the techniques they developed were instrumental to at least four other Nobel winning research projects [4]. The above mentioned methodological advancements were fundamental for a complete paradigm shift in the Neurosciences, as they paved the way for new theories on behaviour and neuronal communication. Currently variants of these tools are used in tandem to investigate the neuronal correlates of behaviour, spanning several sub-fields in Neurosciences.

Even if extremely useful to labs and institutions, the development of scientific equipment has been relegated to a few labs and companies, as it requires a skill-set that is normally not acquired by researchers in life sciences. This “development exclusivity” has also led to distribution being mostly done by companies normally spinning off from, or having intellectual property agreements with, academic

institutions [5]. Such a model has advantages, and has been beneficial (even if costly) for research and education for a number of years, since it allows for cooperating partners to focus on their strong points (Universities/institutions focus on prototyping and development, and companies focus on production and distribution). However, one of the disadvantages is that this works best for well funded institutions, where researchers can simply read what their colleagues have used for a set of experiments and get the same setups from these providers, without much worry about costs. For researchers in institutions less well funded the situation is much harder, as high prices prevents them from accessing cutting edge tools for research [6]. Additionally, having only a few distributors mainly located in the Global North creates a supply chain problem for customers in locations far away: Costs increase due to shipping and customs fees, and repairing tools becomes hard if not impossible as no local customer service is available [7].

One possible way to alleviate these issues, relies on researchers reestablishing the tradition of building their own equipment and tools, by taking advantage of four key developments that are making it easier than ever for anyone to build complex hardware: I) the price drop in microprocessors, which has led to small devices that are at the same time cheap enough to flood the consumer market and powerful enough to perform complex tasks such as running machine vision algorithms [8,9]; II) the development of consumer level fast prototyping tools (eg 3D printers and laser cutters [10,11]), which allows the creation of mechanical parts such as gears, and other mechanical parts that integrate with electronic bits; III) the adoption of the Open Source software (OSS) ethos in hardware development (see open source hardware definition below) by incentivizing documentation distribution of all components and steps necessary to build research equipment; IV) improvement in Internet and storage infrastructures necessary to share and host documentation in an array of media formats (text, photos, videos, interactive web pages, etc). These developments are allowing hobbyists, DIYers and researchers to leverage more than 80 online sharing platforms/repositories for their projects, opening up opportunities for a complete overhaul on the way researchers and educators create/use their tools.

This synopsis summarizes key arguments made in the four papers composing this thesis for the use of open source hardware in academia, discusses how they are related to the current literature and how its use can bring significant changes in the way science is performed. Three of the papers [12–14] are summarized and contextualized in their own sections, while the fourth one [5] can be considered a summary of different aspects of Open Source Hardware in Academia and why researchers should be embracing it, and therefore is cited throughout this synopsis.

Definition of Open Source Hardware

A better understanding of the concept of open source hardware is key to appreciating the opportunities that the philosophy presents to the scientific community. Open Source Hardware (OSH) is inspired by the Open-Source Software (OSS) philosophy, in which, all code (and in a way all ideas) created are made available using legally binding licenses [15] that enable users to modify, contribute, study, improve and redistribute the code/ideas they worked on [16]. This knowledge production philosophy has led to the development of key software platforms that power most of the computing world today (GNU/Linux operating system powers most supercomputers, servers and mobile phones around the globe). Thanks to OSS, researchers can rely on freely available software (such as data analysis tools and office suites) for most of their research tasks, including service provision from companies [16,17].

The same is becoming true for hardware, where freely available design documentation allows researchers and educators to build their own tools much faster and cheaper than before [5]. This is mainly due to the fact that companies providing services around OSH for neurosciences are entering the market [18–25]. Readers interested in the particularities about the documentation and distribution of OSH (as there are significant differences as compared to OSS) are referred to Gibb *et al* [26] and Bonvoisin *et al* [27].

Open Labware (Summary of Open Labware paper [12])

In 2015 we published a paper putting forth the idea that every scientist can make their own tools for various research questions at a fraction of the cost of commercially-available scientific equipment[12] The key aspects of this paper is summarized in this section. Briefly, we discuss how this has been made possible through the development of crucial aspects in tool making and hardware documentation: 1) the introduction of consumer-oriented fast prototyping tools, such as 3D printers and laser-cutters, 2) access to affordable electronic components made easy to use by non-specialists, 3) freely accessible design details and build instructions on online repositories and online community forums. We also point out how groups around the world started leveraging these new developments to improve their equipment infrastructure and teaching. Below these points are further debated, taking into account the current literature.

Perhaps the first noticeable characteristic of OSH tools is their lower price when compared to proprietary ones. Since all information about production costs (both in terms of materials and time necessary to actually build the tool described) is available, the room for disproportionately inflated costs deriving from company monopoly and intellectual property/patent is strongly constrained. In fact, papers describing OSH show that these devices can be up to 97% cheaper than their proprietary counterparts [28–36]. These savings also apply to open source designs of supporting apparel such as Eppendorf tube holders, vial racks and cage systems for optical applications [31,37–39]. Given the current open source 3D printers price of ~US\$ 200 [40] and tube holders cost of ~US\$ 72 [41], printing as little as three tube holders already justifies the initial investment of buying a 3D printer. Considering their versatility and the fact that they can be used by more than one research group makes them even more attractive for lab use. Interestingly, one paper has calculated a potential return on investment (ROI), if federal granting agencies dedicated parts of their budget to the development of OSH projects [42]. Using a published syringe pump design as a basis, they calculated the costs for developing the system from zero, including materials and the human resources necessary for development and assembly (26 hours in total). They found a total cost

of US\$ 30,000. Considering the costs of commercially available pumps and the number of people that reportedly replicated their design, and potential replicators (people who downloaded their design) they estimate a ROI of 460% to 8,300%, thereby maximizing the efficiency of public investments in science. These examples offer strong economic incentives for wider adoption of OSH in academia, from the point of view of both researchers and granting agencies.

Wide adoption of OSH would bring consequences for the many companies producing scientific and medical equipment. What at first seems like a negative prospect for companies given the smaller profit margins or a shrinking market share, and even running out of business, can also be seen as an opportunity to change business models: from leveraging intellectual property and market monopoly to providing services and custom solutions for labs and institutions [26], being able to reach more markets with lower prices (and possibly achieving higher profits) as well as helping science and education develop faster. Moreover, given the legal requirements for medical applications, OSH development in labs can only go so far. Navigating all legal requirements and fronting the necessary costs to medically certify a product will still require companies to bring them to market [5].

Another benefit of a freely available bill of materials and assembly instructions, is the local (re)production of OSH, enabling equipment to reach places where regular supply chains fail and/or repair services are lacking [7]. These characteristics (affordability and local production), bring a series of positive consequences for labs and institutions: a) Smaller budgets can now be used to set up proper equipment infrastructure. b) Expensive equipment normally available as sole units or in small numbers, can now be built/purchased in higher numbers so that they can be used in teaching practical courses, where students and young researchers learn by executing protocols, interpreting collected data, and proposing follow up questions. This situation leads to a much better preparation for a career in academia and has been demonstrated to be effective in courses across the globe [32,43–45], in line with workshops and “demo days” we did in Africa, Chile and the USA [12,46]. In fact, in these practical courses we have engaged participants to actually build the tools they will use to perform experiments, enabling them to gain a

greater understanding of the capabilities and limitations of the tools being used, how they can be repaired and also how to customize/upgrade them when necessary [5]. A systematic review (2007 to 2017 period) on the use of OSH for education [47] found a steady increase in the number of academic and conference publications, in different subjects and at different degree levels. Similarly, the OSH articles published have shown a steady increase between 2010 and 2020, as well as journals and events dedicated to them (Fig 1).

Figure 1: Number of publications describing OSH. Black dashed lines indicate important landmarks in the field (key meetings putting together different networks and the start of journals dedicated to OSH). Blue dashed lines indicate when articles covered in this synopsis were published. Data collected by downloading all references from Pubmed (www.pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov) as a result of a search query containing “open source hardware”. Articles were further filtered by selecting only the ones that shared design files as supplemental data and/or in an online repository.

Even if equipment costs were not an important concern for researchers, there is a lot of opportunity in science and education that stems from bringing research equipment costs down. As mentioned above, technological development in

electronics and internet infrastructure are paving the way for a new hardware open-development paradigm that is quickly spreading through labs worldwide. The next sections go beyond price reduction benefits of open development and provide specific arguments for adopting OSH in academia.

Open Sourcing existing tools (Summary of 100€ lab paper [13])

The recreation of Open Source versions of already established tools brings advantages to research, as developers tend to use newer and more effective technologies to implement the same (and even go beyond) functionalities of existing equipment. In this section I describe some of these initiatives and summarize the “100 Euro lab” paper [13] while putting it in context.

Open-Ephys [48], lowered the price of electrophysiology systems by an order of magnitude (a starter kit with 64 channels goes for 5470€ as of Jan 2020). The open-ephys systems can have up to 512 channels, are scalable and smaller than traditional systems. Coupled with extensive documentation [49], which allowed a number of labs to build add ons for it [50–53], Open Ephys has become a mature and robust environment for electrophysiology used by many labs [21] in less than 7 years. Another example, OpenTrons [54], a pipetting robot for lab automation, started as a master thesis project [55], is helping researchers automate a lot of tedious molecular biology protocols, saving time while increasing experimental reproducibility. Moreover, due to its open nature, OpenTrons is being built in community labs, as well as bio hackerspaces, further contributing to the democratization of science, by bringing it out of academic spaces. Interestingly, in 2018 the project received investments from venture capitalists [56], thereby coupling traditional investment to a new business model where hardware is offered as a service [26]. The same development is being seen for other instruments, such as syringe pumps [57], PCR machines [58], centrifuges [59,60], shakers [61], behavioural boxes [62–65], Drosophila food dispensing robots [66].

Using similar principles, we developed a 3-D printable, open source, modular, low-cost (almost 20X cheaper than current systems) “all in one lab” [13] and showed that a device built with off-the-shelf components can be used to implement

state-of-the-art techniques in neurosciences, including behavioural tracking, optogenetics, thermogenetics, optical and fluorescence microscopy. The system is lightweight, can be driven by 12V batteries, and connected to the Internet, making it well suited for field work and deployable in areas where infrastructure is not well established or temporarily lacking, when compared to traditional systems.

Leveraging our device's open documentation and low price point we have organized "Project-Based learning" workshops where participants built equipment from scratch (and ending up with a new multi tool for their research lab/classroom), and were able in a short period of time to gather enough knowledge and confidence to venture into the maker/DIY world and from there, build tools of their own. In line with the open labware ethos, Open sourcing existing tools can also be seen as a good method to learn electronics and fast mechanical prototyping (basic skills for developing hardware) as the final product should function in a specific way, already known to the developer/user. The tool being developed can be benchmarked against existing equipment and tweaked/improved as needed.

Another feature of OSH implementation is the diversity of projects users can choose from, each with its highlights and shortcomings; enabling them to find tools that are better suited for their environments/needs, as our design is definitely not the only one to describe an easy to build and customizable microscopy system [32,34,36,67–69]. Having a plethora of projects to choose from, developers rarely have to start from zero when creating new tools [70], and our system (or parts of it) was used as inspiration for other tools developed by researchers in different fields [32,35,71–73], enabling faster, collaborative and distributed development of scientific equipment.

Last but not least, having OSH available to furnish labs, opens up the possibility for multiple experiments to be done in parallel, increasing data collection rate [35,62], optimizing the time spent by researchers in experimental procedures, and directly influencing the types of questions that can be asked, as certain comparisons require large datasets that would normally be very hard if not impossible to acquire if they had to be done one after the other. Moreover, the use of

newer technologies means devices can now be connected to computers over a network, and together with a bit of software code, certain repetitive tasks can be automated, again providing time benefits and minimising unwanted outcomes that can happen as a result of human interaction/handling, such as sample contamination [74] and recording bias [75].

Building tools that perform new functions (Summary of Arbitrary spectrum visual stimulator paper [14])

Possibly one of the most exciting features of OSH is the opportunity to easily create tools that are capable of measuring/stimulating natural systems in an unprecedented way, expanding the quantity and quality of possible experiments, and therefore the types of questions that can be asked, as well as the ways to answer them. Leveraging the technical advancements described in the “Open Labware” section (above) researchers can now do just that, and the fact that they are themselves creating tools enables a focused development cycle, supported by consumer electronic components with a great performance-to-cost ratio. This feature is not restricted to neurosciences, and devices are being developed in different fields, such as biochemistry where a “smart centrifuge” [76], with built-in sensors, measures sample concentration during centrifugation and sends data in real-time to a connected device. This setup allows plotting graphs of decantation vs time and decantation vs sample concentration, which leads to an informed optimization of centrifugation protocols, saving time (the centrifuge is automatically turned off and the experimenter notified once a preset concentration is reached), and avoiding “re-runs” of samples not centrifuged long enough. Based on the real-time graphs users could also determine cell concentration in a sample and even the cell type.

Another example is an upgrade on traditional insect pitfall traps. In this paper [70], the authors show a time sorting trap, where 24 traps are added into a carousel, which is then controlled by a motor and a timing system that rotates a new trap into “catching position” once per hour. The system also collects temperature data. Albeit simple, this system opens up the possibility for new protocols to be established, which in turn enables new questions to be asked, such as “are certain insect species

foraging a certain area at specific hours of the day?” If so, could this be correlated with environmental variables such as temperature, CO2 levels, humidity, luminosity, etc. This system could also be redesigned in a way that allows for automated data collection over the course of days, with each day collection being separated from the previous ones, by simply adding multiples of 24 to the trap count.

Similar to these (and many other) examples, we recently published a paper describing an arbitrary wavelength spatial stimulator that can be synchronised to data collection systems (e.g. electrophysiology systems, or 2 photon microscopes) [14]. The system was designed to fill a shortcoming in visual neurosciences, where available solutions could either provide a wide range in the chromatic spectrum, at the cost of spatial resolution, or achieved sufficient spatial resolution but were mostly limited to primate chromatic spectra. By adapting a commercial stimulator and documenting all necessary steps to do so, we have created a starting point for other researchers to not only implement this solution in their own labs, but also to improve upon it [70]. If indeed taken up by the community, it will become easier to compare results and experimental designs between labs as the underlying stimulation technology will be the same. By solving this methodological shortcoming, we create the opportunity for new experimental designs to be developed, where more natural stimuli can be used. Moreover, due to the possibility of using virtually every LED available commercially, we make it possible to optimally stimulate the visual system of species not investigated so far, thereby giving researchers more resources to learn how different biological systems use chromatic information to behave and thrive in their environments.

Challenges for Open Source Hardware adoption in academia

While highlighting the opportunities for OSH in academia, it is equally important to understand the challenges that must be addressed to facilitate its widespread adoption. This section makes an overview on current issues and shows ongoing efforts to mitigate them, where no efforts are present, potential (theoretical) solutions are presented instead.

Given its distributed nature, open designs need to rely on very comprehensive documentation for development, replication and use, as potential users/codevelopers need to base themselves on that documentation to evaluate a) if a certain OSH equipment is suitable for a certain function; b) if they will have easy access to all the necessary components to build it c) if they have the necessary programming skills to install and debug software code when necessary. As there are no documentation standards for OSH (March 2020), the level and quality of OSH documentation differs substantially across different projects [27]. Developers write documentation based on what they consider important/critical, their skill levels and personal style. This leads to tools that are not necessarily user friendly and straightforward to implement, inhibiting the use of these tools, as well as preventing the creation of a wide user/collaborator base. Interim solutions for this issue include relying on existing information and tools from mature fields (such as OSS), and guidelines from OSH associations and organizations. In practice, developers can a) follow software best practices [77,78], b) certify their OSH project using the Open Source Hardware Association (OSHW) system [79], c) make their user documentation existing dedicated platforms [80–83]. A more long term solution for documentation is likely to be available soon, as volunteers are working with the German Institute for Standardization (DIN) on a DIN specification for OSH documentation [84] (public resource with development progress [85]).

Even when good documentation for OSH is present, the lack of necessary skills needed to develop and/or replicate projects can be a barrier to preventing wider adoption of OSH. Researchers in life sciences are not normally trained to work with electronics and/or to use fast prototyping tools, and without them, reproducing small projects could be seen as an extreme time consuming and uncertain task: There is no guarantee that replication efforts will lead to fully functional and calibrated tools, and this potential gamble, can end up shadowing potential OSH benefits. Our experience teaching researchers on Open Labware workshops [46], has shown that newcomers often face subtle issues, such as a poorly soldered wire, that would lead to aberrant equipment functioning. Such things are a bit hard to spot and are only found after all other possibilities have been ruled out. These issues

could inhibit further attempts in the field, even when such problems were corrected right away, as they make the building process look like a long and frustrating road. Having more extensive training programs or adding hardware development as part of elective curricula for life science undergrads could have a potential benefit in solving this issue. Moreover, if after training, students never actually get to develop tools, they would at least have a better understanding of the tools they use everyday, what kind of data they are able to produce, and would be able to spot faulty functioning much sooner. Another possible solution for this issue would be to create partnerships between engineering and life sciences labs/departments, where engineers could create tools based on biologists needs, and biologists could test them with experiments, generating a good opportunity to solve many problems at once (equipment shortage in one lab, material and data for publications/student thesis, knowhow to supply tools locally for other labs/institutions).

The lack of traditional distribution channels can still be a barrier for adoption in cases where users cannot reproduce OSH, or when labs/institutions need several units of the same device for teaching purposes (time becomes a bottleneck when dozens of boards need to be soldered and many parts 3D printed). In these situations it would be beneficial to leverage the structure present in traditional companies, as they have the necessary personnel, manufacturing skills and knowledge to go through health and safety product certification such as the CE certification ("*Conformité Européenne*" - European conformity in french) [86,87]. One possible reason OSH is still not being sold at scale by these companies is that it is not possible to "protect" it, and current collaboration methods between Academia and companies rely on technology transfer using patents and other intellectual protection mechanisms. It must be noted that even though this has proven beneficial for the academic institution in the short term, (as companies take on the task of further developing and commercially exploring their creations, while paying royalties), it is detrimental in the long run, as it stifles innovation and creates access barriers to different parts of the world, unable to pay the premium charged by supplying companies [5]. Filling this gap, "non-traditional" companies [18,19,21–25,54,88,89] are entering the market and producing, selling and/or acting

as third party vendors of OSH. Even though this is a step in the right direction, they are only providing a fraction of the currently available open tools (Fig 1). Based on the idea that OSH should be provided as a service (in the same way OSS companies operate), most of these are fairly young and are still finding the proper way to sustain themselves and what business models work for them. Some are relying on collecting batch orders using online platforms and only producing goods once a minimum number of orders is made, so that they are cost-effective [90], some of the most established ones rely on traditional business models with online shops [18,19] and one company has raised external venture capital [56]. All these companies are making the case that open does not mean non-profitable (as shown time and again for OSS), and creating a precedent that could influence how OSH is seen by traditional companies.

Selling OSH tools also comes with its own particularities, as the selling parties have to be excellent service providers (as their products could be sold with the same quality by competing companies) and products have an unofficial price cap (the point where users would rather build a tool, than pay a price they deem too high). Making the situation better for companies is the fact that they do not have to invest heavily on research and development as tools are being created inside labs by researchers and released for anyone to use/commercially explore. Taken together these particularities allow the benefits of open source and the provision of good customer service to reach a wider audience, generating significant social gains.

Outlook

In this synopsis, points were made for the use of OSH in academia. Benefits include lower costs, increased accessibility via local production, the potential to increase research result turnover with improved quality by tighter calibration of instruments, parallelisation and automation of experiments. Additionally, the use/build of OSH enables researchers to have a better grasp on how their tools work and what are their limitations and capabilities, directly influencing experimental designs and what kind of questions they will help to elucidate.

Although these ideas are not new, it was only due to recent advancements in electronics, fast prototyping, and documentation infrastructure that the entry barrier

for developing research equipment has been sufficiently lowered so that many labs can enter this space. In the brief 5 years period since Baden *et al* [12] made the argument for researchers to join the maker movement, we have seen an increase in the number of projects published every year, an increase in the complexity of these projects and an increased number of projects that base themselves on previous OSH publications to produce new tools (Fig 1). All these indicate that we are in the beginning of an OSH “Cambrian explosion” where many new designs are appearing and evolving as people start to use, improve and make derivatives of them.

As it evolves, the field of OSH is going to bring tools that functionally surpass their proprietary counterparts and contribute to a faster and better development of science on a technical level. On the social side, OSH development is bringing together communities and labs that were previously working in isolation to share knowledge and lessons learned in different socio-economics settings, and to form a unified front to push for the wide adoption of open science hardware [91–93]. This ethos also brings OSH close to Open Science communities, that are pushing an agenda for fairer, transparent and more equitable research.

References

1. Skinner BF, Ferster CB. Schedules of Reinforcement. B. F. Skinner Foundation; 2015.
2. Hodgkin AL, Huxley AF. A quantitative description of membrane current and its application to conduction and excitation in nerve. *J Physiol.* 1952;117: 500–544.
3. The Nobel Prize in Physiology or Medicine 1963. In: NobelPrize.org [Internet]. [cited 16 Nov 2019]. Available: <https://www.nobelprize.org/prizes/medicine/1963/summary/>
4. admin. The Nobel Prizes in the field of neuroscience. In: The Nobel Prize in Physiology or Medicine [Internet]. [cited 16 Nov 2019]. Available: <https://www.nobelprizemedicine.org/selecting-laureates/history/the-nobel-prizes-in-the-field-of-neuroscience/>
5. Chagas AM. Haves and have nots must find a better way: The case for open scientific hardware. *PLOS Biology.* 2018;16: e3000014. doi:10.1371/journal.pbio.3000014
6. Marder E. Living Science: The haves and the have nots. In: eLife [Internet]. 19 Nov 2013 [cited 17 Aug 2018]. doi:10.7554/eLife.01515
7. Perry L, Malkin R. Effectiveness of medical equipment donations to improve health systems: how much medical equipment is broken in the developing world? *Med Biol Eng Comput.* 2011;49: 719–722. doi:10.1007/s11517-011-0786-3
8. Pixy2 – PixyCam. [cited 19 Oct 2019]. Available: <https://pixycam.com/pixy2/>
9. Small - Affordable - Expandable. In: OpenMV [Internet]. [cited 19 Oct 2019]. Available: <https://openmv.io/>
10. Glowforge - the 3D laser printer | Glowforge. [cited 10 Nov 2019]. Available: <https://glowforge.com/>
11. Prusa3D - Open-Source 3D Printers from Josef Prusa. In: Prusa3D - 3D Printers from Josef Průša [Internet]. [cited 10 Nov 2019]. Available: <https://www.prusa3d.com/>
12. Baden T, Chagas AM, Gage G, Marzullo T, Prieto-Godino LL, Euler T. Open Labware: 3-D Printing Your Own Lab Equipment. *PLOS Biology.* 2015;13: e1002086. doi:10.1371/journal.pbio.1002086
13. Chagas AM, Prieto-Godino LL, Arrenberg AB, Baden T. The €100 lab: A 3D-printable open-source platform for fluorescence microscopy, optogenetics, and accurate temperature control during behaviour of zebrafish, *Drosophila*, and *Caenorhabditis elegans*. *PLOS Biology.* 2017;15: e2002702. doi:10.1371/journal.pbio.2002702
14. Franke K, Maia Chagas A, Zhao Z, Zimmermann MJ, Bartel P, Qiu Y, et al. An arbitrary-spectrum spatial visual stimulator for vision research. Borst A, editor. *eLife.* 2019;8: e48779. doi:10.7554/eLife.48779
15. Morin A, Urban J, Sliz P. A Quick Guide to Software Licensing for the Scientist-Programmer. *PLOS Computational Biology.* 2012;8: e1002598. doi:10.1371/journal.pcbi.1002598
16. Eric S. Raymond. Cathedral and the Bazaar. Available: <http://archive.org/details/CathedralAndTheBazaar>
17. Muller E, Bednar JA, Diesmann M, Gewaltig M-O, Hines M, Davison AP. Python in neuroscience. *Front Neuroinform.* 2015;9. doi:10.3389/fninf.2015.00011
18. SparkFun Electronics. [cited 17 Aug 2019]. Available: <https://www.sparkfun.com/>
19. Adafruit Industries, Unique & fun DIY electronics and kits. [cited 17 Aug 2019]. Available: <https://www.adafruit.com/>
20. Sanworks. [cited 17 Aug 2019]. Available: <https://sanworks.io/shop/viewproduct?productID=1102>
21. publications using open ephys. In: Open Ephys [Internet]. [cited 9 Aug 2019]. Available: <http://www.open-ephys.org/publications>
22. Backyard Brains. [cited 24 Aug 2019]. Available: <https://backyardbrains.com/>
23. Olimex. OLIMEX LTD - OLinuXino Arduino Maple Pinguino ARM Open Source Hardware

- Development Boards. In: Olimex [Internet]. [cited 20 Oct 2019]. Available: <https://www.olimex.com/>
24. NeuroTinker. [cited 24 Aug 2019]. Available: <https://www.neurotinker.com/>
 25. OpenBCI - Open Source Biosensing Tools (EEG, EMG, EKG, and more). [cited 24 Aug 2019]. Available: <https://openbci.com/>
 26. Gibb A. Building Open Source Hardware: DIY Manufacturing for Hackers and Makers. Addison-Wesley Professional; 2014.
 27. Bonvoisin J, Mies R, Boujut J-F, Stark R. What is the “Source” of Open Source Hardware? *Journal of Open Hardware*. 2017;1. doi:10.5334/joh.7
 28. Pearce JM. The case for open source appropriate technology. *Environ Dev Sustain*. 2012;14: 425–431. doi:10.1007/s10668-012-9337-9
 29. Pearce JM. Building Research Equipment with Free, Open-Source Hardware. *Science*. 2012;337: 1303–1304. doi:10.1126/science.1228183
 30. Steffens S, Nüßler L, Seiler T-B, Ruchter N, Schumann M, Döring R, et al. A versatile and low-cost open source pipetting robot for automation of toxicological and ecotoxicological bioassays. *PLOS ONE*. 2017;12: e0179636. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0179636
 31. Zhang C, Anzalone NC, Faria RP, Pearce JM. Open-Source 3D-Printable Optics Equipment. *PLOS ONE*. 2013;8: e59840. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0059840
 32. Nuñez I, Matute T, Herrera R, Keymer J, Marzullo T, Rudge T, et al. Low cost and open source multi-fluorescence imaging system for teaching and research in biology and bioengineering. *PLOS ONE*. 2017;12: e0187163. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0187163
 33. Switz NA, D’Ambrosio MV, Fletcher DA. Low-Cost Mobile Phone Microscopy with a Reversed Mobile Phone Camera Lens. *PLOS ONE*. 2014;9: e95330. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0095330
 34. Pitrone PG, Schindelin J, Stuyvenberg L, Preibisch S, Weber M, Eliceiri KW, et al. OpenSPIM: an open-access light-sheet microscopy platform. *Nature Methods*. 2013;10: 598–599. doi:10.1038/nmeth.2507
 35. Geissmann Q, Rodriguez LG, Beckwith EJ, French AS, Jamasb AR, Gilestro GF. Ethoscopes: An open platform for high-throughput ethomics. *PLOS Biology*. 2017;15: e2003026. doi:10.1371/journal.pbio.2003026
 36. Sharkey JP, Foo DCW, Kabla A, Baumberg JJ, Bowman RW. A one-piece 3D printed flexure translation stage for open-source microscopy. *Review of Scientific Instruments*. 2016;87: 025104. doi:10.1063/1.4941068
 37. Thingiverse.com. Search Thingiverse - Eppendorf. [cited 8 Aug 2019]. Available: <https://www.thingiverse.com/search?q=eppendorf&dwh=245d4bfd22e93bc>
 38. Thingiverse.com. Search Thingiverse - Vial Racks. [cited 8 Aug 2019]. Available: <https://www.thingiverse.com/search?q=vial+racks&dwh=395d4bfd6d60eed>
 39. Winters BJ, Shepler D. 3D printable optomechanical cage system with enclosure. *HardwareX*. 2018;3: 62–81. doi:10.1016/j.ohx.2017.12.001
 40. Banggood.com. £159.01 % Creality 3D® Ender-3 V-slot Prusa I3 DIY 3D Printer Kit 220x220x250mm Printing Size With Power Resume Function/MK10 Extruder 1.75mm 0.4mm Nozzle 3D Printer & Supplies from Electronics on banggood.com. In: www.banggood.com [Internet]. [cited 7 Aug 2019]. Available: <https://www.banggood.com/Creality-3D-Ender-3-V-slot-Prusa-I3-DIY-3D-Printer-Kit-220x220x250mm-Printing-Size-p-1278399.html>
 41. Eppendorf 022674048 Tube Holder For 24 x 1.5 ml or 2.0 ml Micro Test Tubes: Amazon.co.uk: Welcome. [cited 7 Aug 2019]. Available: <https://www.amazon.co.uk/Eppendorf-022674048-Holder-Micro-Tubes/dp/B005GRGCGI?psc=1&SubscriptionId=AKIAILSHYYTFIVPWUY6Q&tag=duc08-21&linkCode=xm2&camp=2025&creative=165953&creativeASIN=B005GRGCGI>
 42. Pearce JM. Return on investment for open source scientific hardware development. *Sci Public Policy*. 2016;43: 192–195. doi:10.1093/scipol/scv034

43. Urban PL. Open-Source Electronics As a Technological Aid in Chemical Education. *J Chem Educ.* 2014;91: 751–752. doi:10.1021/ed4009073
44. Gutierrez-Heredia L, Keogh C, Reynaud EG. Assessing the Capabilities of Additive Manufacturing Technologies for Coral Studies, Education, and Monitoring. *Front Mar Sci.* 2018;5. doi:10.3389/fmars.2018.00278
45. Davis EJ, Jones M, Thiel DA, Pauls S. Using Open-Source, 3D Printable Optical Hardware To Enhance Student Learning in the Instrumental Analysis Laboratory. *J Chem Educ.* 2018;95: 672–677. doi:10.1021/acs.jchemed.7b00480
46. Quinn AM, Paffhausen B, Chagas AM. Implementation of a Novel Educational Course to Teach 3D Printing, Circuit Design, and Programming to PhD Candidates in Nigeria. *SocArXiv.* 2017 [cited 20 Aug 2018]. doi:10.31235/osf.io/pyh2r
47. Heradio R, Chacon J, Vargas H, Galan D, Saenz J, Torre LDL, et al. Open-Source Hardware in Education: A Systematic Mapping Study. *IEEE Access.* 2018;6: 72094–72103. doi:10.1109/ACCESS.2018.2881929
48. Siegle JH, Wilson MA. Enhancement of encoding and retrieval functions through theta phase-specific manipulation of hippocampus. Eichenbaum H, editor. *eLife.* 2014;3: e03061. doi:10.7554/eLife.03061
49. open-ephys github repository. In: GitHub [Internet]. [cited 12 Aug 2019]. Available: <https://github.com/open-ephys>
50. Siegle JH, López AC, Patel YA, Abramov K, Ohayon S, Voigts J. Open Ephys: an open-source, plugin-based platform for multichannel electrophysiology. *J Neural Eng.* 2017;14: 045003. doi:10.1088/1741-2552/aa5eea
51. Newman JP, Fong M, Millard DC, Whitmire CJ, Stanley GB, Potter SM. Optogenetic feedback control of neural activity. *eLife.* 4. doi:10.7554/eLife.07192
52. Voigts J, Siegle JH, Pritchett DL, Moore CI. The flexDrive: an ultra-light implant for optical control and highly parallel chronic recording of neuronal ensembles in freely moving mice. *Front Syst Neurosci.* 2013;7. doi:10.3389/fnsys.2013.00008
53. Sanders JI, Kepecs A. A low-cost programmable pulse generator for physiology and behavior. *Front Neuroeng.* 2014;7. doi:10.3389/fneng.2014.00043
54. Opentrons | Open-source Pipetting Robots for Biologists. [cited 13 Aug 2019]. Available: https://opentrons.com/?msclkid=68f95fd6d54214ebc7090284716fa490&utm_source=bing&utm_medium=cpc&utm_campaign=Branded&utm_term=opentrons&utm_content=General
55. Maker SynBio: Empowering Biodevelopers with Automation | ITP Thesis 2014. [cited 1 Sep 2019]. Available: <https://itp.nyu.edu/shows/thesis2014/will-canine/>
56. Woods T. How a biotech robotics startup founded in a community hackerspace by a leftist activist just raised \$10 million. In: *Technical.ly Brooklyn* [Internet]. 29 Mar 2018 [cited 1 Sep 2019]. Available: <https://technical.ly/brooklyn/2018/03/29/opentrons-will-canine-funding-round/>
57. Wijnen B, Hunt EJ, Anzalone GC, Pearce JM. Open-Source Syringe Pump Library. *PLOS ONE.* 2014;9: e107216. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0107216
58. OpenPCR - the \$499 Open Source PCR Machine / Thermal Cycler. [cited 13 Aug 2019]. Available: <https://openpcr.org/>
59. Polyfuge: A DIY Open-Source Microcentrifuge for Everyone. In: *Kickstarter* [Internet]. [cited 13 Aug 2019]. Available: <https://www.kickstarter.com/projects/1733191226/polyfuge-a-diy-open-source-microcentrifuge-for-eve>
60. Sule SS, Petsiuk AL, Pearce JM. Open Source Completely 3-D Printable Centrifuge. *Instruments.* 2019;3: 30. doi:10.3390/instruments3020030
61. Dhankani KC, Pearce JM. Open source laboratory sample rotator mixer and shaker. *HardwareX.* 2017;1: 1–12. doi:10.1016/j.ohx.2016.07.001
62. Itskov PM, Moreira J-M, Vinnik E, Lopes G, Safarik S, Dickinson MH, et al. Automated

- monitoring and quantitative analysis of feeding behaviour in *Drosophila*. *Nat Commun*. 2014;5: 4560. doi:10.1038/ncomms5560
63. Libey T, Fetz EE. Open-Source, Low Cost, Free-Behavior Monitoring, and Reward System for Neuroscience Research in Non-human Primates. *Front Neurosci*. 2017;11. doi:10.3389/fnins.2017.00265
 64. Ribeiro MW, Neto JFR, Morya E, Brasil FL, de Araújo MFP. OBAT: An open-source and low-cost operant box for auditory discriminative tasks. *Behav Res*. 2018;50: 816–825. doi:10.3758/s13428-017-0906-6
 65. Kretschmer F, Kretschmer V, Kunze VP, Kretzberg J. OMR-Arena: Automated Measurement and Stimulation System to Determine Mouse Visual Thresholds Based on Optomotor Responses. *PLOS ONE*. 2013;8: e78058. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0078058
 66. Wayland MT, Landgraf M. A Cartesian Coordinate Robot for Dispensing Fruit Fly Food. *Journal of Open Hardware*. 2018;2: 3. doi:10.5334/joh.9
 67. Rosenegger DG, Tran CHT, LeDue J, Zhou N, Gordon GR. A High Performance, Cost-Effective, Open-Source Microscope for Scanning Two-Photon Microscopy that Is Modular and Readily Adaptable. *PLOS ONE*. 2014;9: e110475. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0110475
 68. Aharoni D, Hoogland TM. Circuit Investigations With Open-Source Miniaturized Microscopes: Past, Present and Future. *Front Cell Neurosci*. 2019;13. doi:10.3389/fncel.2019.00141
 69. Stewart C, Giannini J. Inexpensive, Open Source Epifluorescence Microscopes. *J Chem Educ*. 2016;93: 1310–1315. doi:10.1021/acs.jchemed.5b00984
 70. Dryden MDM, Fobel R, Fobel C, Wheeler AR. Upon the Shoulders of Giants: Open-Source Hardware and Software in Analytical Chemistry. *Anal Chem*. 2017;89: 4330–4338. doi:10.1021/acs.analchem.7b00485
 71. Grier Z, Soddu MF, Kenyatta N, Odame SA, Sanders J, Wright L, et al. A low-cost do-it-yourself microscope kit for hands-on science education. *Optics Education and Outreach V. International Society for Optics and Photonics*; 2018. p. 107410K. doi:10.1117/12.2320655
 72. Mayne R, Morgan J, Whiting JGH, Phillips N, Adamatzky A. On measuring nanoparticle toxicity and clearance with *Paramecium caudatum*. *Sci Rep*. 2019;9: 1–9. doi:10.1038/s41598-019-45353-2
 73. Tristan-Landin SB, Gonzalez-Suarez AM, Jimenez-Valdes RJ, Garcia-Cordero JL. Facile assembly of an affordable miniature multicolor fluorescence microscope made of 3D-printed parts enables detection of single cells. *bioRxiv*. 2019; 592170. doi:10.1101/592170
 74. Sanderson T, Rayner JC. PlasmoTron: an open-source platform for automated culture of malaria parasites. *BioRxiv*. 2018; 241596. doi:10.1101/241596
 75. Drackley B, Holtz M, Yang J. An inexpensive modified weight-bearing device assembled in-house for high throughput unbiased behavioral pain assessment in mice. *HardwareX*. 2018;4: e00031. doi:10.1016/j.ohx.2018.e00031
 76. Hoang T, Moskwa N, Halvorsen K. A ‘smart’ tube holder enables real-time sample monitoring in a standard lab centrifuge. *PLOS ONE*. 2018;13: e0195907. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0195907
 77. Sholler D, Steinmacher I, Ford D, Averick M, Hoyer M, Wilson G. Ten simple rules for helping newcomers become contributors to open projects. *PLOS Computational Biology*. 2019;15: e1007296. doi:10.1371/journal.pcbi.1007296
 78. Bahamdain SS. Open Source Software (OSS) Quality Assurance: A Survey Paper. *Procedia Computer Science*. 2015;56: 459–464. doi:10.1016/j.procs.2015.07.236
 79. OSHA Certification. [cited 22 Mar 2020]. Available: <https://certification.osha.org/>
 80. Dozuki. Standard Work Instruction Software for Manufacturing. [cited 13 Apr 2020]. Available: <https://www.dozuki.com>
 81. DocuBricks. [cited 13 Apr 2020]. Available: <http://docubricks.com/>
 82. Wikifab. [cited 13 Apr 2020]. Available: <https://wikifab.org/wiki/Accueil>
 83. The social platform for collaborative product development. In: Wikifactory [Internet]. [cited 13 Apr 2020]. Available: <https://wikifactory.com/>

84. DIN - German Institute for Standardization. [cited 23 Mar 2020]. Available: <https://www.din.de/en/wdc-beuth:din21:313396436>
85. Häuer M. Open Source Hardware in industry – meet DIN SPEC 3105. Available: </v/36c3-oio-192-open-source-hardware-in-industry-meet-din-spec-3105>
86. European Union Documents. Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs - Manufacturers. In: Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs - European Commission [Internet]. 5 Jul 2016 [cited 25 Mar 2020]. Available: https://ec.europa.eu/growth/single-market/ce-marking/manufacturers_en
87. CE marking. In: Your Europe - Business [Internet]. [cited 13 Apr 2020]. Available: https://europa.eu/youreurope/business/product-requirements/labels-markings/ce-marking/index_en.htm
88. IO Rodeo. In: IO Rodeo [Internet]. [cited 20 Oct 2019]. Available: <https://iorodeo.com/>
89. Sci-Bots. [cited 13 Apr 2020]. Available: <https://sci-bots.com/>
90. Hill AP, Davies A, Prince P, Snaddon JL, Doncaster CP, Rogers A. Leveraging conservation action with open-source hardware. *Conservation Letters*. 2019;12: e12661. doi:10.1111/conl.12661
91. GOSH Manifesto. In: Gathering for Open Science Hardware [Internet]. [cited 20 Aug 2018]. Available: <http://openhardware.science/gosh-manifesto/>
92. GOSH Community Forum. In: GOSH Community Forum [Internet]. [cited 20 Aug 2018]. Available: <http://forum.openhardware.science/>
93. MakerNetAlliance. OpenKnowHow. In: StandardsRepo: Better documents, faster [Internet]. [cited 20 Oct 2019]. Available: <https://app.standardsrepo.com/MakerNetAlliance/OpenKnowHow>

List of appended manuscripts contributions

Open Labware: 3-D Printing Your Own Lab Equipment

Tom Baden , Andre Maia Chagas, Greg Gage, Timothy Marzullo, Lucia L. Prieto-Godino, Thomas Euler

PLoS Biol 13(3): e1002086 doi:[10.1371/journal.pbio.1002086](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.1002086)

Abstract

The introduction of affordable, consumer-oriented 3-D printers is a milestone in the current “maker movement,” which has been heralded as the next industrial revolution. Combined with free and open sharing of detailed design blueprints and accessible development tools, rapid prototypes of complex products can now be assembled in one’s own garage—a game-changer reminiscent of the early days of personal computing. At the same time, 3-D printing has also allowed the scientific and engineering community to build the “little things” that help a lab get up and running much faster and easier than ever before

Contributions

Contributions follow [CRedit Taxonomy](#). Extra detailing is given for Andre’s contributions

Tom Baden: Conceptualization, ideas, Methodology, Supervision, Visualization, Writing - original draft, Writing review & editing

Andre Maia Chagas: Conceptualization, Methodology, Visualization, Writing - original draft, Writing review & editing

- Conceptualization
- Methodology: taught part of the workshops described in the paper
- Visualization: collected data and created tables I & II
- Writing - original draft: Parts of introduction, open source explanation and policy suggestion.
- Writing - review & editing: responding reviewers comments and changing manuscript where necessary

Greg Gage: Methodology, Resources, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing

Timothy Marzullo: Methodology, Resources, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing

Lucia L. Prieto-Godino: Methodology, Resources, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing

Thomas Euler: Funding acquisition, Methodology, Resources, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing

The €100 lab: A 3D-printable open-source platform for fluorescence microscopy, optogenetics, and accurate temperature control during behaviour of zebrafish, *Drosophila*, and *Caenorhabditis elegans*

Andre Maia Chagas, Lucia L. Prieto-Godino, Aristides B. Arrenberg, Tom Baden

PLoS Biol 15(7): e2002702 doi: [10.1371/journal.pbio.2002702](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.2002702)

Abstract

Small, genetically tractable species such as larval zebrafish, *Drosophila*, or *Caenorhabditis elegans* have become key model organisms in modern neuroscience. In addition to their low maintenance costs and easy sharing of strains across labs, one key appeal is the possibility to monitor single or groups of animals in a behavioural arena while controlling the activity of select neurons using optogenetic or thermogenetic tools. However, the purchase of a commercial solution for these types of experiments, including an appropriate camera system as well as a controlled behavioural arena, can be costly. Here, we present a low-cost and modular open-source alternative called 'FlyPi'. Our design is based on a 3D-printed mainframe, a Raspberry Pi computer, and high-definition camera system as well as Arduino-based optical and thermal control circuits. Depending on the configuration, FlyPi can be assembled for well under €100 and features optional modules for light-emitting diode (LED)-based fluorescence microscopy and optogenetic stimulation as well as a Peltier-based temperature stimulator for thermogenetics. The complete version with all modules costs approximately €200 or substantially less if the user is prepared to 'shop around'. All functions of FlyPi can be controlled through a custom-written graphical user interface. To demonstrate FlyPi's capabilities, we present its use in a series of state-of-the-art neurogenetics experiments. In addition, we demonstrate FlyPi's utility as a medical diagnostic tool as well as a teaching aid at Neurogenetics courses held at several African universities. Taken together, the low cost and modular nature as well as fully open design of FlyPi make it a highly versatile tool in a range of applications, including the classroom, diagnostic centres, and research labs.

Contributions

Contributions follow [CRediT Taxonomy](#). Extra detailing is given for Andre's contributions

Andre Maia Chagas: Conceptualization, Data curation, Methodology, Software, Validation, Visualization, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing.

- Conceptualization
- Data curation: preparation of paper repository, creation and update of materials lists, connection of the repository to specialized research engines (kitspace.org, open-knowhow.org)
- Methodology:
 - Hardware development (electronics, PCB), 3D printed parts, writing assembly and user manual
 - Software: Refactored arduino code, Graphical user interface implementation
 - Validation: Prototype testing, data acquisition and software design and implementation, validation, writing, review.
 - Visualization: Figure creation, data preparation for figures.
 - Writing - Original draft: Writing methodology part, contextualization with other tools and literature review.
 - Writing - review & editing: responding reviewers comments and changing manuscript where necessary

Lucia Prieto Godino: Methodology, Resources, Validation, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing Validation, writing, review

Aristides B Arrenberg: Methodology, Resources, Validation, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing.

Tom Baden: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Resources, Formal Analysis, Funding Acquisition, Hardware and software design and implementation, validation, writing, review

Haves and have nots must find a better way: The case for open scientific hardware

André Maia Chagas

PLoS Biol 16(9): e3000014 doi: [10.1371/journal.pbio.3000014](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.3000014)

Abstract

Many efforts are making science more open and accessible; they are mostly concentrated on issues that appear before and after experiments are performed: open access journals, open databases, and many other tools to increase reproducibility of science and access to information. However, these initiatives do not promote access to scientific equipment necessary for experiments. Mostly due to monetary constraints, equipment availability has always been uneven around the globe, affecting predominantly low-income countries and institutions. Here, a case is made for the use of free open source hardware in research and education, including countries and institutions where funds were never the biggest problem.

Contributions

Contributions follow [CRediT Taxonomy](#). Extra detailing is given for Andre's contributions

Andre Maia Chagas: Conceptualization, writing - original draft, visualization, writing - review and editing.

An arbitrary-spectrum spatial visual stimulator for vision research

Katrin Franke*, André Maia Chagas*, Zhijian Zhao, Maxime JY Zimmermann, Philipp Bartel, Yongrong Qiu, Klaudia P Szatko, Tom Baden, Thomas Euler

* equal contributions

eLife 2019;8:e48779 doi: [10.7554/eLife.48779](https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.48779)

Abstract

Visual neuroscientists require accurate control of visual stimulation. However, few stimulator solutions simultaneously offer high spatio-temporal resolution and free control over the spectra of the light sources, because they rely on off-the-shelf technology developed for human trichromatic vision. Importantly, consumer displays fail to drive UV-shifted short wavelength-sensitive photoreceptors, which strongly contribute to visual behaviour in many animals, including mice, zebrafish and fruit flies. Moreover, many non-mammalian species feature more than three spectral photoreceptor types. Here, we present a flexible, spatial visual stimulator with up to six arbitrary spectrum chromatic channels. It combines a standard digital light processing engine with open source hard- and software that can be easily adapted to the experimentalist's needs. We demonstrate the capability of this general visual stimulator experimentally in the in vitro mouse retinal whole-mount and the in vivo zebrafish. With this work, we intend to start a community effort of sharing and developing a common stimulator design for vision research.

Contributions

Contributions follow [CRedit Taxonomy](#). Extra detailing is given for Andre's contributions

Katrin Franke*: Conceptualization, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Visualization, Methodology, Writing—original draft, Writing—review and editing

Andre M Chagas*: Conceptualization, Validation, Methodology, Writing—original draft, Writing—review and editing

- Conceptualization
- Data Curation: preparation of paper repository, creation and update of materials lists, connection of the repository to specialized research engines (kitspace.org, open-knowhow.org)
- Methodology:
 - Design of electronic circuits which solved synchronization and timing issues between stimulators and 2 Photon recording system.
 - Design of led drivers that could be synchronised with the system and could take a wide range of LEDs
 - Co-designed optical path of “through the objective” setup with Zhijian Zhao,
 - Designed and implemented optical chopper solution,
 - Wrote the first draft of calibration scripts for mouse retina.
- Validation: Tests of the stimulators, proof-of-principle data collection (retina recordings) and analysis.
- Writing - original draft: Method description, parts of the introduction.
- Writing - review and editing: responding reviewers comments and changing manuscript where necessary.

Zhijian Zhao: Conceptualization, Validation, Visualization, Methodology, Writing—review and editing

Maxime JY Zimmermann: Conceptualization, Validation, Investigation, Visualization, Writing—review and editing

Phillip Bartel: Validation, Methodology

Yongrong Qiu: Validation, Methodology

Klaudia P Szatko: Validation, Methodology

Tom Baden: Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Visualization, Writing—review and editing

Thomas Euler: Conceptualization, Software, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Visualization, Methodology, Writing—original draft, Writing—review and editing

* equal contributions

Appended Manuscripts

Open Labware: 3-D Printing Your Own Lab Equipment

Tom Baden^{1,2,3,4*}, Andre Maia Chagas^{1,2,4,5,6}, Greg Gage⁷, Timothy Marzullo⁷, Lucia L. Prieto-Godino^{4,8}, Thomas Euler^{1,2,3}

1 Werner Reichardt Centre for Integrative Neuroscience (CIN), University of Tübingen, Tübingen, Germany, **2** Bernstein Centre for Computational Neuroscience, University of Tübingen, Tübingen, Germany, **3** Institute for Ophthalmic Research, University of Tübingen, Tübingen, Germany, **4** TReND in Africa gUG, Tübingen, Germany, **5** Hertie Institute for Clinical Brain research, University of Tübingen, Tübingen, Germany, **6** Graduate School of Neural and Behavioural Sciences, International Max Planck Research School, University of Tübingen, Germany, **7** Backyard Brains, Ann Arbor, Michigan, United States of America, **8** Centre for Integrative Genomics, University of Lausanne, Lausanne, Switzerland

* thomas.baden@uni-tuebingen.de

 OPEN ACCESS

Citation: Baden T, Chagas AM, Gage G, Marzullo T, Prieto-Godino LL, Euler T (2015) Open Labware: 3-D Printing Your Own Lab Equipment. *PLoS Biol* 13(3): e1002086. doi:10.1371/journal.pbio.1002086

Published: March 20, 2015

Copyright: © 2015 Baden et al. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Funding: This work was supported by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG) (Werner Reichardt Centre for Integrative Neuroscience Tübingen, EXC 307 to TE and TB; BA 5283/1-1 to TB) and the U.S. National Institutes of Mental Health Small Business Innovation Research grant #R44 MH093334 to GG and TM. The funders had no role in study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the manuscript.

Competing Interests: Authors GG and TM are founders of Backyard Brains (www.backyardbrains.com), a company specializing in the design and distribution of Open Labware.

Abbreviations: ABS, Acrylnitrile butadiene styrene; CNC, computer numerical control; DIY, Do It Yourself; EMG, Electromyogram; ERG, Electroretinogram; FOSSFA, Free Software and Open Source Foundation for Africa; GNU, "GNU is not Unix" (recursive acronym); GPIO, general-purpose input-

Abstract

The introduction of affordable, consumer-oriented 3-D printers is a milestone in the current "maker movement," which has been heralded as the next industrial revolution. Combined with free and open sharing of detailed design blueprints and accessible development tools, rapid prototypes of complex products can now be assembled in one's own garage—a game-changer reminiscent of the early days of personal computing. At the same time, 3-D printing has also allowed the scientific and engineering community to build the "little things" that help a lab get up and running much faster and easier than ever before.

Applications of 3-D printing technologies (Fig. 1A, Box 1) have become as diverse as the types of materials that can be used for printing. Replacement parts at the International Space Station may be printed in orbit from durable plastics or metals, while back on Earth the food industry is starting to explore the same basic technology to fold strings of chocolate into custom-shaped confectionary. Also, consumer-oriented laser-cutting technology makes it very easy to cut raw materials such as sheets of plywood, acrylic, or aluminum into complex shapes within seconds. The range of possibilities comes to light when those mechanical parts are combined with off-the-shelf electronics, low-cost microcontrollers like Arduino boards [1], and single-board computers such as a Beagleboard [2] or a Raspberry Pi [3]. After an initial investment of typically less than a thousand dollars (e.g., to set-up a 3-D printer), the only other materials needed to build virtually anything include a few hundred grams of plastic (approximately US\$30/kg), cables, and basic electronic components [4,5].

It therefore comes as no surprise that these technologies are also routinely used by research scientists and, especially, educators aiming to customize existing lab equipment or even build sophisticated lab equipment from scratch for a mere fraction of what commercial alternatives cost [6]. Designs for such "Open Labware" include simple mechanical adaptors [7],

output; IT, information technology; LED, Light Emitting Diode; NIH, National Institutes of Health; PCB, Printed Circuit Board; PLA, Polylactic acid; TRenD, Teaching and Research in Natural Sciences for Development (in Africa); UV, Ultraviolet.

Fig 1. Examples of open 3-D printed laboratory tools. **A₁**, Components for laboratory tools, such as the base for a micromanipulator [18] shown here, can be rapidly prototyped using 3-D printing. **A₂**, The printed parts can be easily combined with an off-the-shelf continuous rotation servo-motor (bottom) to motorize the main axis. **B₁**, A 3-D printable micropipette [8], designed in OpenSCAD [19], shown in full (left) and cross-section (right). **B₂**, The pipette consists of the printed parts (blue), two biro fillings with the spring, an off-the-shelf piece of tubing to fit the tip, and one screw used as a spacer. **B₃**, Assembly is complete with a laboratory glove or balloon spanned between the two main printed parts and sealed with tape to create an airtight bottom chamber continuous with the pipette tip. Accuracy is $\pm 2\text{--}10\ \mu\text{l}$ depending on printer precision, and total capacity of the system is easily adjusted using two variables listed in the source code, or accessed via the “Customizer” plugin on the thingiverse link [8]. See also the first table.

doi:10.1371/journal.pbio.1002086.g001

micropipettes (Fig. 1B) [8], and an egg-whisk-based centrifuge [9] as well as more sophisticated equipment such as an extracellular amplifier for neurophysiological experiments [10], a thermocycler for PCR [11], or a two-photon microscope [12]. At the same time, conceptually

Box 1. Glossary

Open source

A collective license that defines terms of free availability and redistribution of published source material. Terms include free and unrestricted distribution, as well as full access to source code/blueprints/circuit board designs and derived works. For details, see <http://opensource.org>.

Maker movement

Technology-oriented extension of the traditional “Do-it-Yourself (DIY)” movement, typically denoting specific pursuits in electronics, CNC (computer numerical control) tools such as mills and laser cutters, as well as 3-D printing and related technologies.

3-D printing

Technology to generate three-dimensional objects from raw materials based on computer models. Most consumer-oriented 3-D printers print in plastic by locally melting a strand of raw material at the tip (“hot-end”) and “drawing” a 3-D object in layers. Plastic materials include Acrylnitrile butadiene styrene (ABS) and Polylactic acid (PLA). Many variations of 3-D printers exist, including those based on laser-polymerization or fusion of resins or powdered raw materials (e.g., metal or ceramic printers).

Arduino boards

Inexpensive and consumer-oriented microcontroller boards built around simple processors. These boards offer a variety of interfaces (serial ports, I2C and CAN bus, etc.), μ s-timers, and multiple general-purpose input-output (GPIO) pins suitable for running simple, time-precise programs to control custom-built electronics.

Single board computers

Inexpensive single-board computers capable of running a mature operating system with graphical-user interface, such as Linux. Like microcontroller boards, they offer a variety of hardware interfaces and GPIO pins to control custom-built electronics.

related approaches are also being pursued in chemistry [13–15] and material sciences [16,17]. See also [Table 1](#).

A Culture of Sharing

Most makers share their designs under an open source license together with detailed assembly instructions in online repositories [20–22] such as the National Institutes of Health (NIH) 3-D print exchange [23] or in peer-reviewed journals [10,17,24–29]. As a result, anyone can freely use and modify them. This open culture, which has transformed the world of software engineering over the past decades, offers several advantages over traditional product design. First, designs are not only free, but are directly shaped by people who will actually use the final product. Second, building your own experimental equipment yields a much deeper understanding of the principles underlying its design and a better awareness of its limits. Third, manufacturing is immediate and local—thus empowering laboratories and schools located in difficult-to-

Table 1. Open Labware designs for a biology lab.

Area	Project	Source
Microscopy	Smartphone Microscope	http://www.instructables.com/id/10-Smartphone-to-digital-microscope-conversion
	iPad Microscope	http://www.thingiverse.com/thing:31632
	Raspberry Pi Microscope	http://www.thingiverse.com/thing:385308
	Foldscope	http://www.foldscope.com/
Molecular Biology	Thermocycler (PCR)	http://openpcr.org/
	Water bath	http://blog.labfab.cc/?p=47
	Centrifuge	http://www.thingiverse.com/thing:151406
	Dremelfuge	http://www.thingiverse.com/thing:1483
	Colorometer	http://www.thingiverse.com/thing:73910
	Micropipette	http://www.thingiverse.com/thing:255519
	Gel Comb	http://www.thingiverse.com/thing:352873
	Hot Plate	http://www.instructables.com/id/Programmable-Temperature-Controller-Hot-Plate/
	Magnetic Stirrer	http://www.instructables.com/id/How-to-Build-a-Magnetic-Stirrer/
Electrophysiology	Waveform Generator	http://www.instructables.com/id/Arduino-Waveform-Generator/
	Open EEG	https://www.olimex.com/Products/EEG/OpenEEG/
	Mobile ECG	http://mobilecg.hu/
	Extracellular amplifier	https://backyardbrains.com/products/spikerBox
	Micromanipulator	http://www.thingiverse.com/thing:239105
Other	Open Ephys	http://open-ephys.org/
	Syringe pump	http://www.thingiverse.com/thing:210756
	Translational Stage	http://www.thingiverse.com/thing:144838
	Vacuum pump	http://www.instructables.com/id/The-simplest-vacuum-pump-in-the-world/
	Skinner Box	http://www.kscottz.com/open-skinner-box-pycon-2014/

See also [S1 Data](#).

doi:10.1371/journal.pbio.1002086.t001

reach places. Fourth, the open source movement is a global phenomenon, connecting people worldwide, often to recruit talented builders and coders from outside the traditional scientific establishment. Still, there are drawbacks. For example, a commercial solution may be preferred if the time and cost of in-house development exceeds the benefits of control and instrument knowledge. Nevertheless, and perhaps counter-intuitively, some open designs are published by commercial companies that offer the parts as well as the assembled product with technical support for a fee, while maintaining the source material online under an open source license. Consumers can more freely balance cost against time to build, while companies gain in customer relations and product feedback.

Quality Control and the Evolution of Open Labware Designs

The flagship of the open source movement, the operation system GNU/Linux [30], is perhaps the best example for the potential of open designs. First available in the 1990s, today it is one of the most widely used system on supercomputers, servers, and mobile phones (Android) and increases its share of home users every year. Critically, Linux is fully open source—anyone can freely access its entire source code, change it, and distribute modifications. Its success flows from the idea that “given enough eyeballs all bugs are shallow” [31]. In other words, a distributed network of collaborators helps to identify and rectify bugs in the system as they arise. Open Labware works the same way: release of a design sparks feedback and refinements from the

community. Although Open Labware’s contributor base is still relatively small, feedback can nonetheless markedly improve product design and expand potential applications over time. For example, free online sharing of the designs for a manually controlled 3-D printed micro-manipulator (Fig. 2A) [18] provided the starting point for a high-precision motorized version (Fig. 2B) [32]. Subsequently, and in combination with open designs for smartphone lens-adapters offering portable options for field-microscopy [33], both designs led to the “Raspberry Pi-scope” [34]—a self-standing histology microscope based on a Raspberry Pi, equipped with a high-resolution camera module, a low-cost acrylic lens, and the manipulator body to accurately position the sample (Fig. 2C). One next step in this evolution may be to add low-cost fluorescence capability through the addition of a ultraviolet light-emitting diode (UV-LED) and the appropriate filters, perhaps inspired by materials used in the less than US\$1 fluorescence-capable Foldscope [24]. Without free-and-open sharing of the complete source materials at all stages of development, this evolution would not have been possible. With educators and researchers increasingly integrating Open Labware approaches into their projects, designs are expected to continuously improve and diversify.

Online Resources for Learning and Problem Solving

Although most Open Labware designs are published with detailed assembly instructions aimed at the non-specialist, a basic understanding of concepts in physics, electronics, and computer programming is certainly helpful. Luckily, freely available online resources facilitate self-learning (Table 2). In addition, many makers hone their skills directly at the workbench, simply by attempting to recreate or modify existing designs. Expert community help can be rapidly found in online forums such as Stack Overflow [35], returning to the idea that many eyes lead to rapid problem-solving. In addition, online aggregators gather and summarize information on specific topics, serving as a hub for both information seekers and distributors. Some of them are curated in a centralized manner [36], while others follow the distributed wiki principle [37].

Application in a Resource-Challenged Context

If a commercial alternative is available, it is usually the compromise between time and money spent that determines whether to build or purchase equipment. While Open Labware designs may benefit any research or education setting [38], one obvious foothold for their possibilities lies in economically deprived schools and universities in the developing world. Here, the introduction of Open Labware may make the crucial difference between having some usable equipment to work with and having none at all. Several benefits of an open model come to light: low cost, local manufacture, and the possibility to customize according to local demands or availability of parts. In sub-Saharan Africa, only a few bases and organizations that offer training in “maker” skills or general promotion of open source principles operate. These include the Free Software and Open Source Foundation for Africa (FOSSFA [39]), Fundi bots [40], as well as a few physical spaces such as FabLabs [41] and Maker- [42] and Hackerspaces [43] scattered mostly around the major cities. In addition, companies selling easily transportable 3-D printers and supplies are rapidly establishing their foothold on the African continent, such that local sourcing of the required hardware is no longer an insurmountable obstacle. However, on the whole, Open Labware possibilities remain poorly established in this context, as attested in a survey taken by 89 biomedical researchers from 12 sub-Saharan African countries in August 2014 (Fig. 3). When asked about their software competency, most respondents indicated that while they are comfortable with “basic” IT usage (defined as using office packages or navigating the web), few were routine users of standard open analysis packages such as R [44], octave [45],

Fig 2. Evolution of an Open Labware design. A, A 3-D printable micromanipulator with a slanted Z-axis [18], here shown amidst commercial alternatives, initially served as the basis for a motorized version with

“real” Z axis [32] (B). **B**_{1,2}, the three axes are driven by continuous-rotation micro-servos, controlled by an Arduino fitted with a Joystick-shield and a 9V battery. **B**₃, The motorized manipulator offers sufficient precision to target individual hairs on the head of a fruitfly ($\pm 5\text{--}20\ \mu\text{m}$ during movements, depending on printer precision; $< 1\ \mu\text{m}\ \text{min}^{-1}$ when stationary). Scale bar 1 mm. **C**₁, The same manipulator build was then converted into a microscope-stage to permit accurate placement and focus of histology samples [34]. The optics are provided by an off-the-shelf, low-power acrylic lens positioned directly above a Raspberry Pi camera module [3]. **C**₂, Image taken with the microscope, showing a slice of mouse brain (hippocampus) stained for cytochrome oxidase C. Scale bar 500 μm .

doi:10.1371/journal.pbio.1002086.g002

or other Python [46] based packages, and programming skills were even less prevalent (Fig. 3A). Awareness and competency in the use of open hardware approaches were even less developed: over 90% of respondents (83/89) had never used 3-D printing or any form of single-board computers or microcontrollers (Fig. 3B).

As part of ongoing efforts to promote scientific education and research in the developing world, we introduced the many possibilities of Open Labware to schools and universities in sub-Saharan Africa (TRend in Africa [47]) and Latin America (Backyard Brains [48]). Different formats were used, ranging from three-week intensive neuroscience summer schools aimed at university graduates in Uganda and Tanzania (four events), to multiday MakerSpace workshops aimed at school students and their teachers in Chile and Mexico (12 events), to outreach events and lectures held at scientific conferences, schools, and public spaces on four continents (more than 100 events). Here, we present some experiences and success stories from this work.

In-Depth Exposure during Multiday Training Events

The longer events, such as the three-week neuroscience summer schools in Africa or the multiday MakerSpace workshops in Latin America, afforded participants the opportunity to get hands-on experience using, assembling, and contributing to the development of Open Labware designs. One popular activity was to assemble existing designs (such as a spikerbox, Fig. 4A [10,49]) from off-the-shelf parts. This required participants to study the circuit diagram, note the identity and polarity of simple electronic components such as chips and capacitors and to solder them in place on the printed circuit board (PCB) (Fig. 4B). The assembled amplifiers

Table 2. Open resources for self-taught learning of programming, electronics, and basic physics.

Project	Description	Source
Code.org	Well-structured teaching units to learn computer programming, mainly aimed at beginners.	http://code.org/
Code Academy	Teaches a wide range of programming languages based on brief explanations followed by exercise-based learning.	http://codecademy.com
Khan Academy	Promotes self-paced information technology (IT) education for high school curricula and beyond through videos and exercises.	http://khanacademy.org
Software carpentry	Aimed at scientists to improve coding and data management skills through online material, as well as offline lectures and bootcamps.	http://software-carpentry.org/
Sparkfun tutorials	Company selling electronic components—their website contains a free tutorial section teaching basic electronics.	https://learn.sparkfun.com/tutorials
Openeuroscience	Gathers open source projects for neurosciences.	http://openeuroscience.wordpress.com
Labrigger	Gathers both open and closed source software and hardware projects for biomedical research.	http://labrigger.com
Hackteria	Website that gathers open source projects for DIY biology	http://hackteria.org/wiki/index.php
Appropedia	Wiki page that gathers information on environmental, sustainability-related projects.	http://www.appropedia.org/
Openstax college	Non-profit foundation creating open college-level textbooks (e-books).	http://www.openstaxcollege.org

doi:10.1371/journal.pbio.1002086.t002

Fig 3. Open Labware at universities in sub-Saharan Africa. An online survey was taken by 89 biomedical researchers (MSc. to Professor) at universities in 12 different sub-Saharan African countries in August 2014. Researchers rated their own competency and awareness in aspects of software and hardware usage. **A**, Software competency rated on a scale of 1 (low) to 10 (high) in “basic usage such as navigating office software or the internet,” “usage of open analysis packages such as R [44], octave [45], or similar,” and “programming, e.g., using C++, python, or any other mainstream language.” **B**, Hardware awareness for possibilities in “3-D printing” (top) and “single board computers/microcontrollers such as Raspberry Pi, Arduino, Beagleboard, or similar” rated in four categories: (i) “I have never heard of this,” (ii) “I have heard of it but I have no access,” (iii) “I have tried using this at least once,” (iv) “I am a competent/routine user.”

doi:10.1371/journal.pbio.1002086.g003

were subsequently used to perform classic neurophysiological experiments such as recording of action potentials from the locust [50] or cricket [51,52] extensor tibiae (Fig 4C). Although initially daunting especially for the many participants without previous contact with any form

Fig 4. Hands-on exposure to Open Labware in the developing world. **A**, Each student assembled a spikerbox [10,49], an amplifier for neurophysiological experiments, from its off-the-shelf components. **B**, Students at a workshop in Dar es Salaam, Tanzania. **C**, The assembled amplifiers were subsequently used to perform simple neurophysiological experiments [51]. Image credit for panels B and C: Horst Schneider. **D**, One student set up a spikerbox via an Arduino to trigger closure of a “gripper-hand,” a low-cost robotic limb, through contractions of their forearm muscles.

doi:10.1371/journal.pbio.1002086.g004

of electrical engineering, the experience tended to be very motivating across ages and cultures. In particular, it contributed to take away the fear of experimenting with simple electronic circuits or opening up and attempting to modify or repair existing electronic tools in their daily environment. The low cost of required parts also allowed participants to build their own gear, rather than that of their school or university, making them more invested in its success and maintenance. Critically, building equipment from scratch often resulted in a high level of mechanistic understanding and a curiosity to “play” with the finished product to see if it can be improved or modified to better suit a particular purpose. For example, one undergraduate student linked an electromyogram (EMG)-amplifier to an off-the-shelf “robotic limb” [53] via an Arduino microcontroller [1] to remotely control grasping movements by contracting their forearm muscles (Fig. 4D). Clearly, introduction of low-cost and open source electronics and mechanical parts has the potential to open up vast possibilities to resourceful people anywhere in the world, independent of financial means or educational background.

During the three-week neuroscience summer schools in Uganda and Tanzania [54] we introduced participants to 3-D printed lab tools such as pipettes [8], manipulators [18,32], and microscope adapters [55] and compared the usefulness of self-built versus commercially available solutions for different types of experiments. For example, although printed pipettes [8] offer lower precision than commercially available ones ($\pm 2\text{--}10\ \mu\text{l}$, depending on printer precision) they are nonetheless adequate for many “low precision” tasks such as distributing diluted antibody solutions to different samples or applying mounting media for immunohistochemistry. Similarly, we used different versions of 3-D printed micromanipulators [18,32] to position reference electrodes during neurophysiological experiments, e.g., for *Calliphora* tangential cell recordings [56], but maintained the recording tungsten electrode on a more stable commercial manipulator. For some types of recordings, such as *Drosophila* electroretinograms (ERGs) [57], the printed manipulators were adequate to hold both electrodes, and the magnification gained by attaching a low-power acrylic lens to a webcam or smartphone easily sufficed for their accurate placement. We also provided access to pre-installed Raspberry Pi computers [3] running a range of open analysis and office software packages and provided basic training in their use. Hands-on exposure allowed students to judge for themselves which designs would be useful in their own research and teaching activities. In a subsequent survey, students rated the usefulness of every open design described above as at least nine out of ten on average ($n = 33$). We believe that the introduction of Open Labware possibilities to the African university system may be a highly effective measure towards fostering excellence in research and education on the continent.

Motivating More High School Graduates to Pursue a Career in Science

One pervasive issue in building a sustainable research infrastructure and scientific culture in resource-challenged countries is a perceived limit on career choices afforded by higher education. Traditionally, three disciplines—medicine, civil engineering, or law—are considered the best choices for reliable income, with few individuals enrolling in a natural science subject and fewer still ending up in active research [58,59]. To encourage students to consider a career in science, we (TReND and Backyard Brains) have participated in more than a hundred science outreach events around (Neuro)science, engaging more than 10,000 students, parents, and teachers. In several science camps (“ChileVA! [60]”), we gave two-hour lectures to high school students about the brain and how to record from neurons and muscles. The students not only “tolerated” this unusually long-format science lecture without breaks, but swarmed the

demonstration booth afterwards. Clearly, low-cost and portable equipment offers the possibility to perform science demonstrations anywhere, independent of local infrastructure.

In TReND's African activities, student-alumni of our summer workshops have taken over local science outreach by organizing into regional teams to visit schools and universities in their respective home countries [61]. Many of these young scientists come from similar backgrounds as the students they engage, allowing them to act as powerful role models. Thus, students attending a school that cannot afford the equipment or infrastructure to perform live experiments during science classes are exposed to local scientists with a similar background, handling equipment they know how to build from affordable, local resources. The experience can be very powerful and inspire them to pursue a similar career, as well as offering local teachers ideas to use in future science classes. This approach of "teaching the teachers" also means that the impact of educating a few students at a high level has the potential to trickle-down and achieve a wide impact in the long term.

Policy Recommendations

Clearly, the use and design of Open Labware designs can be a powerful ingredient to foster scientific research, education, and public science engagement. Their evolution spans several disciplines, from computer sciences and mechanical engineering to electronics and biology—thus connecting experts and the wider public across fields and sparking creativity in people of all ages. Their low cost, adaptability and robustness renders designs suitable for a broad range of applications in both teaching and research. Below we present some suggestions for policy implementations to optimize available possibilities.

1. Integrate more aspects of design and use of Open Labware into traditional science curricula, ideally at an early age.
2. Establish more hands-on training courses in basic hardware design and programming skills for established scientists and educators.
3. Establish infrastructural support to afford more students and educators easy and direct access to 3-D printing and related technologies. With 3-D printers starting at a few hundred dollars and their price steadily falling, schools and university departments should not be barred from investing in their own model because of economic reasons.
4. Provide incentives for companies to invest in an open model of product design. This move promises to spark a new generation of open companies in more direct dialogue with the end user, towards better, individually tailored, and more affordable product design.

Supporting Information

S1 Data. Thingiverse files. Container with all files mentioned in the article that are currently hosted on thingiverse (www.thingiverse.com).
(ZIP)

Acknowledgments

We thank the students and voluntary instructors of the many lectures and workshops mentioned in the manuscript, as well as the TReND outreach team, headed by Mahmoud Bukar Maina and Yunusa Mohammed Garba, for their ongoing efforts in promoting science education in Africa. We thank all sponsors of workshops, most notably including the International

Brain Research Organization (IBRO), The Company of Biologists, and the Cambridge Alborada Fund.

References

1. Arduino SA (2015) Arduino. <http://www.arduino.cc/>.
2. BeagleBoard.org Foundation (2014) Beagleboards. <http://beagleboard.org/>.
3. Raspberry Pi Foundation (2015) Raspberry Pi. <http://www.raspberrypi.org/>.
4. Anderson C (2012) Makers: The New Industrial Revolution. New York: Crown Business.
5. Levy S (2010) Hackers: Heroes of the Computer Revolution. 25th ed. O'Reilly Media.
6. Pearce JM (2013) Open-Source lab. 1st ed. Elsevier.
7. Zhang C, Anzalone NC, Faria RP, Pearce JM (2013) Open-source 3-D-printable optics equipment. *PLoS One* 8: e59840. doi: [10.1371/journal.pone.0059840](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0059840) PMID: [23544104](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/23544104/)
8. Baden T (2014) Biopette: customisable, high precision pipette. <http://www.thingiverse.com/thing:255519>.
9. Wong AP, Gupta M, Shevkopyas SS, Whitesides GM (2008) Egg beater as centrifuge: isolating human blood plasma from whole blood in resource-poor settings. *Lab Chip* 8: 2032–2037. doi: [10.1039/b809830c](https://doi.org/10.1039/b809830c) PMID: [19023465](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/19023465/)
10. Marzullo TC, Gage GJ (2012) The SpikerBox: a low cost, open-source bioamplifier for increasing public participation in neuroscience inquiry. *PLoS One* 7: e30837. doi: [10.1371/journal.pone.0030837](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0030837) PMID: [22470415](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/22470415/)
11. Chai Biotechnologies Inc (2014) OpenPCR. <http://openpccr.org/>.
12. Rosenegger DG, Tran CHT, LeDue J, Zhou N, Gordon GR (2014) A High Performance, Cost-Effective, Open-Source Microscope for Scanning Two-Photon Microscopy that Is Modular and Readily Adaptable. *PLoS One* 9: e110475. doi: [10.1371/journal.pone.0110475](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0110475) PMID: [25333934](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/25333934/)
13. Kitson PJ, Macdonell A, Tsuda S, Zang H, Long D-L, et al. (2014) Bringing Crystal Structures to Reality by Three-Dimensional Printing. *Cryst Growth Des* 14: 2720–2724.
14. Greenberg A (2009) Integrating nanoscience into the classroom: perspectives on nanoscience education projects. *ACS Nano* 3: 762–769. doi: [10.1021/nn900335r](https://doi.org/10.1021/nn900335r) PMID: [19397342](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/19397342/)
15. Gutierrez JMP, Hinkley T, Taylor JW, Yaney K, Cronin L (2014) Evolution of oil droplets in a chemorobotic platform. *Nat Commun* 5: 5571. doi: [10.1038/ncomms6571](https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms6571) PMID: [25482304](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/25482304/)
16. Pearce JM (2013) A Low-Cost Open-Source Metal 3-D Printer. *Academia.edu*. https://www.academia.edu/5327317/A_Low-Cost_Open-Source_Metal_3-D_Printer.
17. Pearce JM (2012) Materials science. Building research equipment with free, open-source hardware. *Science* 337: 1303–1304. doi: [10.1126/science.1228183](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1228183) PMID: [22984059](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/22984059/)
18. Marzullo T (2013) Searcher—3-D printable micromanipulator. <https://backyardbrains.com/products/micromanipulator>.
19. Kintel M (2014) OpenSCAD. <http://www.openscad.org/>.
20. MakerBot (2015) Thingiverse. <http://www.thingiverse.com/>.
21. Autodesk, Inc. (2014) Instructables. <http://www.instructables.com/>.
22. GitHub Inc (2015) GitHub. <https://github.com/>.
23. National Institutes of Health (2015) NIH 3-D print exchange. <http://3-Dprint.nih.gov/>.
24. Cybulski JS, Clements J, Prakash M (2014) Foldscope: origami-based paper microscope. *PLoS One* 9: e98781. doi: [10.1371/journal.pone.0098781](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0098781) PMID: [24940755](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/24940755/)
25. Sulkin MS, Widder E, Shao C, Holzem KM, Gloschat C, et al. (2013) Three-dimensional printing physiology laboratory technology. *Am J Physiol Heart Circ Physiol* 305: H1569–73. doi: [10.1152/ajpheart.00599.2013](https://doi.org/10.1152/ajpheart.00599.2013) PMID: [24043254](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/24043254/)
26. Lee WM, Upadhyaya A, Reece PJ, Phan TG (2014) Fabricating low cost and high performance elastomer lenses using hanging droplets. *Biomed Opt Express* 5: 1626–1635. doi: [10.1364/BOE.5.001626](https://doi.org/10.1364/BOE.5.001626) PMID: [24877020](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/24877020/)
27. Baker E (2014) Open source data logger for low-cost environmental monitoring. *Biodivers data J*: e1059.
28. Da Costa ET, Mora MF, Willis PA, do Lago CL, Jiao H, et al. (2014) Getting started with open-hardware: Development and control of microfluidic devices. *Electrophoresis* 35: 2370–2377. doi: [10.1002/elps.201400128](https://doi.org/10.1002/elps.201400128) PMID: [24823494](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/24823494/)

29. Bwambok DK, Christodouleas DC, Morin SA, Lange H, Phillips ST, et al. (2014) Adaptive use of bubble wrap for storing liquid samples and performing analytical assays. *Anal Chem* 86: 7478–7485. doi: 10.1021/ac501206m PMID: 24983331
30. XenoForo Ltd (2013) Linux. <http://www.linux.org/>.
31. Raymond ES (1999) *The Cathedral & the Bazaar: Musings on Linux and Open Source by an Accidental Revolutionary*. O'Reilly Media.
32. Baden T (2014) Parametric 3 axis manipulator—optional servo mounts. <http://www.thingiverse.com/thing:239105>.
33. Yoshinok. \$10 Smartphone to digital microscope conversion. <http://www.instructables.com/id/10-Smartphone-to-digital-microscope-conversion/>.
34. Baden T (2014) RPI-microscope for histology with focus-drive and XY stage. <http://www.thingiverse.com/thing:385308>.
35. Stack Exchange Inc (2015) Stack Overflow. <http://stackoverflow.com/>.
36. Chagas AM (2014) Openeuroscience. <http://openeuroscience.wordpress.com/>.
37. Appropedia. http://www.appropedia.org/Welcome_to_Appropedia.
38. Pearce JM (2013) Commentary: Open-source hardware for research and education. *Phys Today* 66: 8. <http://scitation.aip.org/content/aip/magazine/physicstoday/article/66/11/10.1063/PT.3.2160>.
39. Free Software and Open Source Foundation for Africa (FOSSFA). <http://www.fossfa.net/>.
40. Fundi Bots (2014) Fundi bots. <http://fundibots.org/>.
41. Fab Foundation (2014) Fab Labs. <http://www.fabfoundation.org/fab-labs/>.
42. Google. The Maker Map. <http://themakermap.com/>.
43. (2013) Hackerspaces. <http://hackerspaces.org/wiki/>.
44. Institute for Statistics and Mathematics of WU (Wirtschaftsuniversität Wien). R-project. <http://www.r-project.org/>.
45. Eaton JW (2013) GNU-Octave. <https://www.gnu.org/software/octave/>.
46. Pérez Fernando, Granger Brian E. (2007) IPython: A System for Interactive Scientific Computing. *Computing in Science and Engineering* 9: 21–29. <http://ipython.org>
47. Prieto Godino LL, Yusuf S, Baden T (2014) Teaching and Research in Natural Sciences for Development (TReND) in Africa. www.TReNDinAfrica.org.
48. Gage G, Marzullo T (2013) Backyard Brains. www.backyardbrains.com.
49. Backyard Brains. (2013) The Electromyogram (EMG) SpikerBox. <https://backyardbrains.com/products/emgspikerbox>.
50. Heitler WJ, Burrows M (1976) The Locust Jump. *Journal of Experimental Biology* 66: 221–241.
51. Dagda RK, Thalhauser RM, Dagda R, Marzullo TC, Gage GJ (2013) Using crickets to introduce neurophysiology to early undergraduate students. *J Undergrad Neurosci Educ* 12: A66–74. PMID: 24319394
52. Baden T, Hedwig B (2008) Front leg movements and tibial motoneurons underlying auditory steering in the cricket (*Gryllus bimaculatus* deGeer). *J Exp Biol* 211: 2123–2133. doi: 10.1242/jeb.019125 PMID: 18552302
53. SparkFun Electronics. Robotic Claw. <https://www.sparkfun.com/products/11524>.
54. Prieto Godino LL, Yusuf S, Baden T (2014) TReND in Africa Neuroscience Summer Schools. <http://trendinafrica.org/activities/education/neuroscience-schools/>.
55. MakerBot Industries (2015) Universal Smartphone adapter for microscope. <http://www.thingiverse.com/thing:78071>.
56. Krapp HG, Hengstenberg R (1996) Estimation of self-motion by optic flow processing in single visual interneurons. *Nature* 384: 463–466. PMID: 8945473
57. Montell C (1999) Visual transduction in *Drosophila*. *Annu Rev Cell Dev Biol* 15: 231–268. PMID: 10611962
58. Kolb H, Nelson R (1996) Hyperpolarizing, small-field, amacrine cells in cone pathways of cat retina. *JCompNeurol* 371: 415–436. PMID: 8842896
59. Irikefe V, Vaidyanathan G, Nordling L, Twahirwa A, Nakkazi E, et al. (2011) Science in Africa: The view from the front line. *Nature* 474: 556–559. doi: 10.1038/474556a PMID: 21720341
60. Chile VA! Innovacion. <http://www.innovacion.gob.cl/etiqueta/chile-va/>.
61. Maina MB, Garba YM (2013) TReND in Africa—Science Outreach. <http://trendinafrica.org/activities/outreach/>.

COMMUNITY PAGE

The €100 lab: A 3D-printable open-source platform for fluorescence microscopy, optogenetics, and accurate temperature control during behaviour of zebrafish, *Drosophila*, and *Caenorhabditis elegans*

Andre Maia Chagas^{1,2,3,4*}, Lucia L. Prieto-Godino^{3,5}, Aristides B. Arrenberg^{1,6}, Tom Baden^{1,3,4,7*}

1 Werner Reichardt Centre for Integrative Neuroscience, University of Tübingen, Tübingen, Germany, **2** Graduate school for Neural and Behavioural Neuroscience, University of Tübingen, Tübingen, Germany, **3** TRenD in Africa gUG, Bonn, Germany, **4** Institute of Ophthalmic Research, University of Tübingen, Tübingen, Germany, **5** Center of Integrative Genomics, University of Lausanne, Lausanne, Switzerland, **6** Institute of Neurobiology, University of Tübingen, Tübingen, Germany, **7** School of Life Sciences, University of Sussex, Brighton, United Kingdom

* andremaia.chagas@gmail.com (AMC); t.baden@sussex.ac.uk (TB)

OPEN ACCESS

Citation: Maia Chagas A, Prieto-Godino LL, Arrenberg AB, Baden T (2017) The €100 lab: A 3D-printable open-source platform for fluorescence microscopy, optogenetics, and accurate temperature control during behaviour of zebrafish, *Drosophila*, and *Caenorhabditis elegans*. PLoS Biol 15(7): e2002702. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.2002702>

Published: July 18, 2017

Copyright: © 2017 Maia Chagas et al. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Funding: H2020 ERC StG (grant number 677687). Support for TB. The funder had no role in study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the manuscript. Baden Wuerttemberg Stiftung (grant number AZ 1.16101.09). Support for TB. The funder had no role in study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the manuscript. The intramural fortune program of the University of Tübingen (grant number 2125-0-0). Support for TB. The funder had no role in study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the manuscript. National Institute of Neurological Disorders and Stroke (grant number U01NS090562). Support for AMC. The funder had no role in study design, data

Abstract

Small, genetically tractable species such as larval zebrafish, *Drosophila*, or *Caenorhabditis elegans* have become key model organisms in modern neuroscience. In addition to their low maintenance costs and easy sharing of strains across labs, one key appeal is the possibility to monitor single or groups of animals in a behavioural arena while controlling the activity of select neurons using optogenetic or thermogenetic tools. However, the purchase of a commercial solution for these types of experiments, including an appropriate camera system as well as a controlled behavioural arena, can be costly. Here, we present a low-cost and modular open-source alternative called 'FlyPi'. Our design is based on a 3D-printed mainframe, a Raspberry Pi computer, and high-definition camera system as well as Arduino-based optical and thermal control circuits. Depending on the configuration, FlyPi can be assembled for well under €100 and features optional modules for light-emitting diode (LED)-based fluorescence microscopy and optogenetic stimulation as well as a Peltier-based temperature stimulator for thermogenetics. The complete version with all modules costs approximately €200 or substantially less if the user is prepared to 'shop around'. All functions of FlyPi can be controlled through a custom-written graphical user interface. To demonstrate FlyPi's capabilities, we present its use in a series of state-of-the-art neurogenetics experiments. In addition, we demonstrate FlyPi's utility as a medical diagnostic tool as well as a teaching aid at Neurogenetics courses held at several African universities. Taken together, the low cost and modular nature as well as fully open design of FlyPi make it a highly versatile tool in a range of applications, including the classroom, diagnostic centres, and research labs.

collection and analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the manuscript. Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (grant number BA 5283/1-1). Support for TB. The funder had no role in study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the manuscript. CIN-Werner Reichardt Centre for Integrative Neuroscience (grant number EXC307). DFG funding to ABA. The funder had no role in study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the manuscript.

Competing interests: The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Abbreviations: AVI, audio video interleave; BOM, bill of materials; CCD, charge-coupled device; CPU, central processing unit; *dpf*, days postfertilisation; ERG, electroretinogram; GFP, Green Fluorescent Protein; GPP, General Purpose Pin; GUI, Graphical User Interface; IDE, Integrated Development Environment; LED, NO-IR, no infrared [filter]; light-emitting diode; NO-IR, no-infrared filter; PCB, printed circuit board; PER, proboscis extension reflex; *psf*, point-spread function; RGB, red-green-blue; RPi, Raspberry Pi; RPi3, Raspberry Pi 3 single-board computer; SD, secure digital.

Provenance: Not commissioned; externally peer reviewed.

Introduction

The advent of protein engineering has brought about a plethora of genetically encoded actuators and sensors that have revolutionised neuroscience as we knew it but a mere decade ago. On the back of an ever-expanding array of genetically accessible model organisms, these molecular tools have allowed researchers to both monitor and manipulate neuronal processes at unprecedented breadth (e.g., [1–3]). In parallel, developments in consumer-oriented manufacturing techniques such as 3D printing as well as low-cost and user-friendly micro-electronic circuits have brought about a silent revolution in the way that individual researchers may customise their lab equipment or build entire setups from scratch (reviewed in: [4–7]). Similarly, already ultra-low-cost light-emitting diodes (LEDs), when collimated, now provide sufficient power to photo-activate most iterations of Channelrhodopsins or excite fluorescent proteins for optical imaging, while a small Peltier-element suffices to thermo-activate heat-sensitive proteins [8–10]. In tandem, falling prices of high-performance charge-coupled device (CCD) chips and optical components such as lenses and spectral filters mean that today, already a basic webcam in combination with coloured, transparent plastic or a diffraction grating may suffice to perform sophisticated optical measurements [11,12]. Taken together, modern biosciences today stand at a precipice of technological possibilities, in which a functional neuroscience laboratory set-up, capable of delivering high-quality data over a wide range of experimental scenarios, can be built from scratch for a mere fraction of the cost traditionally required to purchase any one of its individual components. Here, we present such a design.

Assembled from readily available off-the-shelf mechanical, optical, and electronic components, “FlyPi” provides a modular solution for basic light and fluorescence microscopy as well as time-precise opto- and thermogenetic stimulation during behavioural monitoring of small, genetically tractable model species such as zebrafish (*Danio rerio*), fruit flies (*Drosophila melanogaster*), or nematodes (e.g., *C. elegans*). The system is based on an Arduino microcontroller [13] and a Raspberry Pi 3 single-board computer (RPi3; [14]), which also provides sufficient computing power for basic data analysis, word processing, and web access using a range of fully open-source software solutions that are preinstalled on the secure digital (SD) card image provided. The mechanical chassis is 3D printed, and all source code is open, such that the design and future modifications can be readily distributed electronically to enable rapid sharing across research labs and institutes of science education. This not only facilitates reproducibility of experimental results across labs, but also promotes rapid iteration and prototyping of novel modifications to adapt the basic design for a wide range of specialised applications. More generally, it presents a key step towards a true democratisation of scientific research and education that is largely independent of financial backing [4].

Here, we first present the basic mode of operation, including options for micropositioning of samples and electrodes, and demonstrate FlyPi’s suitability for light microscopy and use as a basic medical diagnostic tool. Second, we present its fluorescence capability including basic calcium imaging using GCaMP5 [1]. Third, we survey FlyPi’s suitability for behavioural tracking of *Drosophila* and *C. elegans*. Fourth, we demonstrate optogenetic activation of Channelrhodopsin 2 [3] and CsChrimson [15] in transgenic larval zebrafish as well as *Drosophila* larvae and adults. Fifth, we evaluate the performance of FlyPi’s Peltier-thermistor control loop for thermogenetics [16]. Sixth, we briefly summarise our efforts to introduce this tool for university research and teaching in sub-Saharan Africa [4,17].

Results

Overview

The basic FlyPi can resolve samples down to approximately 10 microns, acquire video at up to 90 Hz, and acquire time-lapse series over many hours. It consists of the 3D-printed mainframe (Fig 1A–1D), one RPi3 computer with a Pi camera and off-the-shelf objective lens, one Arduino-Nano microcontroller, as well as a custom printed circuit board (PCB) for flexible attachment of a wide range of actuators and sensors (Fig 1C). The main printed frame allows modular placement of additional components into the camera path, such as holders for petri dishes or microscope slides (Fig 1D–1I). This basic build, including power adapters, cables, and the module for lighting and optogenetic stimulation, can be assembled for less than €100 (S1 Table; Fig 1D). Additional modules for fluorescence imaging (Fig 1E), temperature control (Fig 1F), or an automated focus drive (Fig 1G) can be added as required. For a full bill of materials (BOM), see S1 Table. A complete user manual and assembly instructions are deposited on GitHub (https://github.com/amchagas/Flypi/blob/master/User%20and%20Assembly%20Manual_revised.pdf). In time, additional content and updated versions will be added to the FlyPi GitHub repository (<https://github.com/amchagas/Flypi/>).

Basic camera operation and microscopy

To keep the FlyPi design compact and affordable yet versatile, we made use of the Raspberry Pi (RPi) platform, which offers a range of FlyPi-compatible camera modules. Here, we use the ‘adjustable focus RPi red-green-blue (RGB) camera’ (S1 Table), which includes a powerful 12-mm threaded objective lens. Objective focal distance can be gradually adjusted between approximately 1 mm (peak zoom) and infinity (panoramic, not shown), while the camera delivers 5-megapixel Bayer-filtered colour images at 15 Hz. Spatial binning increases peak framerates to 42 Hz (x2) or 90 Hz (x4). Alternatively, the slightly more expensive 8-megapixel RPi camera or the infrared-capable no-infrared filter (NO-IR) camera can be used. Objective focus can be set manually or via a software-controlled continuous-rotation micro servo motor (Fig 1G). Alternatively, the RPi CCD chip can be directly fitted above any other objective with minimal mechanical adjustments.

A custom-written Graphical User Interface (GUI, S1 Fig) using the Python-based PiCamera library allows for control of framerates, sensitivity, contrast, white balance, and digital zoom. Control over other parameters can be added as required. The GUI facilitates saving images and image sequences in jpeg format and video data in h264 or audio video interleave (AVI) format. Notably, the GUI can also function independent of the remainder of FlyPi components if only easy control for a RPi camera is required.

The camera can be mounted in two main configurations: upright or inverted (Fig 2A and 2B). While the former may be primarily used for resolving larger objects such as adult *Drosophila* (Fig 2C) or for behavioural tracking, the latter may be preferred for higher-zoom applications (Fig 2D and 2E) and fluorescence microscopy (see below) or if easy access to the top of a sample is required. Here, the image quality is easily sufficient to monitor basic physiological processes such as the heartbeat or blood flow in live zebrafish larvae (Fig 2F, S1 Video).

If required, specimens can be positioned by a 3D-printed micromanipulator [4] (Fig 2B). Up to three manipulators can be attached to the free faces of FlyPi (Fig 1D and 1I). Manipulators can also be configured to hold probes such as electrodes or stimulation devices (Fig 1I). Like the camera objective, manipulators can be optionally fitted with continuous-rotation servo motors to provide electronic control of movement in three axes [4]. These motors can be either controlled via software or via a stand-alone joystick unit based on a separate Arduino-

Fig 1. Overview. **A.** The 3D model, colour coded by core structure (black), mounting adapters (blue), and micromanipulator (green). **B.** Printed parts and electronics, partially assembled. **C.** Wiring diagram and summary of electronics. Full bill of materials (BOM) in [S1 Table](#). **D.** The assembled FlyPi with single micromanipulator and light-emitting diode (LED)-ring module, diffuser, and Petri dish adapter mounted in the bottom. **E.** Filter wheel mounted above the inverted camera objective. **F.** Peltier element and thermistor

embedded into the base. **G.** Automatic focus drive. **H.** Petri dish mounting adapters. **I.** A second micromanipulator mounted to the left face of FlyPi holding a probe (here, a 200- μ l pipette tip for illustration) above the microscope slide mounted by the micromanipulator on the right.

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.2002702.g001>

Uno microcontroller and a Sparkfun Joystick shield [19]. Depending on print quality and manipulator configuration, precision is in the order of tens of microns [4].

For lighting, we use an Adafruit Neopixel 12 LED ring [20] comprising 12 high-power RGB-LEDs that can be configured for flexible intensity and wavelength lighting. For example, the LED ring with all LEDs active simultaneously can be used to add ‘white’ incident or transmission illumination (e.g., Fig 2A and 2F) while behavioural tracking can be performed under dim, red light. A series of white weighing boats mounted above the ring can be used as diffusers (Fig 2A). Long-term time-lapse imaging, for example, to monitor developmental processes or bacterial growth, can be performed in any configuration. Lighting is controlled from the GUI through an open Adafruit LED control Python library.

The implementation of a cost-effective option for digital microscopy also opens up possibilities for basic medical diagnosis, such as the detection of small parasitic nematodes *Brugia malayi* or *Wuchereria bancrofti* in human lymph tissue samples (Fig 2G and 2H) or *Schistosoma* eggs in human urine (Fig 2I). Similarly, the image is sufficient to detect and identify counterstained types of blood cells in an infected smear (here, *Mansonella perstans*; Fig 2J and 2K).

Fluorescence microscopy

Next, we implemented fluorescence capability based on a 350 mA 410 nm LED attached to a reflective collimator as well as ultra-low-cost theatre lighting filters. For this, the excitation and emission light was limited by a low-pass and a notch filter, respectively (Fig 3A–3D, S1 Table). Imperfect emission filter efficiency for blocking direct excitation light necessitated that the source was positioned at 45° relative to the objective plane, thereby preventing direct excitation bleed-through into the camera path (Fig 3A and 3B). Many commonly used fluorescent proteins and synthetic probes exhibit multiple excitation peaks. For example, Green Fluorescent Protein (GFP) is traditionally excited around 488 nm; however, there is a second and larger excitation peak in the near UV [21] (Fig 3D, but see [1]). Here, we made use of this short-wavelength peak by stimulating at 410 nm to improve spectral separation of excitation and emission light despite the suboptimal emission filter. Fig 3C shows the fluorescence image recorded in a typical fluorescence test slide. The RGB camera chip allowed simultaneous visualisation of both green and red emission. If required, the red channel could be limited either through image processing or by addition of an appropriate short-pass emission filter positioned above the camera. Next, using green fluorescent beads (100 nm, Methods), we measured the point-spread function (*psf*) of the objective as 5.4 μ m (s.d.) at full zoom (Fig 3E and 3F). This is >10 times broader than that of a typical state-of-the-art confocal or 2-photon system [22], though without optical sectioning, and imposes a theoretical resolution limit in the order of approximately 10 μ m. Notably, with an effective pixel size of approximately 1 μ m (Fig 1E), the system is therefore limited by the objective optics rather than the resolution of the camera chip, such that the use of a higher numerical aperture objective would yield a substantial improvement in spatial resolution. It also means that at peak zoom, the camera image can be binned at x4 for increased speed and sensitivity without substantial loss in image quality.

Next, we tested FlyPi’s performance during fluorescence imaging on live animals. At lower magnification, image quality was sufficient for basic fluorescence detection as required, for example, for fluorescence-based sorting of transgenic animals (screening). We illustrate this

Fig 2. Basic light microscopy. **A, B.** The camera and objective can be mounted in upright (A) or inverted mode (B). In each case, the micromanipulator allows accurate positioning of a microscope slide in the image plane, while the light-emitting diode (LED) ring coupled to a series of diffusers provides for flexible spectrum and brightness illumination (A). **C.** At low zoom, the magnification is appropriate to provide high-resolution colour images of several animals at once (here, *D. melanogaster* fed with 5 mM sucrose in 0.5% agarose dyed with blue or red food dyes (Food Blue No. 1 and Food Red No. 106 dyes; Tokyo Chemical Industry Co.,

Japan) as described in [18]. **D, E.** When the objective is fully extended, magnification is sufficient to resolve large neurons of the mouse brain, while different positions of the LED ring permit one to highlight different structures in the tissue. **F.** The system is also appropriate to provide high-resolution imagery of zebrafish larvae (*D. rerio*) with only room lighting (cf. [S1 Video](#)). **G, H.** *Brugia malayi* (G) and *Wuchereria bancrofti* (H) in human lymph tissue biopsy. **I.** *Schistosoma* eggs in human urine. **J.** *Mansonella perstans* in human blood smear (Wright Giemsa stain) and **K.** magnification of bottom-right image section.

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.2002702.g002>

using a transgenic zebrafish larva (3 days postfertilisation [*dpf*]) expressing the GFP-based calcium sensor GCaMP5G in all neurons (Fig 3G–3I, [S2 Video](#)). Similarly, the system also provided a sufficient signal-to-noise ratio for basic calcium imaging, demonstrated here using *Drosophila* larvae driving GCaMP5 in muscles that reveal clear fluorescence signals associated with peristaltic waves as the animal freely crawls on a microscope slide (Fig 3J–3M; see also [S3 Video](#), cf. [24]). However, the system failed to provide a sufficient signal-to-noise ratio for imaging clear calcium signals in substantially smaller structures, such as neurons of the *Drosophila* antennal lobe or zebrafish optic tectum (not shown). This is likely related to the limited optical power and large field of depth of the objective used, and might, therefore, be ameliorated in the future by integration of different commercial objectives and/or optical filters. Further fluorescence example videos are provided in the supplementary materials ([S4](#) and [S5 Videos](#)).

Behavioural tracking

‘To move is all mankind can do’. Sherrington’s (1924) thoughts on the ultimate role of any animal’s nervous system still echoes today, when despite decades of (bio)technological advances, behavioural experiments are still amongst the most powerful means for understanding neuronal function and organisation. Typically, individual or groups of animals are placed in a controlled environment and filmed using a camera system. Here, FlyPi’s colour camera with adjustable zoom offers a wide range of video-monitoring options, while the RGB LED ring provides for easily adjusted wavelength and intensity lighting (Fig 4A) including dim red light, which is largely invisible to many invertebrates including *C. elegans* (Fig 4B, [S6 Video](#)) and *Drosophila*. A series of mounting adapters for petri dishes (Fig 1H) as well as a custom chamber consisting of a 3D-printed chassis and two glass microscope slides for adult *Drosophila* (Fig 4C) can be used as behavioural arenas. Following data acquisition, videos are typically fed through a series of tracking and annotation routines to note the spatial position, orientation, or behavioural patterns of each animal. Today, a vast range of open behavioural analysis packages is available, including many that run directly on the RPi3 such as CTrax [25], used here to track the movements of adult *Drosophila* in a 10-s video (Fig 4D; [S7 Video](#)).

Optogenetics and thermogenetics

One key advantage of using genetically tractable model organisms is the ability to selectively express proteins in select populations of cells whose state can be precisely controlled using external physical stimuli such as light (Optogenetic effectors, e.g., [26]) or heat (Thermogenetic effectors, e.g., [16]). Through these, the function of individual or sets of neurons can be readily studied in behavioural experiments. A plethora of both light- and heat- sensitive proteins are available, with new variants being continuously developed. Many of these proteins exhibit sufficient sensitivity for activation by collimated high-power LEDs, rather than having to rely on more expensive light sources like a Xenon lamp or a laser. Similarly, temperature variation over a few degrees Celsius, as achieved by an off-the-shelf Peltier element with adequate heat dissipation, is sufficient to activate or inactivate a range of temperature-sensitive

Fig 3. Fluorescence microscopy. **A.** A collimated 410 nm light-emitting diode (LED) angled at 45° and two ultra-low-cost theatre lighting filters provide for fluorescence capability. **B.** A photo of the fluorescence setup. **C.** Fluorescence test slide. **D.** Top: Spectra of excitation LED and filters superimposed (dark blue) on green fluorescent protein (GFP) excitation (light blue) and emission (green) spectra. Emission filter in orange. Bottom: Quantum efficiency of the OmniVision OV5647 charge-coupled device (CCD) camera chip used in the Raspberry Pi (Rpi) system, taken from [23]. **E, F.** Point-spread function (*psf*) measured using green fluorescent beads (Methods): Standard deviation is approximately 5.4 μm . **G, H.** Three days postfertilisation (*dpf*) Zebrafish larva expressing GCaMP5Gf in neurons (*HuC:GCaMP5G*) in transmission (**G**) and

fluorescence mode (H). I. At low zoom, the system can be used for fish sorting (cf. S2 Video). Note the absence of green fluorescence in the brain of the nontransgenic animal to the upper right. J–M. Calcium Imaging in *Drosophila* larva expressing GCaMP5 in muscles (Mef2-Gal4; UAS-myr::GCaMP5). J, K. Three regions of interest placed across the raw image stack of a freely crawling larva (J) reveal period bouts of increased fluorescence, as peristaltic waves drive up calcium in muscles along the body (K). Arrowheads in J indicate the positions of peaks in a calcium wave. L. A space–time plot of the time-differentiated image stack, averaged across the short body axis, reveals regular peristaltic waves. Warm colours indicate high positive rates of change in local image brightness. M. A single peristaltic wave (as indicated in L) in 12 image planes separated by 100-ms intervals (cf. S5 Video).

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.2002702.g003>

Fig 4. Behavioural tracking. A, B. Red light illumination from the light-emitting diode (LED) ring can be used to illuminate animals during behavioural tracking—*C. elegans* is shown here on an Agar plate (B). C. A behavioural chamber based on two microscope slides and a 3D-printed chassis is adequate for behavioural monitoring of adult *Drosophila*. D. Animals tracked using Ctrax [25].

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.2002702.g004>

proteins. We therefore implemented both opto- and thermogenetic stimulation capability for FlyPi.

Optogenetics. For optogenetic activation, we used the LED ring (Fig 5A), whose spectrum and power are appropriate for use with both ChR2 (single LED ‘blue’ $P_{w_{460}}$: 14.2 mW) as well as ReaChr and CsChrimson (‘red’ $P_{w_{628}}$: 7.2 mW; ‘green’ $P_{w_{518}}$: 7.5 mW) (Fig 5B) [3,15,27,28]. Alternatively, an Adafruit 8 x 8 high-power single-wavelength LED matrix [20] can be attached for spatially selective optogenetic or visual stimulation [29]. For demonstration, a zebrafish larva (3 dpf) expressing ChR2 in all neurons was mounted on top of a microscope slide, which was in turn held above the inverted objective using the micromanipulator (Fig 5A and 5C). The LED ring was positioned facedown approximately 2 cm above the animal, outside of the centrally positioned camera’s field of view. Concurrent maximal activation of all 12 ‘blue’ LEDs ($P_{w_{460}}$: approximately 4.9 mW cm^{-2} at the level of the specimen) reliably elicited basic motor patterns for stimuli exceeding 500 ms, illustrated here by pectoral fin swimming bouts (Fig 5C and 5D, S8 Video). Substantially shorter stimuli did not elicit the behaviour (e.g., third trial: approximately 150 ms), nor did activation of the other wavelength LEDs or blue light activation in ChR2-negative control animals (not shown). This strongly indicated that motor networks were activated through ChR2 rather than innate, visually mediated escape reflexes in response to the light (cf. [30]) or photomotor responses [31]. Notably, in the example shown, while the stimulus artefact was used as a timing marker, excitation light could be blocked (>95% attenuation) using an appropriate filter (Fig 5B dark red trace, S1 Table) without substantially affecting image quality, while timing could be verified using the flexibly programmable low-power RGB LED normally integrated into the Peltier-thermistor loop (not shown).

We also tested ChR2 activation in *Drosophila* larvae. Animals were left to freely crawl on ink-stained agarose with both the LED ring and camera positioned above. Activation of all 12 blue LEDs reliably triggered body contractions for the duration of the 1-s stimulus, followed by rapid recovery (Fig 5E and 5F). Finally, full-power activation of the red LEDs reliably triggered proboscis extension reflex (PER) in adult *Drosophila* expressing CsChrimson in the gustatory circuit (Fig 5G and 5H). In this latter demonstration, we made use of the GUI’s protocol function, which allows easy programming of microsecond-precision looping patterns controlling key FlyPi functions such as LEDs and the Peltier Loop (see below).

Thermogenetics. Owing to their remarkable ability to tolerate a wide range of ambient temperatures, many invertebrate model species including *Drosophila* and *C. elegans* also lend themselves to thermogenetic manipulation. Through the select expression of proteins such as Trp-A or shibire^{ts} [16,34], sets of neurons can be readily activated or have their synaptic drive blocked by raising the ambient temperature over a narrow threshold of 28°C and 32°C, respectively. Here, FlyPi offers the possibility to accurately control the temperature of the upper surface of a 4 cm x 4 cm Peltier element embedded in its base, with immediate feedback from a temperature sensor (Fig 6A, S1 Table). A central processing unit (CPU) fan and heat sink below the Peltier element dissipate excess heat (Fig 6B, S1 Table). The setup reaches surface temperatures \pm approximately 20°C around ambient temperature within seconds (approximately 1°C/s) and holds set temperatures steady over many minutes (s.d. < 1°C) (Fig 6C).

Discussion

We primarily designed FlyPi to achieve a good balance of performance, cost, and flexibility in its use. Using higher quality components, individual function performance can certainly be improved (see Potential for further development). Here, it is instructive to compare FlyPi’s microscope function to other open microscope designs. For example, the fully 3D-printable

Fig 5. Optogenetics. **A**. Experimental configuration suitable for optogenetic stimulation of an individual zebrafish larva suspended in a drop of E3 (Methods). **B**. Spectrum and peak power of the three light-emitting diodes (LEDs) embedded at each ring position. Spectral filters can be used to limit excitation light reaching the camera (Rosco Supergel No. 19, 'Fire'). **C**. Zebrafish larva (3 days postfertilisation [*dpf*]) expressing ChR2 broadly in neurons (*Et(E1b:Gal4)s1101t, Tg(UAS::Cr.ChR2_H134R-mCherry)s1985t, nacre^{-/-}*). **D**. The animal exhibits pectoral fin burst motor patterns upon activation of blue LEDs (cf. *S8 Video*). **E, F**. *Drosophila* larvae expressing ChR2 in all neurons (*elav-GAL4/+; UAS-shibre⁵⁹; UAS-ChR2/+; UAS-ChR2/+*) crawling on ink-stained agar reliably contract when blue LEDs are active. **G, H**. Proboscis extension reflex (PER) in adult *Drosophila* expressing CsChrimson in the gustatory circuit (*w; +; GMR86A08-GAL4/UAS-CsChrimson*); the GMR86A08-GAL4 is part of the Janelia Farm Flightlight collection [32]; its effect on PER is a personal communication from Olivia Schwarz and Jan Pielage, University of Kaiserslautern, Germany, who observed this phenotype as part of behavioural screen [33] is reliably elicited by activation of red LEDs.

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.2002702.g005>

Fig 6. Thermogenetics. **A.** The 4 cm x 4 cm Peltier element embedded in the FlyPi base, with the Thermistor clamped into one corner. **B.** Side view with FlyPi propped up on a set of 3D-printed feet to allow air dissipation beneath the base. The central processing unit (CPU) fan is positioned directly beneath the Peltier. **C.** Performance of the Peltier-thermistor feedback loop. Command 15°C and 35°C indicated by blue and red shading, switching every 5 minutes; room temperature 19°C (no shading).

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.2002702.g006>

microscope stage of the “Waterscope” [35] achieves superior stability of the focussing mechanism. However, unlike FlyPi, this design cannot achieve the same range of possible magnifications needed for behavioural experiments. Some other open microscope designs (e.g., [36,37]) use a larger fraction of commercial components to provide superior image quality and/or stability, albeit invariably at a substantially higher cost. On the extreme low-cost scale, available designs typically do not provide the imaging systems (i.e., the camera, control software, and processor) but instead rely on the addition of a mobile phone camera or, indeed, the eye itself (e.g., [38–40]). Next, FlyPi also provides for a powerful range of sample illumination options, which typically exceed available alternatives. To our knowledge, no alternative open microscope design encompasses the experimental accessories and control systems required for behavioural tracking under both opto- and thermogenetic control.

Another key aspect of FlyPi’s design is its modular nature. This means that the system does not require all integrated options to be assembled to function. For example, if the main purpose of an assembled unit is to excite Channelrhodopsin, the only module beside the base unit is the LED ring. Similarly, only the Peltier-thermistor circuit is needed for Thermogenetics experiments. This means that units designed for a dedicated purpose can be assembled quickly and at substantially reduced cost. Moreover, given a functional base unit, it is easy for the user to modify any one part or to integrate a fully independent module built for a different purpose altogether. The modular nature also renders the design more robust in the face of difficulties with sourcing building components.

Potential for further development

Clearly, the current FlyPi only scratches the surface of possible applications. Further development is expected to take place as researchers and educators integrate aspects of our design into their laboratory routines. To explicitly encourage resharing of such designs with the community, we maintain and curate a centralised official project page (<http://open-labware.net/projects/flypi/>) linked to a code repository (<https://github.com/amchagas/Flypi>). Indeed, a basic description of the FlyPi project has been online since 2015, which has led to several community-driven modifications. For example, a recent modification of the 3D-printed main-frame implements the camera and focus motor below a closed stage [41]. At the expense of a fixed camera position, this build is substantially more robust and thus perhaps more suitable, e.g., for classroom teaching. Other community-driven modifications include a version in which all 3D-printed parts are replaced by Lego[®] blocks [42] as well as several forks geared to optimise the code, details in the 3D model, or additions in the electronic control circuits.

Currently, one obvious limit of FlyPi is spatial resolution. The system currently resolves individual human red blood cells (Fig 2K), but narrowly fails to resolve malaria parasites within (not shown). Here, the limit is optical rather than related to the camera chip, meaning that use of a higher numerical aperture and magnification objective lens will yield substantial improvements. This development might come in hand with additional improvements in the micromanipulator's Z-axis stability to facilitate focussing at higher magnification—for example, as implemented in the Waterscope [35]. Similarly, photon catch efficiency of the CCD sensor could be improved by use of an unfiltered (monochrome) chip. Unfortunately, to date, no such chip is available for the RPi platform; however, it may be possible to carefully scratch off the Bayer filter using a wooden chisel [43]. Next, the contrast of fluorescence images could be markedly improved by further investment in optical filters. Other alleys of potential further development include the following: (i) the addition of further options for fluorescence microscopy to work over a wider range of wavelengths, likely through the use of other excitation LEDs and spectral filters; (ii) FlyPi could also be tested for stimulating photo-conversion of genetically encoded proteins such as CamPari, Kaede, or photoconvertible GFP [44–46]; (iii) auto-focussing could be implemented by iteratively rotating the servo-assisted focus while evaluating changes in the spatial autocorrelation function or Fourier spectrum of the live image; (iv) a motorised manipulator could be integrated for stage-automation through a simple software routine; and (v) one or several FlyPis could be networked wirelessly or through the integrated Ethernet port to allow centralised access and control, thereby removing the need for dedicated user interface peripherals. Taken together, by providing all source code and designs under an open-source license, together with an expandable online repository, we aim to provide a flexible, modular platform upon which enthusiastic colleagues may build and exchange modifications in time. We will be pleased to add modifications to our basic design to the online project repositories as appropriate. For this, please contact the first author directly.

Classroom teaching and laboratory improvisation

In large parts of the world, funding restrictions hamper the widespread implementation of practical science education—a problem that is pervasive across both schools and universities [4,47]. Often, limitations include broken or complete lack of basic equipment such as low-power light microscopes or computing resources. Here, the low cost and robustness of FlyPi may offer a viable solution. If only one unit can be made available for an entire classroom, the teacher can project the display output of FlyPi to the wall such that many students can follow demonstrated experiments. Already a low amount of funding may furnish an entire classroom with FlyPis, allowing students in groups of two or three to work on and maintain their own

unit. The relative ease of assembly also means that building FlyPi itself could be integrated into part of the syllabus. In this way, a basic technical education in electronics and soldering or basic 3D printing could be conveyed in parallel. As an additional advantage, each student could build their own equipment, which brings about further benefits in equipment maintenance and long-term use beyond the classroom.

To survey to what extent FlyPi assembly and use may be beneficial in a classroom scenario, we introduced the equipment to African biomedical MSc and PhD students as well as senior members of faculty during a series of multi-day workshops at Universities in sub-Saharan Africa since 2015, including the University of KwaZulu Natal (Durban, SA), the International Centre of Insect Physiology and Ecology (icipe, Nairobi, Kenya), Kampala International University (Dar es Salaam, Tanzania and Ishaka Bushyeni, Uganda), and the International Medical and Technical University (IMTU, Dar es Salaam, Tanzania). In addition, colleagues have used and modified the design for projects held in Accra, Ghana, Khartoum, Sudan, and Ishaka, Uganda. In one workshop, we only provided the 3D-printed parts, the custom PCB, and off-the-shelf electronics and took students through the entire process of assembly and installation. Having had no previous experience with basic electronics, soldering, or the use of simple hand tools such as a Dremel or cable-strippers, all students successfully assembled a working unit. Towards the end of the training, students used their own FlyPi to perform basic neurogenetics experiments with *Drosophila*, including heat activation of larvae expressing *shibire^{ts}* in all neurons (*elav-GAL4/+; UAS-shibre^{ts}; UAS-ChR2 / +; UAS-ChR2 / +*, cf. Fig 6) and optogenetic activation of ChR2 to elicit a range of behaviours in both adults and larvae (cf. Fig 5). Following the training, students took their assembled FlyPis home for their own research and teaching purposes. In other courses, we brought preassembled FlyPis with a range of different modules. Students learned to operate the equipment within minutes and subsequently used them for a range of experiments and microscopy tasks, including several novel configurations not formally introduced by the faculty. Indeed, many experiments presented in this paper were performed during these training courses. We also used individual FlyPi modules to improvise workarounds for incomplete commercial lab equipment. For example, the RPi camera with focus drive and live image-processing options served as an excellent replacement for a missing Gel-doc camera. Similarly, we used FlyPi as a replacement camera for odour-evoked calcium imaging in *Drosophila* antennas on a commercial, upright fluorescence microscope or for dissection demonstrations under a stereoscope that also utilised the LED rings for illumination. Moreover, FlyPi's programmable General Purpose Pins (GPPs) and LEDs were used to drive time-precise light-stimulus series, e.g., for independently recorded *Drosophila* electroretinograms (ERGs). Similarly, the Peltier-feedback circuit was adequate to maintain developing zebrafish embryos at a controlled temperature during prolonged experiments or to reversibly block action potential propagation in long nerves through local cooling. Clearly, beyond its use as a self-standing piece of equipment and teaching tool, the low cost and modular nature of FlyPi also renders it versatile to support or take over a wide range of additional functions in the lab. In hand, the use and assembly of a system like FlyPi may inspire confidence in researchers' ability to build and modify other pieces of equipment themselves, shaped to their individual needs, which in a teaching scenario is perhaps the greatest benefit of all.

Conclusion

Taken together, we anticipate that the open design of FlyPi will be useful in scientific teaching and research as well as for medical professionals working in low-resource settings looking to supplement their diagnostic toolkit. We anticipate that in time, further improvement and new

designs will emerge from the global open hardware community. Notably, a curated collection of further “Open-Labware” [4,48] designs can be found on the PLOS website [49].

Methods

A complete assembly and user manual is deposited on GitHub (https://github.com/amchagas/Flypi/blob/master/User%20and%20Assembly%20Manual_revised.pdf).

Assembly time and necessary skills

From our previous workshop experiences, the assembly of the FlyPi (including software setup) should take about 5 hours for a person with no previous soldering experience, provided that all individual components are in place. Experienced users can expect to be done in 2 to 3 hours.

3D modelling and printing

3D modelling was performed in OpenSCAD [50], and all files are provided as both editable scad and compiled surface tessellation lattice (stl) files. All parts were printed in polylactic acid (PLA) on an Ultimaker 2 3D printer (Ultimaker, Geldermalsen, Netherlands) in six prearranged plates using the following parameters: infill 30%, no supports, 5-mm brim, layer height 0.1 mm, print speed 60 mm/s, and travel speed 200 mm/s. Total printing time of a single FlyPi, including all presented modules, was about 40 hours. Notably, this time can be substantially reduced by using faster print settings and/or a larger nozzle, as is commonly implemented in lower-cost 3D printers. For example, using a well-calibrated delta Rep-Rap delta (www.reprap.org) printing at full speed, the entire system can be printed at sufficient precision in less than 20 hours. In case a 3D printer is not locally available, several available “print-on-demand” services (e.g., Shapeways, Sculpteo, 3D hubs) can be used to source the parts. We estimated that the cost to have parts printed in plastic from one of the services available at 3Dhubs to be approximately €40.

PCB design and printing

The PCB was designed in KiCad [51] and is provided as the native KiCad file format, as well as the more widely used gerber file format. The PCB facilitates connections between peripherals and the microcontroller and was designed to be modular such that only components that will be used need to be soldered on the board. The power circuitry designed for a single 12 V 5 A power supply is provided. The large spacing between component slots, PCB labelling, and consistent use of the “through-hole” component format is intended to facilitate assembly by users with little soldering experience. Using the provided Gerber files, it is possible to order the PCBs from a variety of producers (e.g., pcbway.com, seedstudio.com/pcb, dirtypcbs.com). Of course, if required, the entire PCB could also be improvised using individual cables and/or a suitable breadboard by taking reference to the circuit diagram provided.

The GUI

The GUI (S1 Fig) was written in Python3. The control functions for each peripheral component is created in its own class, making it easier for the end user to create/alter functions independently. These classes are then contained in a ‘general purpose’ class, responsible for the display of the user interface and addressing the commands to be sent to the Arduino board (responsible for time-precise events and direct interaction with peripherals, for details see below). The communication between the RPi and the Arduino is established via universal

serial bus (USB) through a serial protocol (Python Serial library [52]). The GUI is created using Tkinter [53]. Both libraries are compatible with Python2 and Python3.

The GUI is also capable of creating folders and saving files to the Raspberry Pi desktop. For simplicity, the software creates a folder called 'FlyPi_output' and subfolders depending on the type of data being acquired (time lapse, video, snapshots, temperature logging). The files within the subfolders are created using date and time as their names, preventing overwriting of data.

Arduino

We used an ATmega328-based Arduino Nano [13]. The board was chosen due to a high number of input/output ports, its variety of communication protocols (e.g., Serial, I2C), its low cost and easy availability (including several ultra-low-cost clones at €2 to €3), very well-documented environment (hardware specifications, function descriptions, 'how to' recipes), and large user database. The board is programmed in C++ together with the modifications added by the Arduino integrated development environment (IDE). The board is responsible for controlling all peripheral devices except the camera and provides microsecond precision for time measurement. The code can be adapted to most of the other boards of the Arduino family, with small changes (e.g., digital, analogue, and serial port addresses).

Raspberry Pi 3 operating system

We used Raspian [54] as the operating system (OS) on the Raspberry Pi 3 [14] for its installation simplicity through 'new out of the box software' (NOOBS) [55] and because it is derived from Debian [56], a stable and well-supported GNU-Linux distribution. However, any Linux distribution compatible with the Raspberry Pi and the chosen Python3 libraries can be used. Arduino compatibility is not mandatory, since once the board is loaded with the correct code, which can be done on any computer, the Arduino IDE is not used further, as all live communication goes via the serial port directly from Python.

Spectral and power measurements

We used a commercial photo-spectrometer (USB2000+VIS-NIR, Ocean Optics, Ostfildern, Germany) and custom-written software in Igor-Pro 7 (Wavemetrics) to record and analyse spectra of LEDs and filters. Peak LED power was determined using a Powermeter (Model 818, 200–1800 nm, Newport). We used fluorescent beads (PS-Speck TM Microscope Point Source Kit P-7220, ThermoFisher) for estimating FlyPi's *psf*.

Video and image acquisition

All static image data was obtained as full-resolution RGB images (2592 x 1944 pixels) and saved as jpeg. All video data was obtained as RGB at 42 Hz (x2 binning), yielding image stack of 1296 x 972 pixels, and saved as h264. Video data was converted to AVI using the ffmpeg package for GNU/Linux (ffmpeg.org, a conversion button is added to the GUI for simplicity). All further data analysis was performed in Image-J (NIH) and Igor-Pro 7 (Wavemetrics). Figures were prepared in Canvas 15 (ACD Systems).

Calcium imaging in larval *Drosophila* muscles

Second instar larvae (Mef2-Gal4; UAS-myr::GCaMP5) were left to freely crawl between a microscope slide and cover slip loosely suspended with tap water. For analysis, x2 binned video data (42 Hz) was further down-sampled by a factor of 2 in the image plane and a factor

of 4 in time. Only the green channel was analysed. Following background subtraction, regions of interest were placed as indicated (Fig 3J). Next, from each image frame, we subtracted the mean image of four preceding frames to generate a “running average time-differential” stack—shown as the space-time plot in Fig 3L with the original x-axis collapsed. Individual noncollapsed frames of this stack, separated by 100-ms intervals, are shown in Fig 3M.

Zebrafish Chr2 activation

A 3 dpf zebrafish larva (*Et(E1b:Gal4)s1101t, Tg(UAS:Cr.ChR2_H134R-mCherry)s1985t, nacre/-*) was mounted in a drop of E3 medium (5 mM NaCl, 0.17 mM KCl, 0.33 mM CaCl₂, 0.33 mM MgSO₄, pH adjusted to 7.4 using NaHCO₃) on top of a microscope slide and placed immediately above the inverted camera objective. The NeoPixel 12 LED ring was placed about 2 cm above the specimen, facing down. Concurrent maximal activation of all 12 blue LEDs for more than 500 ms reliably elicited pectoral fin swimming bouts. Shorter stimuli were not effective. RGB image data was obtained at 42 Hz, down-sampled by a factor of 4 in time and visualised by tracking the mean brightness of two regions of interest placed onto the pectoral fins.

Drosophila larva Chr2 activation

First, instar *Drosophila* larvae (*elav-GAL4/+; UAS-shibre^{ts}, UAS-ChR2/+; UAS-ChR2/+*, raised on standard food mixed with 200 μM all-trans retinal as described in [33]) were placed on agarose darkened with Indian ink (1% v/v) within the lid of a 50-ml falcon tube and left to freely crawl. The camera and NeoPixel LED ring were placed about 3 cm above the surface. Concurrent activation of all 12 blue LEDs for 1 s at a time reliably triggered larval contractions. Image data acquired at 42 Hz and saved as 8-bit greyscale. Larval length was quantified manually in ImageJ by measuring the distance between head and tail along the body axis at three time points: $t = -1, 0.5, \text{ and } 5$ s relative to the flash ($t = 0-1$ s). $n = 12$ responses from three animals, error bars in standard deviation.

Drosophila adult Chrimson activation

Adult *Drosophila* (*w; +; GMR86A08-Gal4/UAS-CsChrimson* raised on standard food mixed with 200 μM all-trans retinal as described in [33]) were fixed to a cover slide by gluing the back of their thorax with nail varnish, with limbs moving freely. The NeoPixel 12 LED ring was positioned around the camera objective about 2 cm above the fly, pointing down. Concurrent maximal activation of all 12 red LEDs for 1 s, separated by 2-s intervals, reliably elicited the PER. RGB image data was obtained at 42 Hz (x2 binning). The image stack was converted to 8-bit greyscale, and background over time was subtracted from the entire image stack to limit the excitation light artefact. To calculate proboscis position over time, we plot image brightness over time within a region of interest placed at the tip of the fully extended proboscis.

Thermogenetics

To assess the performance and stability of the Peltier-Thermistor loop we exported the Peltier command setting and Thermistor reading at 2 Hz through the serial port into an Ascii file and analysed the data using Igor Pro 6 (Wavemetrics).

Supporting information

S1 Fig. Graphical User Interface (GUI). Screenshots of the Python-based GUI divided into four main control panels that can be individually activated depending on user requirements:

A, Camera control, **B**, LED, **C**, Peltier and Focus Servo control, **D**, Custom protocol window. For details, please refer to the user and assembly manual online: <https://github.com/amchagas/Flypi/blob/master/User%20and%20Assembly%20Manual.pdf>. (PDF)

S1 Table. Bill of materials (BOM). Complete list, estimated costs and online links to all required parts, organised by modules. For details, please refer to the user and assembly manual online: <https://github.com/amchagas/Flypi/blob/master/User%20and%20Assembly%20Manual.pdf>. (XLSX)

S1 Video. Zebrafish larva transmission to visualise circulation (related to Fig 2F). (AVI)

S2 Video. Zebrafish larva fluorescence sorting (related to Fig 3I). (AVI)

S3 Video. Zebrafish larva expressing GFP in the heart (related to Fig 3). (AVI)

S4 Video. Zebrafish eggs expressing GCaMP5 in all neurons (related to Fig 3). (AVI)

S5 Video. *Drosophila* larva calcium imaging (related to Fig 3J–3M). (AVI)

S6 Video. *C. elegans* crawling freely (related to Fig 4B). (AVI)

S7 Video. *Drosophila* adults walking freely in custom chamber (related to Fig 4D). (AVI)

S8 Video. Zebrafish expressing ChR2 in all neurons under blue light (related to Fig 5C and 5D). (AVI)

S9 Video. *Drosophila* larvae ChR2 under blue light (related to Fig 5E and 5F). (AVI)

S10 Video. *Drosophila* adult proboscis extension reflex driven by CsChrimson using red light (related to Fig 5G and 5H). (AVI)

Acknowledgments

We thank the following people who kindly provided technical advice, specimens, reagents and other vital forms of support: Thomas Euler (technical advice and support for A.M.C.), Ihab Riad (discussions, development, and field testing), Paul Szyska (advice on optical filters), Cornelius Schwarz (support for A.M.C.), Thirumalaisamy P Velavan (human parasite slides), Della David (*C. elegans*), Marta Rivera-Alba (CTrax and field testing), Olivia Schwartz and Jan Pielage (Gal4 and UAS-CsChrimson flies and field testing), Matthias Landgraf (Mef2-Gal4; UAS-myr::GCaMP5 and w; UAS-shits, UAS-ChR2; UAS-ChR2 flies and field testing), Richard Benton (several *Drosophila* lines, support for L.L.P.G.), Juan Sanchez (*Drosophila* feeding assay and field testing), Miroslav Róman-Róson (brain slice) and Georg Raiser, Tom Laudes, Lukas v Tobel. and Christen Mirth (field testing). In addition, we thank the many students and

teaching volunteers as well as funders of TReND in Africa's (www.TReNDinAfrica.org) workshops and other activities who jointly supported the inspiration for and development of FlyPi: The International Brain Research Organisation, The Company of Biologists, The Wellcome Trust, The VolkswagenStiftung, The International Society of Neurochemistry, The Cambridge Alborada Trust, Cambridge in Africa, The American Physiological Society, The Physiological Society, The University of Lausanne Officine de egalite, and many others. The content is solely the responsibility of the authors and does not necessarily represent the official views of the funders.

References

1. Akerboom J, Chen T, Wardill T. Optimization of a GCaMP calcium indicator for neural activity imaging. *J Neurosci*. 2012; 32(40):13819–13840. <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.2601-12.2012> PMID: 23035093
2. Marvin JS, Borghuis BG, Tian L, Cichon J, Harnett MT, Akerboom J, et al. An optimized fluorescent probe for visualizing glutamate neurotransmission. 2013; 10.
3. Fenno L, Yizhar O, Deisseroth K. The development and application of optogenetics. *Annu Rev Neurosci*. 2011; 34: 389–412. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-neuro-061010-113817> PMID: 21692661
4. Baden T, Chagas AM, Gage G, Marzullo T, Prieto Godino L, Euler T. Open Labware—3D printing your own lab equipment. *PLoS Biol*. 2015; 13(5): e1002175. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.1002175> PMID: 25996924
5. Chagas AM, Baden T. Open Source Toolkit: Hardware. In: *PLoS Blogs* [Internet]. 2015. <http://blogs.plos.org/collections/open-source-toolkit-hardware/>
6. Pearce JM. *Open-Source lab*. 1st ed. Elsevier. Elsevier; 2013.
7. Forman CJ, Tomes H, Mbobo B, Baden T, Raimondo J V. Openspritzer: an open hardware pressure ejection system for reliably delivering picolitre volumes. *bioRxiv*. 2016; <https://doi.org/10.1101/093633>.
8. Oswald D, Lin S, Waddell S. Light, heat, action: neural control of fruit fly behaviour. *Philos Trans R Soc Lond B Biol Sci*. 2015; 370: 20140211. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2014.0211> PMID: 26240426
9. Bernstein JG, Garrity PA, Boyden ES. Optogenetics and thermogenetics: technologies for controlling the activity of targeted cells within intact neural circuits. *Curr Opin Neurobiol*. 2012; 22: 61–71. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conb.2011.10.023> PMID: 22119320
10. Nagel G, Szellas T, Huhn W, Kateriya S, Adeishvili N, Berthold P, et al. Channelrhodopsin-2, a directly light-gated cation-selective membrane channel. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*. National Academy of Sciences; 2003; 100: 13940–5.
11. PublicLab. *Public Lab Spectrometer* [Internet]. <https://publiclab.org/wiki/spectrometer/>
12. Belušič G, Ilić M, Meglič A, Pirih P, Mogdans J, Coombs SL, et al. A fast multispectral light synthesiser based on LEDs and a diffraction grating. *Sci Rep*. 2016; 6: 32012. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep32012> PMID: 27558155
13. Arduino [Internet]. <http://www.arduino.cc/>
14. Raspberry Pi [Internet]. <http://www.raspberrypi.org/>
15. Klapoetke NC, Murata Y, Kim SS, Pulver SR, Birdsey-Benson A, Cho YK, et al. Independent optical excitation of distinct neural populations. *Nat Methods*. 2014; 11: 338–46. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nmeth.2836> PMID: 24509633
16. Pulver SR, Pashkovski SL, Hornstein NJ, Garrity PA, Griffith LC. Temporal dynamics of neuronal activation by Channelrhodopsin-2 and TRPA1 determine behavioral output in *Drosophila* larvae. *J Neurophysiol*. 2009; 101: 3075–88. <https://doi.org/10.1152/jn.00071.2009> PMID: 19339465
17. Prieto Godino LL, Baden T. TReND in Africa [Internet]. www.TReNDinAfrica.org/
18. Sánchez-Alcañiz JA, Zappia G, Marion-Poll F, Benton R, Montell C. A mechanosensory receptor required for food texture detection in *Drosophila*. *Nat Commun*. 2017; 8: 14192. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms14192> PMID: 28128210
19. Baden T. Parametric 3 axis manipulator—optional servo mounts [Internet]. 2014; <http://www.thingiverse.com/thing:239105/>
20. Adafruit Neopixels [Internet]. <https://www.adafruit.com/category/168/>
21. Tsien RY. The green fluorescent protein. *Annu Rev Biochem*. 1998; 67: 509–44. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.biochem.67.1.509> PMID: 9759496

22. Euler T, Hausselt SE, Margolis DJ, Breuninger T, Castell X, Detwiler PB, et al. Eyecup scope—optical recordings of light stimulus-evoked fluorescence signals in the retina. *Pflugers Arch*. 2009; 457: 1393–414. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00424-008-0603-5> PMID: 19023590
23. “khufkens.” OV5647 Quantum efficiency [Internet]. 2015. <https://publiclab.org/notes/khufkens/11-02-2015/ov5647-raspberry-pi-camera-spectral-response-quantum-efficiency/>
24. Pulver SR, Bayley TG, Taylor AL, Berni J, Bate M, Hedwig B. Imaging fictive locomotor patterns in larval *Drosophila*. *J Neurophysiol*. 2015; 114: 2564–77. <https://doi.org/10.1152/jn.00731.2015> PMID: 26311188
25. Branson K, Robie AA, Bender J, Perona P, Dickinson MH. High-throughput ethomics in large groups of *Drosophila*. *Nat Methods* 2009; 6: 451–7. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nmeth.1328> PMID: 19412169
26. Boyden ES, Zhang F, Bamberg E, Nagel G, Deisseroth K. Millisecond-timescale, genetically targeted optical control of neural activity. *Nat Neurosci*. 2005; 8: 1263–1268. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nn1525> PMID: 16116447
27. Arrenberg AB, Stainier DYR, Baier H, Huisken J. Optogenetic control of cardiac function. *Science*. 2010; 330: 971–4. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1195929> PMID: 21071670
28. Arrenberg AB, Del Bene F, Baier H. Optical control of zebrafish behavior with halorhodopsin. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*. 2009; 106: 17968–73. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0906252106> PMID: 19805086
29. Prieto-Godino LL, Rytz R, Cruchet S, Bargeton B, Abuin L, Silbering AF, et al. Evolution of Acid-Sensing Olfactory Circuits in *Drosophilids*. *Neuron*. 2017; 93: 661–676.e6. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuron.2016.12.024> PMID: 28111079
30. Dunn TW, Gebhardt C, Naumann EA, Riegler C, Ahrens MB, Engert F, et al. Neural Circuits Underlying Visually Evoked Escapes in Larval Zebrafish. *Neuron*. Elsevier; 2016; 89: 613–628.
31. Kokel D, Dunn TW, Ahrens MB, Alshut R, Cheung CYJ, Saint-Amant L, et al. Identification of Nonvisual Photomotor Response Cells in the Vertebrate Hindbrain. *J Neurosci*. 2013; 33(9): 3834–43. <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.3689-12.2013> PMID: 23447595
32. Jenett A, Rubin GM, Ngo TTB, Shepherd D, Murphy C, Dionne H, et al. A GAL4-Driver Line Resource for *Drosophila* Neurobiology. *Cell Rep*. 2012; 2: 991–1001. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.celrep.2012.09.011> PMID: 23063364
33. Schwarz O, Bohra AA, Liu X, Reichert H, VijayRaghavan K, Pielage J, et al. Motor control of *Drosophila* feeding behavior. *Elife* 2017; 6: 615–628.
34. Berni J, Pulver SR, Griffith LC, Bate M. Autonomous circuitry for substrate exploration in freely moving *Drosophila* larvae. *Curr Biol*. 2012; 22: 1861–70. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2012.07.048> PMID: 22940472
35. Sharkey JP, Foo DCW, Kabla A, Baumberg JJ, Bowman RW. A one-piece 3D printed flexure translation stage for open-source microscopy. *Rev Sci Instrum*. 2016; 87(2): 25104.
36. Miller AR, Davis GL, Oden ZM, Razavi MR, Fateh A, Ghazanfari M, et al. Portable, Battery-Operated, Low-Cost, Bright Field and Fluorescence Microscope. Doherty TM, editor. *PLoS One*. 2010; 5: e11890. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0011890> PMID: 20694194
37. Holm T, Klein T, Löscherberger A, Klamp T, Wiebusch G, van de Linde S, et al. A Blueprint for Cost-Efficient Localization Microscopy. *Chem. Phys. Chem*. 2014; 15: 651–654. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cphc.201300739> PMID: 24227751
38. Kim H, Gerber LC, Chiu D, Lee SA, Cira NJ, Xia SY, et al. LudusScope: Accessible Interactive Smartphone Microscopy for Life-Science Education. *PLoS One* 2016; 11: e0162602. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0162602> PMID: 27706189
39. Cybulski JS, Clements J, Prakash M. Foldscope: origami-based paper microscope. *PLoS One* 2014; 9: e98781. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0098781> PMID: 24940755
40. Wei Q, Qi H, Luo W, Tseng D, Ki SJ, Wan Z, et al. Fluorescent Imaging of Single Nanoparticles and Viruses on a Smart Phone. *ACS Nano* 2013; 7: 9147–9155. <https://doi.org/10.1021/nm4037706> PMID: 24016065
41. Baden T, Riad I. FlyPiScope [Internet]. <http://www.thingiverse.com/thing:1865014/>
42. LEGO-FlyPi [Internet]. <http://www.instructables.com/id/A-Raspberry-Pi-camera-based-microscope-built-from-/>
43. Zhang M. Scratching the Color Filter Array Layer Off a DSLR Sensor for Sharper B&W Photos [Internet]. 2013. https://calendar.google.com/calendar/render?pli=1#main_7/
44. Griffiths N, Jaipargas E-A, Wozny MR, Barton KA, Mathur N, Delfosse K, et al. Photo-convertible fluorescent proteins as tools for fresh insights on subcellular interactions in plants. *J Microsc*. 2016; 263(2): 148–57. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jmi.12383> PMID: 26820914

45. Nienhaus K, Nienhaus GU. Fluorescent proteins for live-cell imaging with super-resolution. *Chem Soc Rev.* 2014; 43: 1088–106. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c3cs60171d> PMID: 24056711
46. Schmidt A, Wiesner B, Schüle R, Teichmann A. Use of Kaede and Kikume green-red fusions for live cell imaging of G protein-coupled receptors. *Methods Mol Biol.* 2014; 1174: 139–56. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4939-0944-5_9 PMID: 24947379
47. Yusuf S, Baden T, Prieto-Godino LL. Bridging the Gap: establishing the necessary infrastructure and knowledge for teaching and research in neuroscience in Africa. *Metab Brain Dis.* 2014; 29: 217–20. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11011-013-9443-x> PMID: 24166356
48. Baden T. Open Labware [Internet]. www.Open-Labware.net/
49. PLoS Open Hardware Collection [Internet]. <http://collections.plos.org/open-source-toolkit-hardware/>
50. OpenSCAD [Internet]. <http://www.openscad.org/>
51. KiCad [Internet].: www.kicad.org
52. Python Serial library [Internet].: <https://pypi.python.org/pypi/pyserial>
53. Tkinter [Internet].: <https://wiki.python.org/moin/TkInter>
54. Raspian [Internet].: <https://www.raspbian.org/>
55. New out of the box Software (NOOBS) [Internet].: <https://www.raspberrypi.org/downloads/noobs/>
56. Debian [Internet].: <https://www.debian.org/>

PERSPECTIVE

Haves and have nots must find a better way: The case for open scientific hardware

André Maia Chagas ^{1,2,3,4,5*}

1 Werner Reichardt Centre for Integrative Neurosciences, University of Tübingen, Tübingen, Germany, **2** Graduate School for Neural and Behavioural Sciences, University of Tübingen, Tübingen, Germany, **3** TReND in Africa gUG, Bonn, Germany, **4** Institute of Ophthalmic Research, University of Tübingen, Tübingen, Germany, **5** School of Life Sciences, University of Sussex, Brighton, United Kingdom

* a.maia-chagas@sussex.ac.uk

 OPEN ACCESS

Citation: Maia Chagas A (2018) Haves and have nots must find a better way: The case for open scientific hardware. *PLoS Biol* 16(9): e3000014. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.3000014>

Published: September 27, 2018

Copyright: © 2018 André Maia Chagas. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Funding: AMC was supported by the Levelhulme Trust (Sir Philipp Leverhulme Prize 2017 for biological sciences awarded to Tom Baden). The funders had no role in study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the manuscript.

Competing interests: I have read the journal's policy and the author of this manuscript has the following competing interests: Editor of the Open Source Toolkit Channel for PLOS.

Abbreviations: AfricaOSH, African Open Source Hardware Summit; CCD, charge-coupled device; CERN, European Organization for Nuclear Research; CPU, central processing unit; DIY, do-it-yourself; FOSH, free open source hardware; GDP, gross domestic product.

Provenance: Not commissioned; externally peer reviewed.

Abstract

Many efforts are making science more open and accessible; they are mostly concentrated on issues that appear before and after experiments are performed: open access journals, open databases, and many other tools to increase reproducibility of science and access to information. However, these initiatives do not promote access to scientific equipment necessary for experiments. Mostly due to monetary constraints, equipment availability has always been uneven around the globe, affecting predominantly low-income countries and institutions. Here, a case is made for the use of free open source hardware in research and education, including countries and institutions where funds were never the biggest problem.

In 2013, Eve Marder [1] expressed concerns about the increasing costs of equipment necessary to do state-of-the-art research in the field of biology and the decreasing amount of funding available to be shared between an ever-growing number of labs and researchers. Even though the funding situation in the United States has improved since 2013, a closer look shows that the investments accumulated an inflation of 9% in the period between 2012 and 2017 [2] and a budget increase of 4.5% and 6% for the National Institutes of Health and National Science Foundation, respectively [3] [4], while the Environmental Protection Agency has had a cut of 4.5% in the same period [5]. The concerns raised by this situation have been expressed for quite some time in many places of the world, where lower investment (as a proportion of gross domestic product [GDP]) in science and education makes research conditions suboptimal and access to bleeding edge technology and tools difficult. Now, in times of shrinking funding, however, this difficulty is being felt by researchers in places earlier considered safe havens of science. One of the fears Professor Marder expressed is that we might return to the “old days,” when only a privileged few men were able to do research.

A major reason for high prices in scientific equipment is related to the way innovation, technological development, and new knowledge generated inside universities and research institutes are introduced to the world: to make them commercially interesting and to allow their development outside academia, they are protected using legal mechanisms such as

patents and/or copyrights, which are then licensed/sold to companies. Although this system enables universities and companies to work in collaboration and leverage each others' strengths, it ends up locking away research results funded with public money. Not only is this morally debatable, but it also does the following:

1. increases costs in product development, as each patent normally requires the involvement of specialised lawyers and has several fees that can easily sum up to considerable amounts (between US\$10,000 and US\$30,000 in 2018 [6]);
2. slows down innovation cycles, as sometimes companies owning patents do not invest in further developing them into commercial applications, delaying derivative innovations that would rise from its implementation [7]. Kodak for example patented [8] the idea for a charge-coupled device (CCD) digital camera (the same as today's digital cameras) in 1978, but the first commercial versions were only released by Fuji in 1989 [9];
3. creates instruments/technologies that are "black boxes" since consumers are not allowed to open them up (for repair, maintenance, or simple curiosity), which, in the case of scientific equipment, can lead to an incomplete understanding of how complex instruments work as well as their capabilities and limitations;
4. and equipment ends up being used in suboptimal conditions or thrown away instead of being repaired, especially in countries where manufacturing companies do not offer appropriate customer support [10].

An alternative to this production model exists, and it relies on a free distribution philosophy, in which code and design blueprints are shared freely so that anyone can study, build, modify, and improve existing projects. This philosophy is strongly present in the software industry, more known as open source, in which several companies act as service providers for their products instead of leveraging scarcity and intellectual property [11]. One example of such a company is Red Hat, which was founded in 1993 and has, as of 2015, reported over 2 billion dollars in revenue yearly for the last three years [12].

As a consequence, researchers can now use freely available software for most of their work-related tasks (e.g., office suites, statistics, or data analysis packages), which in turn helps reduce research costs and frees resources for other expenses (as well as improves research quality and scientific outputs [13]—a more detailed description of the benefits of using freely available initiatives can be found in the following paragraphs). For Eve Marder's main concern—the lack of funds to buy expensive equipment—a solution was still lacking. While this is worrisome, the increasing affordability of electronic systems to the general public should provide relief to the problem, as they can be used to assemble tools in an open source way in which everyone is free to use and improve designs based on their specific needs. Smartphones, for example, carry powerful central processing units (CPUs), camera, microphone, and an array of sensors, which makes these ever-present devices excellent tools for recording, analysing, and visualizing data [14]. One popular application is smartphone-based microscopes, in which a glass bead or other inexpensive plastic lens (normally found inside a laser pointer) can be placed in front of the smartphone camera for very large magnifications (see Table 1 for examples). A brief online search for "phone microscope" will guide the reader to a wealth of similar projects. The quality of such simple microscopes allows users, among other things, to image blood samples for diagnostics [15], with costs in the range of US\$5–US\$20 (assuming users already have a smartphone with a camera).

In contrast to this, the initial cost for a "scientific-grade" optical microscope is in the range of thousands of dollars, with prices rising steeply for more complex designs, severely

Table 1.

Smartphone-based microscopes	
PNNL Smartphone Microscope	https://availabletechnologies.pnnl.gov/technology.asp?id=393
US\$10 smartphone-to-microscope conversion	http://www.instructables.com/id/10-Smartphone-to-digital-microscope-conversion/
PhoneScope	https://www.thingiverse.com/thing:280004
LudusScope	http://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0162602
Smartphone clip-on microscope	https://www.amazon.com/KINGMAS-Microscope-Magnifier-Universal-Smartphones/dp/B00PQ9XV2E
Open source optical microscopes	
FlyPi	http://journals.plos.org/plosbiology/article/metrics?id=10.1371/journal.pbio.2002702#citedHeade
Open Source Multifluorescence System	http://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0187163
OpenFlexure Microscope	http://tutorial.waterscope.org/
Foldscope	https://www.foldscope.com/
The Open Source Microscope	http://openlabtools.eng.cam.ac.uk/Instruments/Microscope/
Public Lab Basic Microscope	https://publiclab.org/wiki/basic-microscope
Free and open source automated 3D microscope	http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/jmi.12433/full
Hackaday.io list on optical microscopes	https://hackaday.io/list/12057-optical-microscope-projects
Organizations using FOSH for education	
TReND in Africa	http://trendinafrica.org/
Biohackacademy	http://biohackacademy.github.io/bha2/
Lego2Nano	http://lego2nano.openwisdomlab.net/index.html
Public Lab	https://publiclab.org/
PhotosynQ	https://photosynq.org/education
Conector Ciência	http://www.conecien.com/
ScienceXplore	https://www.sciencexplore.org/
Backyard brains	http://blog.backyardbrains.com
FOSH for science (publications, companies, and nonacademics)	
Smart tube holder for centrifuges	http://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0195907
Optics	http://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0059840
Defibrillator	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2468067217300354
Microfluidic thermometer	http://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0189430
Time sorting pitfall trap	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2468067216300220?via%3Dihub
Automated four-point probe	http://www.mdpi.com/1996-1944/10/2/110
Pico Spritzer	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-017-02301-2
pH Stat	http://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0193744
Ultrasonic signal generator	https://arxiv.org/abs/1610.00492
Automated feeder	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2468067216300050?via%3Dihub
Plant tissue culture system	https://plantmethods.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s13007-017-0156-8
PCR machine	http://openpcr.org/
US\$5 PCR machine	https://hackaday.io/project/1864-5-dna-replicator
Electrophysiology system	http://www.open-ephys.org/
Raspberry Pi-based supercomputer I	http://www.southampton.ac.uk/mediacentre/features/raspberry_pi_supercomputer.shtml
Test Tube photometer	http://openplant.science/2017/12/09/photometer-shopping-list.html

(Continued)

Table 1. (Continued)

Generic lab equipment	http://www.gaudi.ch/GaudiLabs/?page_id=328
Scanning electron microscope	http://benkrasnow.blogspot.de/2011/04/diy-scanning-electron-microscope-image.html
Prostheses I	http://www.openbionics.org/
Prostheses II	http://enablingthefuture.org/
Water quality-testing platform	http://www.appropedia.org/Open-source_mobile_water_quality_testing_platform
FOSH repositories	
Appropedia	http://www.appropedia.org/
Hackaday	www.hackaday.io
Hackteria	http://hackteria.org/
BioHackacademy	https://github.com/BioHackAcademy
PLOS Channels–Open Source Toolkit	https://channels.plos.org/open-source-toolkit
Openeuroscience	www.openeuroscience.com
Github	https://github.com
Gitlab	https://gitlab.com/
Open Plant Science	http://openplant.science/
Journal of Open Hardware	http://openhardware.metajnl.com/
HardwareX	https://www.journals.elsevier.com/hardwarex
KitSpace	https://kitspace.org/
DocuBricks	https://www.docubricks.com/
Wevolver	https://www.wevolver.com/discover
Open Hardware Repository	https://www.ohwr.org/projects

Abbreviations: FOSH, free open source hardware; PNNL, Pacific Northwest National Laboratory.

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.3000014.t001>

constraining access to such a fundamental tool. As such devices are core to scientific investigations, there have been several open source models beyond just the “basic smartphone hack;” some examples can be found in Table 1. They have different capabilities and different levels of complexity, but all of these freely distributed models have two key features in common: (i) they are produced with “off-the-shelf” components, which are mostly cheap and easy to get, and (ii) their designs and bill of materials are available online, allowing anyone to build as well as customize/improve them, depending on specific needs and material availability [16]. These features are nothing more than the translation of the open source software philosophy to the world of hardware (a more rigorous definition can be found on the Open Source Hardware Association page [17]). Like in software, the adoption of this philosophy in research and education has deeper implications, which have been debated in reference to specific fields (analytical chemistry [18], engineering [19], life sciences [20], and nanotechnology [21]) as well as concerning research in general [22,23]. The common implications of adopting free open source hardware (FOSH) are summarized below:

1. It allows more people to participate in the scientific endeavour, in turn enabling research to be done outside academia, enabling people to exercise their curiosity and better understand the world around them. Public Lab [24] and Safecast [25] are two good examples of non-profit organizations that use FOSH to empower global communities to gather data about environmental variables and to understand the impact of human activity on the environment, health, and quality of life.

2. It allows for a better understanding of the tools themselves because the available blueprints can be studied, leading to more informed decisions by users concerning the feasibility of experiments and the results they can expect. This, in turn, can also lead to better reproducibility, as researchers can calibrate their devices according to the blueprints more often and make sure they are performing consistently at high standards, avoiding discrepancies in experimental outcomes.
3. In long-term projects lasting years or even decades, laboratories are less vulnerable to supply problems. If a company producing a certain device decides to discontinue its production or if the company goes out of business, researchers are left orphaned without means to repair or replace said device in the case of malfunction. If all the build plans are open, scientists can reproduce/repair it themselves or find other companies to produce them on demand. A concrete example [26] of this issue is provided by the European Organization for Nuclear Research (CERN) in which a specific hardware license [27] and several businesses protocols were created to ensure that hardware developed and sold to the project would have to comply with this license. This has enabled close collaborations in tool development between CERN and the hardware industry (as CERN employees could freely apply their expertise, both as end users and as engineers) and made the project robust to fluctuations in the market, since the necessary tools could be sourced from many suppliers.
4. In a FOSH-rich environment, information about material costs are easy to obtain and building plans are publicly available. Therefore, consumers are better equipped to decide whether the price being charged for a certain equipment is reasonable and to decide which route to take; they can invest time and effort in building, calibrating, and repairing their own tools (therefore saving money) or they can invest money to hire a company to do it for them (saving time and effort). In this new setting, saving potentials are quite large [28], without excluding companies from operating and offering valuable services for research and education.
5. The lower price tag on FOSH enables scientists in regions that are normally constrained by lack of funds to address scientific problems previously outside their reach. It fosters the discovery of untapped talent and paves the way for inside-out development, rather than relying on external aid and humanitarian assistance, a model that has had little success [29]. TReND in Africa [30], a volunteer-run nongovernmental organization, is leveraging this idea to train researchers in Africa on basic electronics and 3D printing as tools to develop labware and to involve academics in the global “maker movement” [31].
6. FOSH is also an excellent tool for education. As curious people learn how to build their own equipment, they are “forced” to learn about physics, electronics, and biology (see Table 1 for examples), creating new teaching possibilities for both schools and universities. Content can be taught in a “hands-on approach” by which students are challenged with a scientific question and try to solve it by thinking about what kind of experiments will be needed, building the instruments, gathering data, and drawing conclusions from them.

More examples of scientific equipment produced under the open source paradigm can be found for PCR machines, electrophysiology systems, supercomputers, prostheses, centrifuges, optics, spectrometers, diving robots, and even electron microscopes (Table 1 and Fig 1). The list is not exhaustive and new tools are added to online repositories and dedicated journals almost daily (Table 1).

In this modern version of the “do-it-yourself” (DIY) tradition, people are developing tools with bits, bytes, resistors, and integrated circuits. They are still learning what works and what

Fig 1. Open source hardware for research and education. A. Time-sorting pitfall trap and temperature logger [32]. B. “Smart” tube holder for real-time sample monitoring [33]. C. Pipetting robot for toxicological assays [34]. D. Low-cost multifluorescence system [35].

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.3000014.g001>

doesn't, becoming ever more interdisciplinary, interconnected, and increasing the complexity of their designs. Taking advantage of the Internet, project repositories and information hubs are coming alive, breaking down the ivory tower, as scientists, makers, DIYers, and hobbyists interact on the same level, suggesting, contributing, and improving each others' projects in a much richer peer review system, done by many, instead of just two or three pairs of eyes, and in an iterative manner. A prime example is the community growing around the *Gathering for Open Scientific Hardware* [36], set to have its third meeting from October 10th–13th 2018, bringing together ideas from different fields and creating collaborative, inclusive documentation, a manifesto [37], a roadmap ([38] for an ambitious but noble destination) to make open science hardware ubiquitous by 2025 and more importantly, a truly global community spirit [39], in which interdisciplinary and international events have been organized by the community members, among them the African Open Source Hardware Summit ([40], AfricaOSH), project Vuela! [41], and workshops on Open Source Laboratory equipment [42].

In 2013, Professor Marder was concerned by the number of times the phrase “the haves and the have nots” was being used in academia and the divide it represented. Even if the problem

was solved by unlimited funding, it did not address the fact that, in the current system, institutions and labs that belong to the group that “has” are still in a system held hostage by their own tools. In order to solve this issue, we don’t necessarily need more money but rather need to reassess our relationship to knowledge and technology, how it determines our role in society, and how we want to spend grant money entrusted to us by the people. By making our tools and knowledge truly free, “haves and have nots” will not only erase the divide but will actually move together to a better way.

References

1. Marder E. Living Science: The haves and the have nots. In: eLife [Internet]. 19 Nov 2013 [cited 17 Aug 2018]. <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.01515> PMID: 24252880
2. CPI Inflation Calculator [Internet]. [cited 7 Sep 2018]. https://www.bls.gov/data/inflation_calculator.htm
3. NIMH » Budget [Internet]. [cited 7 Sep 2018]. <https://www.nimh.nih.gov/about/budget/index.shtml>
4. Budget and Performance | NSF—National Science Foundation [Internet]. [cited 7 Sep 2018]. <https://www.nsf.gov/about/performance/>
5. US EPA O. EPA’s Budget and Spending. In: US EPA [Internet]. 8 Feb 2013 [cited 7 Sep 2018]. <https://www.epa.gov/planandbudget/budget>
6. Officer O of the CF. USPTO Fee Schedule [Internet]. [cited 22 Aug 2018]. [/learning-and-resources/fees-and-payment/uspto-fee-schedule](https://www.uspto.gov/learning-and-resources/fees-and-payment/uspto-fee-schedule)
7. Stiglitz DB Arjun Jayadev and Joseph. Innovation, Intellectual Property, and Development: A Better Set of Approaches for the 21st Century | Reports | CEPR [Internet]. [cited 17 Aug 2018]. <http://cepr.net/publications/reports/innovation-intellectual-property-and-development-a-better-set-of-approaches-for-the-21st-century>
8. Lloyd GA, Sasson SJ. United States Patent: 4131919—Electronic still camera [Internet]. 4131919, 1978. <http://patft.uspto.gov/netacgi/nph-Parser?Sect2=PTO1&Sect2=HITOFF&p=1&u=/netahtml/PTO/search-bool.html&r=1&f=G&l=50&d=PALL&RefSrch=yes&Query=PN/4131919>
9. Innovation History. In: FUJIFILM United Kingdom [Internet]. [cited 22 Aug 2018]. <https://www.fujifilm.eu/uk/about-us/history/innovation-history>
10. Perry L, Malkin R. Effectiveness of medical equipment donations to improve health systems: how much medical equipment is broken in the developing world? *Med Biol Eng Comput.* 2011; 49: 719–722. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11517-011-0786-3> PMID: 21597999
11. Eric S. Raymond. Cathedral and the Bazaar [Internet]. <http://archive.org/details/CathedralAndTheBazaar>
12. Financial Statements [Internet]. [cited 20 Aug 2018]. <https://investors.redhat.com/financial-information/financial-statements>
13. Goble C. Better Software, Better Research. *IEEE Internet Comput.* 2014; 18: 4–8. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MIC.2014.88>
14. Malykhina E. 8 Apps That Turn Citizens into Scientists. In: *Scientific American* [Internet]. [cited 17 Aug 2018]. <https://www.scientificamerican.com/article/8-apps-that-turn-citizens-into-scientists/>
15. Switz NA, D’Ambrosio MV, Fletcher DA. Low-Cost Mobile Phone Microscopy with a Reversed Mobile Phone Camera Lens. *PLoS ONE.* 2014; 9: e95330. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0095330> PMID: 24854188
16. Bonvoisin J, Mies R, Boujut J-F, Stark R. What is the “Source” of Open Source Hardware? *J Open Hardw.* 2017; 1. <https://doi.org/10.5334/joh.7>
17. Definition (English). In: Open Source Hardware Association [Internet]. 26 May 2012 [cited 17 Aug 2018]. <https://www.oshwa.org/definition/>
18. Dryden MDM, Fobel R, Fobel C, Wheeler AR. Upon the Shoulders of Giants: Open-Source Hardware and Software in Analytical Chemistry. *Anal Chem.* 2017; 89: 4330–4338. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.analchem.7b00485> PMID: 28379683
19. Berg DR, Niemeyer KE. The case for openness in engineering research. *F1000Research.* 2018; 7: 501. <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.14593.1>
20. Baden T, Chagas AM, Gage G, Marzullo T, Prieto-Godino LL, Euler T. Open Labware: 3-D Printing Your Own Lab Equipment. *PLoS Biol.* 2015; 13: e1002086. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.1002086> PMID: 25794301

21. Pearce JM. Open-source nanotechnology: Solutions to a modern intellectual property tragedy. *Nano Today*. 2013; 8: 339–341. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nantod.2013.04.001>
22. Pearce JM. Building Research Equipment with Free, Open-Source Hardware. *Science*. 2012; 337: 1303–1304. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1228183> PMID: 22984059
23. Kera D. Science Artisans and Open Science Hardware. *Bull Sci Technol Soc*. 2017; 37: 97–111. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0270467618774978>
24. Public Lab: a DIY environmental science community [Internet]. [cited 20 Aug 2018]. <https://publiclab.org/>
25. Safecast. In: Safecast [Internet]. [cited 20 Aug 2018]. <https://blog.safecast.org/>
26. CERN launches Open Hardware initiative | Media and Press Relations [Internet]. [cited 20 Aug 2018]. <http://press.cern/press-releases/2011/07/cern-launches-open-hardware-initiative>
27. Open Hardware Repository | CERN Open Hardware Licence—CERN OHL [Internet]. [cited 20 Aug 2018]. <https://www.ohwr.org/documents/294>
28. Pearce JM. Return on investment for open source scientific hardware development. *Sci Public Policy*. 2016; 43: 192–195. <https://doi.org/10.1093/scipol/scv034>
29. Moyo D. *Dead Aid: Why aid is not working and how there is another way for Africa*. Penguin UK; 2011.
30. TRenD | Teaching and Research in Natural Sciences for Development in Africa [Internet]. [cited 4 Mar 2016]. <http://preview.trendinafrica.org/>
31. Quinn AM, Paffhausen B, Chagas AM. Implementation of a Novel Educational Course to Teach 3D Printing, Circuit Design, and Programming to PhD Candidates in Nigeria. *SocArXiv*. 2017; <https://doi.org/10.31235/osf.io/pyh2r>
32. McMunn MS. A time-sorting pitfall trap and temperature datalogger for the sampling of surface-active arthropods. *HardwareX*. 2017; 1: 38–45. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ohx.2017.02.001>
33. Hoang T, Moskwa N, Halvorsen K. A ‘smart’ tube holder enables real-time sample monitoring in a standard lab centrifuge. *PLoS ONE*. 2018; 13: e0195907. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0195907> PMID: 29659624
34. Steffens S, Nüßer L, Seiler T-B, Ruchter N, Schumann M, Döring R, et al. A versatile and low-cost open source pipetting robot for automation of toxicological and ecotoxicological bioassays. *PLoS ONE*. 2017; 12: e0179636. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0179636> PMID: 28622373
35. Nuñez I, Matute T, Herrera R, Keymer J, Marzullo T, Rudge T, et al. Low cost and open source multi-fluorescence imaging system for teaching and research in biology and bioengineering. *PLoS ONE*. 2017; 12: e0187163. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0187163> PMID: 29140977
36. Dosemagen S, Liboiron M, Molloy J. Gathering for Open Science Hardware 2016. *J Open Hardw*. 2017; 1. <https://doi.org/10.5334/joh.5>
37. GOSH Manifesto. In: Gathering for Open Science Hardware [Internet]. [cited 20 Aug 2018]. <http://openhardware.science/gosh-manifesto/>
38. Global Open Science Hardware Roadmap. In: Gathering for Open Science Hardware [Internet]. [cited 20 Aug 2018]. <http://openhardware.science/global-open-science-hardware-roadmap/>
39. GOSH Community Forum. In: GOSH Community Forum [Internet]. [cited 20 Aug 2018]. <http://forum.openhardware.science/>
40. Africa Open Science & Hardware Summit. In: Africa OSH [Internet]. [cited 20 Aug 2018]. africaosh.com
41. Bernaldo P, Irujo GP, Pérez A, Narváez N, Jude L, Egozcue A. ¡Vuela!—Open science with drones—Ciencia libre con drones. *Open Sci Framew*. 2017;
42. Open science hardware across the Andes. In: Gathering for Open Science Hardware [Internet]. [cited 20 Aug 2018]. <http://openhardware.science/2018/04/16/open-science-hardware-across-the-andes/>

An arbitrary-spectrum spatial visual stimulator for vision research

Katrin Franke^{1,2†}, André Maia Chagas^{1,3,4†}, Zhijian Zhao^{1,3},
Maxime JY Zimmermann⁴, Philipp Bartel⁴, Yongrong Qiu^{1,3}, Klaudia P Szatko^{1,2},
Tom Baden^{1,4}, Thomas Euler^{1,2,3*}

¹Institute for Ophthalmic Research, University of Tübingen, Tübingen, Germany; ²Bernstein Center for Computational Neuroscience, University of Tübingen, Tübingen, Germany; ³Center for Integrative Neuroscience, University of Tübingen, Tübingen, Germany; ⁴Sussex Neuroscience, School of Life Sciences, University of Sussex, Falmer, United Kingdom

Abstract Visual neuroscientists require accurate control of visual stimulation. However, few stimulator solutions simultaneously offer high spatio-temporal resolution and free control over the spectra of the light sources, because they rely on off-the-shelf technology developed for human trichromatic vision. Importantly, consumer displays fail to drive UV-shifted short wavelength-sensitive photoreceptors, which strongly contribute to visual behaviour in many animals, including mice, zebrafish and fruit flies. Moreover, many non-mammalian species feature more than three spectral photoreceptor types. Here, we present a flexible, spatial visual stimulator with up to six arbitrary spectrum chromatic channels. It combines a standard digital light processing engine with open source hard- and software that can be easily adapted to the experimentalist's needs. We demonstrate the capability of this general visual stimulator experimentally in the in vitro mouse retinal whole-mount and the in vivo zebrafish. With this work, we intend to start a community effort of sharing and developing a common stimulator design for vision research.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.48779.001>

*For correspondence:
thomas.euler@cin.uni-tuebingen.de

†These authors contributed equally to this work

Competing interests: The authors declare that no competing interests exist.

Funding: See page 24

Received: 24 May 2019

Accepted: 20 September 2019

Published: 23 September 2019

Reviewing editor: Alexander Borst, Max Planck Institute of Neurobiology, Germany

© Copyright Franke et al. This article is distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/), which permits unrestricted use and redistribution provided that the original author and source are credited.

Introduction

Challenges in visual stimulation

From psychophysics to single-cell physiology, neuroscientists fundamentally rely on accurate stimulus control. At first glance, generating visual stimuli appears to be much easier than, for example, olfactory stimuli, because computer screens and video projectors are omnipresent, suggesting a range of cost-effective choices for the vision researcher. However, commercially available display devices target human consumers and, thus, are designed for the primate visual system. These devices provide superb spatial resolution, approximately cover the colour space relevant for trichromatic human vision (reviewed in *SurrIDGE et al., 2003*) and support refresh rates that consider the human flicker-fusion frequency (e.g. *Hecht and Verrijp, 1933*). Moreover, as the emphasis is on improving the subjective viewing experience, commercial display devices typically lack or even purposefully distort properties that are important when used as visual stimulator for research.

While the spatial resolution provided by even basic commercial displays is typically in excess of what most model species can resolve, limitations may exist with respect to timing (i.e. refresh rate) and, in particular, colour space. For example, many insects including *Drosophila* have flicker fusion frequencies higher than 100 Hz (*Miall, 1978*) and use five or more main visual opsins (*Feuda et al., 2016*). For most vertebrate model species (e.g. mice and zebrafish), standard refresh rates of ~60 Hz suffice for the majority of stimulus requirements; however, the limited colour space poses a serious

issue: The light sources (i.e. light-emitting diodes, LEDs) are selected based on the spectrum spanned by the human cone photoreceptor opsins (*Dartnall et al., 1983; Nathans et al., 1986*) and spectrally arranged to cover the human trichromatic colour space. Hence, these devices fail to generate adequate colours for species with different spectral photoreceptor sensitivities and typically three-channel devices impose further limitations for species with more than three spectral types of (cone) photoreceptor (reviewed in *Baden and Osorio, 2019*).

Since some of the aforementioned constraints are 'hard-wired' in display devices for the consumer market, it is often impractical if not impossible to modify such devices. Specialised solutions aimed to overcome some of the above constraints are commercially available, for instance, as special calibrated LCD monitors for human psychophysics (e.g. Display++, Cambridge Research Systems, Rochester, UK). However, these solutions are expensive, optimised for primates and often closed source, which makes it difficult for the user to modify them. As a result, vision researchers either invest large amounts of time and/or money aiming to overcome these constraints or are forced to settle on a custom suboptimal solution that addresses the needs of a particular experimental situation. This, in turn, may critically limit the stimulus space that can be routinely explored, and yields substantial problems in reproducibility and interpretation when comparing physiological data between laboratories. Comparability and reproducibility are of particular interest in the backdrop of recent developments in increasingly efficient data acquisition technologies. For example, being able to simultaneously record from hundreds of neurons using multielectrode arrays (e.g. *Jun et al., 2017*) or two-photon functional imaging (e.g. *Ahrens et al., 2013; Stringer et al., 2019*) means that experimental limitations are rapidly shifting the 'bottleneck' away from the recording side towards the visual stimulation side.

Visual stimuli for current animal models

Choosing the adequate animal model for a specific research question may, on the one hand, greatly facilitate the experimental design and the interpretation of the results. On the other hand, when trying to transfer such results to other species, it is critical to keep in mind that each species is adapted to different environments and employs different strategies to survive and procreate (reviewed in *Baden and Osorio, 2019*). In vision research, classical studies often used monkeys and cats as model organisms, which with respect to visual stimuli, for example, in terms of spatial resolution and spectral sensitivity range, have similar requirements as humans. Today, frequently used animal models – such as *Drosophila*, zebrafish or rodents – feature adaptations of their visual systems outside the specifications for human vision: For instance, all of the aforementioned species possess UV-sensitive photoreceptors, zebrafish have tetrachromatic vision, and both zebrafish and *Drosophila* display higher flicker fusion frequencies than most mammals (reviewed in *Marshall and Arikawa, 2014; Boström et al., 2016*). Still, many studies in these species use visual stimulation devices produced and optimised for humans. At best, this will suboptimally drive the animal model's visual system, potentially resulting in wrong interpretations of the data.

Here, we present a highly flexible spatial visual stimulator with up to six arbitrary-spectrum chromatic channels. It builds upon a DLP LightCrafter (LCr), which uses a DMD (digital micromirror device) chip, originally developed by Texas Instruments (Dallas, TX; *Hornbeck, 1996*). The LCr and similar DMD-based 'light engines' are broadly used in consumer products. A DMD chip holds an array of tiny mirrors – each representing a pixel – that can be rapidly flipped between two positions, with the 'on' and 'off' position reflecting the incident light towards the projection optics or a 'light dump', respectively. The LCr we used here contains a single DMD chip and, hence, generates colour images by sequentially presenting the R/G/B contents (as 3×8 bitplanes) of each frame while turning on the respective LED. The intensity of a, say, green pixel is defined by the temporal pattern the corresponding DMD-mirror is flicked between the 'on' and 'off' position while the green LED is constantly on.

Because the spectrum of the light that illuminates the DMD chip can be (almost) arbitrary, a DLP-based projector like the LCr can be customised and adapted to different animal models and their spectral requirements – as has been demonstrated in earlier studies on mice (e.g. *Baden et al., 2016; Denman et al., 2017*), zebrafish (e.g. *Guggiana-Nilo and Engert, 2016*) and fruit flies (e.g. *Haberkern et al., 2019*). Alternatively, one can purchase an LCr with custom LEDs (including UV, for commercial systems, see Table 4) or build an external LED unit that illuminates the DMD chip via a light guide (e.g. *Tan et al., 2015*). Here, we use the highly flexible light guide LCr as a light engine

and demonstrate the adaptability of our solution using two exemplary animal species: mice and zebrafish (larvae). Mice currently represent a frequently used model for the mammalian visual system and serve as an example for UV-sensitive vision, while zebrafish are a representative for a well-studied non-mammalian vertebrate species with tetrachromatic vision. Since species-specific chromatic requirements are often more difficult to meet than, for instance, sufficient spatial resolution, our focus here is on adequate chromatic stimulation.

To achieve adequate chromatic stimulation, the spectral composition of the light sources in the stimulator need to cover the spectral sensitivity of the respective model organism. In the ideal case, there should be (i) as many LED peaks as the number of spectrally separable photoreceptor types and (ii) these should be distributed across the spectral sensitivity range of the species. In general, the spectral sensitivity of an animal is determined by the palette of light-sensitive proteins expressed in their photoreceptors. Vertebrate photoreceptors are divided into rod photoreceptors (rods) and cone photoreceptors (cones). Rods are usually more light-sensitive than cones and, hence, serve vision at dim illumination levels, whereas cones are active at brighter light levels and support colour vision. Depending on the peak sensitivity and the genetic similarity of their opsins, cones are grouped into short (sws, 'S'), medium (mws, 'M') and long wavelength-sensitive (lws, 'L') types, with the sws cones further subdivided into sws1 (near-ultraviolet to blue range, <430 nm, here 'UV') and sws2 (blue range, >430 nm) (reviewed in [Ebrey and Koutalos, 2001](#); [Yokoyama, 2000](#)). The rod:cone ratio of a species is related to the environmental light levels during their activity periods. For instance, while the central fovea of the macaque monkey retina lacks rods altogether, the rod:cone ratio in its periphery is approx. 30:1 ([Wikler and Rakic, 1990](#)) and therefore similar to that in mice ([Jeon et al., 1998](#)). In adult zebrafish, the rod:cone ratio is approx. 2:1 ([Hollbach et al., 2015](#)).

Many vertebrates feature a single type of rod (for exceptions, see [Baden and Osorio, 2019](#)) but up to five spectral types of cone, which is why cones are more relevant for chromatically adequate visual stimulation. Old-world primates including humans, for example, possess three spectral types of cones (S, M and L). Hence, these primates feature trichromatic daylight vision (reviewed in [Jacobs, 2008](#)). In contrast, mice are dichromatic like the majority of mammals; they only have two cone types (S and M; [Figure 1a–c](#)). Unlike most mammals, however, the spectral sensitivities of the mouse are shifted towards shorter wavelengths, resulting in a UV-sensitive S-opsin ([Jacobs et al., 1991](#)). While one cone type usually expresses only one opsin type, some mammalian species, such as mice or guinea pigs, show opsin co-expression: In mice, for instance, M-cones co-express S-opsin with increasing levels towards the ventral retina ([Figure 1b](#)) ([Applebury et al., 2000](#); [Baden et al., 2013](#); [Röhlich et al., 1994](#)). As a 'more typical' example for non-mammalian vertebrates, the cone-dominated retina of zebrafish contains four cone types, resulting in tetrachromatic vision ([Figure 1d](#)): In addition to S- and M-cones, they have also UV- and L-cones ([Chinen et al., 2003](#)). In adult zebrafish, all cone types are organised in a highly regular array, with alternating rows of UV-/S- and M-/L-cones ([Figure 1e,f](#)) ([Li et al., 2012](#)). In zebrafish larvae, however, the cone arrangement shows distinct anisotropic distributions for different cone types matched to image statistics present in natural scenes ([Figure 1g,h](#)) ([Zimmermann et al., 2018](#)).

Taken together, the diversity of spectral sensitivities present in common animal models used in visual neuroscience as well as their differences to the human visual system necessitates a species-specific stimulator design. Here, we present a highly flexible, relatively low-cost visual stimulation system that combines digital light processing (DLP) technology with easily customisable mechanics and electronics, as well as intuitive control software written in Python. We provide a detailed description of the stimulator design and discuss its limitations as well as possible modifications and extensions; all relevant documents are available online (for links, see [Table 1](#)). Finally, we demonstrate the use of our stimulator in two exemplary applications; as a dichromatic version for in vitro two-photon (2P) recordings in whole-mounted mouse retina and as a tetrachromatic version for in vivo 2P imaging in zebrafish larvae.

Results

Stimulator design

As the 'light engine' of our stimulator, we use the DLP LightCrafter 4500 (here, referred to as 'LCr') developed by Texas Instruments (Dallas, TX). The LCr is a bare-metal version for developers and

Figure 1. Photoreceptor types and distribution in mouse and zebrafish retina. (a) Peak-normalised sensitivity profiles of mouse S- (magenta) and M-opsin (green) as well as rhodopsin (black; profiles were estimated following [Stockman and Sharpe, 2000](#)). (b) Schematic drawing of the distribution of cone photoreceptor (cone) types in the mouse; rod photoreceptors (rods) are homogeneously distributed ([Jeon et al., 1998](#)) (not shown here). Purple dots represent 'true' S-cones exclusively expressing S-opsin ([Haverkamp et al., 2005](#)); ratio of co-expression of S-opsin in M-cones ([Applebury et al., 2000](#); [Baden et al., 2013](#)) is colour-coded from green to magenta (d, dorsal; t, temporal; v, ventral; n, nasal). (c) Illustration of mouse cone and rod arrangement (vertical view; OS+IS, outer and inner segments; ONL, outer nuclear layer; OPL, outer plexiform layer). (d) Peak-normalised sensitivity profiles of zebrafish UV- (magenta), S- (blue), M- (green) and L-opsin (red) as well as rhodopsin (black). (e) Schematic illustration of the regular cone arrangement in adult zebrafish. Coloured dots represent UV-, S-, M- and L-cones. (f) Like (c) but for adult zebrafish retina. (g) Schematic drawing illustrating the distribution of cone types in zebrafish larvae ([Zimmermann et al., 2018](#)). Colours as in (d). (h) Like (c,f) for zebrafish larvae. Lighter colour of rods indicate that they are not functional at this age (7–9 dpf; [Branchek and Bremiller, 1984](#); [Morris and Fadool, 2005](#)).

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.48779.002>

offers several advantages over consumer devices: (i) its control protocol is well documented (for links, see [Table 1](#)), allowing to program the device via a USB connection on-the-fly; (ii) its flexibility in terms of light sources; lightcrafters with customised LEDs ([Table 4](#)) and a version with a light guide port (see below) are available; (iii) its small footprint (15 × 10 × 5 cm) facilitates incorporating the LCr into existing setups. While the stimulators are built around the LCr, we attempted to use a minimum of commercial parts. Except for the specialised optical elements (i.e. dichroic filters, beam splitters, mirrors), most parts can be replaced by 3D printed parts (e.g. designed using OpenSCAD, see Key Resources Table) to increase flexibility and to lower the total costs. For example, instead of commercial rail systems, such as LINOS microbank (Qioptiq, Göttingen, Germany), alternative 3D-printed parts can be used ([Delmans and Haseloff, 2018](#)). All electronics and the visual stimulation software are Open Source ([Table 1](#)).

For the two-channel (dichromatic) mouse stimulator ([Figure 2a–c](#)), we used a light guide LCr (Fiber-E4500MKIITM, EKB Technologies Ltd., Israel). It lacks internal LEDs and the respective beam splitters and instead features a built-in port for a standard light guide (7 mm outer diameter, 5 mm core diameter; see recommendations by EKB). It was coupled by a light guide (for parts list, see [Table 2](#)) to an external illumination unit ([Figure 2a right,c](#)). In this unit, a long-pass dichroic mirror combines the light from two band pass-filtered LEDs (with $\lambda_{\text{peak}} = 387$ and 576 nm) and feeds it into a light guide using a fitting collimation adapter. This arrangement facilitates the exchange of the LEDs and allows to mount the illumination unit outside the microscope cabinet. One disadvantage

Table 1. For detailed part lists, see **Tables 2** and **3**.

Part	Links to online resources
TI DLP LightCrafter 4500 Evaluation Module ('LCr')	Product overview: http://www.ti.com/tool/dlplcr4500evm User guide: http://www.ti.com/lit/ug/dlpu011f/dlpu011f.pdf Programmer's guide: http://www.ti.com/lit/ug/dlpu010g/dlpu010g.pdf DLP4500 data sheet w/DMD specs: http://www.ti.com/lit/ds/symlink/dlp4500.pdf Alternate DMD windows for increased UV transmission: http://www.ti.com/lit/an/dlpa031d/dlpa031d.pdf DMD reflectance w/o window: https://ntrs.nasa.gov/archive/nasa/casi.ntrs.nasa.gov/20160010355.pdf
QDSpy – Open Source Visual stimulation software	Documentation: http://qdspsy.eulerlab.de/ Python source code: https://github.com/eulerlab/QDSpy (Euler, 2019b; copy archived at https://github.com/elifesciences-publications/QDSpy) Information on 'pattern mode' with QDSpy: http://qdspsy.eulerlab.de/lightcrafter.html#example-scripts
Chopper	For a 'mechanical' LED blanking solution (see Discussion), based on Thorlabs' Optical Chopper System
open-visual-stimulator – Project GitHub repository	Contains spectral calibration scripts, 3D design files for printed parts, printed circuit board design files, bill of materials to populate boards, etc. https://github.com/eulerlab/open-visual-stimulator (Euler et al., 2019a; copy archived at https://github.com/elifesciences-publications/open-visual-stimulator)

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.48779.003>

with this current LCr model is, however, that – in our experience – it passes only a fraction of the light entering the light guide port (see Discussion). The LCr is positioned next to the microscope's stage and projects the stimulus via a condenser from below into the recording chamber, where it is focussed on the photoreceptor layer of the isolated mouse retina (**Figure 2a left**). In the type of 2P microscope used here (MOM, Sutter Instruments, Novato, CA; Materials and methods), the scan head including the objective lens – as well as the substage assembly with the condenser – moves relative to the static recording chamber. Hence, to allow the stimulus to 'follow' the objective lens-condenser axis, the LCr is mounted on a pair of low-friction linear slides, with the LCr mechanically coupled to the substage assembly (**Figure 2b**). To allow for stimulus centring, a combination of an x-y and a z-stage, both manually adjustable with micrometer screws, is fitted between slides and LCr.

In addition to this 'through-the-condenser' (TTC) configuration for visual stimulation, we also used the 'through-the-objective' (TTO) configuration described earlier (**Figure 2—figure supplement 1**) (Euler et al., 2009). Here, the stimulus is optically coupled into the laser pathway and therefore does not require mechanical coupling of microscope head and visual stimulator. In addition, only scattered light of the visual stimulus will reach the photodetectors above the objective, reducing artefacts caused by stimulus light entering the photodetectors (e.g. photomultipliers, PMTs). However, the disadvantage of the TTO configuration is that the stimulation area is limited by the field-of-view of the objective (approximately 700 μm in diameter for our 20x objective) and, therefore, large-scale retinal networks that may be critical for naturalistic stimulation are likely not well activated.

For the four-channel (tetrachromatic) zebrafish stimulator variant, we optically coupled two light guide LCrs (**Figure 2d,e**; for parts list, see **Table 3**). They used a similar external illumination unit as the mouse stimulator, but with different LED/filter combinations ($\lambda_{\text{peak}} = 586, 480, 420, \text{ and } 370 \text{ nm}$). The beams of the two LCrs are collimated and combined using a long-pass dichroic mirror and projected onto a flat teflon screen that covers one side of a miniature water-filled aquarium (**Table 1**), in which the zebrafish larva is mounted on a microscope slide under the objective lens of a MOM-type 2P microscope (**Figure 2e**). Each LCr is placed on an independent three-axis manipulator to facilitate alignment of the two images. Then, small 0.5-cm circular stimuli are projected (one from each stimulator) and the LCrs positions are adjusted using the manipulators until the stimuli are completely overlapping. The general design of the zebrafish stimulator – with one or two LCr

Table 2. Parts list of the mouse visual stimulator (cf. **Figure 2a–c** and **Figure 2—figure supplement 6**).

Part	Description (link)	Company	Item number
Parts for stimulator (except external illumination unit)			
LCr	0.45' 'DLP Fiber couple E4500MKII Development Module FC/PC	EKB Technologies Ltd.	DPM-FE4500MKIIF
Condenser	C-C Achromat-Aplanat Condenser N.A. 1.40, oil	Nikon	MBL71400
Objective	W Plan-Apochromat 20x/1.0 DIC (UV) VIS-IR	Zeiss	421452-9880-000
DM 00	Beamsplitter 900DCXXR	AHF Analysetechnik AG	F73-903
Lens 00	Achromatic Doublet, f = 75 mm	Thorlabs	AC254-075-A-ML
Light guide	Liquid light guide 5 mm Core, 1.2 m length	Thorlabs	LLG05-4H
z stage	13 mm Travel Vertical Translation Stage	Thorlabs	MVS005/M
x-y stage	XY Stage, 13 mm Travel	Thorlabs	XYT1/M
Frictionless tables	Type NK frictionless table (rollers/balls)	Schneeberger GmbH	NK2-50 (x2)
Perfusion chamber	Quick release magnetic imaging chamber	Warner Instruments	64-1943
Parts for the external illumination unit			
Cage plate 1	Cage Plate with Ø2.2' Double Bore	Thorlabs	LCP09/M
Cage plate 2	30 mm to 60 mm Cage Plate Adapter	Thorlabs	LCP02/M
Cage plate 3	SM1-Threaded Standard Cage Plates	Thorlabs	CP02/M (x7)
Cage assembly rods	ER Assembly Rods for 30 mm and 60 mm Cage Systems	Thorlabs	ER1/2/3 (x4)
Post holders	Pedestal Post Holders	Thorlabs	PH40E (x2)
Post holders	Clamping Forks and Base Adapters	Thorlabs	CF175 (x2)
Collimator	5 mm LLG Collimating Adapter, Zeiss Axioskop	Thorlabs	LLG5A4-A
BP 00	387/11 BrightLine HC	AHF	F39-387
BP 01	576/10 BrightLine HC	AHF	F37-576
UV LED	385 nm, 320 mW at 350 mA, +- 75°	Roithner	H2A1-H385-r2
Green LED	590 nm, 8–10 mW at 350 mA, +- 30°	Roithner	M3L1-HY-30
DM 01	Beamsplitter HC BS 495	AHF	F38-495
Lens 01	1" N-BK7 Plano-Convex Lens, f = 25.4 mm	Thorlabs	LA1951-A-ML (x2)
DM holder	DM_holder , Nylon	Custom-made (University workshop)	
LED holder	LED_holder , Aluminium	Custom-made (University workshop)	(x2)

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.48779.011>

projecting onto a teflon screen – is also suitable for visual stimulation during in vivo experiments of other model organisms like mouse or *Drosophila*.

Separating light stimulation and fluorescence detection

A difficulty when combining visual stimulation with fluorescence imaging is that the spectral photoreceptor sensitivities and the emission spectra of the fluorescent probes tend to greatly overlap. Hence, to avoid imaging artefacts, stimulator light has to be prevented from reaching the PMTs of the microscope, while ensuring that each of the spectral photoreceptor types is stimulated efficiently and as much of the fluorescence signal as possible is captured. To address this issue, light stimulation and fluorescence detection have to be separated temporally and/or spectrally (*Euler et al., 2009*).

Table 3. Parts list of the zebrafish visual stimulator (cf. **Figure 2d,e**; italic entries are not shown in figure).

Part	Description (link)	Company	Item number
Parts for stimulator (except external illumination unit)			
LCr	0.45' 'DLP Fiber couple E4500MKII Development Module FC/PC	EKB Technologies Ltd.	DPM-FE4500MKIIF (x2)
DM 04	Beamsplitter T 400 LP	AHF	F79-100
Lens 02	Mounted N-BK7 Bi-Convex Lens, f = 50.0 mm	Thorlabs	LB1844-ML (x2)
Lens 03	Air-Spaced Achromatic Doublet, f = 50 mm	Thorlabs	ACA254-050-A (x3)
Lens 04	Achromatic Doublet, f = 100 mm	Thorlabs	AC508-100-A-ML
Light guide	Liquid light guide 5 mm Core, 1.2 m length	Thorlabs	LLG05-4H (x2)
z stage	13 mm Travel Vertical Translation Stage	Thorlabs	MVS005/M (x2)
x-y stage	13 mm Translation Stage	Thorlabs	MT1B/M (x4)
Mount plate	Aluminium Breadboard	Thorlabs	MB2530/M
Lens holder	30 mm to 60 mm Cage Plate Adapter	Thorlabs	LCP02/M (x4)
Optical Post	Optical Post 12.7 mm diam	Thorlabs	TR100/M (x2)
Post Holder	Post holder 12.7 mm diam 100 mm	Thorlabs	PH100/M (x2)
Post clamp	Clamping Fork, 1.24' Counterbored Slot	Thorlabs	CF125-P5 (x2)
Metal rods	Cage Assembly Rod, 12' Long, Ø6 mm	Thorlabs	ER-12 (x4)
Metal rods	Cage Assembly Rod, 3' Long, Ø6 mm	Thorlabs	ER-3 (x8)
Dichroic holder	Kinematic Cage Cube Platform for C4W/C6W, Metric	Thorlabs	B4C/M
Dichroic holder	Cage compatible rectangular filter mount	Thorlabs	FFM1
Cage cube	60 mm cube cage	Thorlabs	LC6W
Lens holder	SM1-Threaded 30 mm Cage Plate	Thorlabs	CP02/M (x2)
LCr Lens holder	LCr lens holder adapter	3D printed part	(x2)
Fish aquarium	Fish Cinema v10.0_40X_Objective	3D printed part(s)	
Teflon screen	PTFE (Teflon) glass fibre high temperature coating cloth, 0.15 mm	Artistore	
Parts for the external illumination units (RGB + UV)			
Collimator	5 mm LLG Collimating Adapter, Zeiss Axioskop	Thorlabs	LLG5A4-A (x2)
Lens 01	1" N-BK7 Plano-Convex Lens, f = 25.4 mm	Thorlabs	LA1951-A-ML (x4)
DM 02	Laser Beamsplitter H 560 LPXR superflat	AHF	F48-559
DM 03	Beamsplitter T 450 LPXR	AHF	F48-450
BP 02	370/36 BrightLine HC	AHF	F39-370
BP 03	420/40 ET Bandpass	AHF	F47-420
BP 04	480/40x ET Bandpass	AHF	F49-480
BP 05	586/20 BrightLine HC	AHF	F39-587
UV LED	365 nm 2.4–6.0 mW 20 mA 15°	Roithner	XSL-365-5E
Blue LED	420 nm 420 mW 350 mA 20°	Roithner	SMB1N-420H-02

Table 3 continued on next page

Table 3 continued

Part	Description (link)	Company	Item number
Green LED	470 nm 70 mW 350 mA 20'	Roithner	SMB1N-D470-02
Red LED	588 nm 13.5 cd 20 mA 8'	Roithner	B5B-434-TY
Filter/LED/lens holder	SM1-Threaded 30 mm Cage Plate	Thorlabs	CP02/M (x4)
Collimator holder	Double Bore for SM2 Lens Tube Mounting	Thorlabs	LCP09 (x2)
Vertical holder	60 mm to 30 mm Cage System Right-Angle Adapter	Thorlabs	LCP30 (x3)
Dichroic frame	Dichroic frame	3D printed part	(x2)
Frame holder	Frame holder	3D printed part	(x2)
Horizontal holder	Horizontal holder	3D printed part	(x2)
Metal rods	Cage Assembly Rod, 8' Long, Ø6 mm	Thorlabs	ER-8 (x4)
Metal rods	Cage Assembly Rod, 3' Long, Ø6 mm	Thorlabs	ER-3 (x10)
Optical Post	Optical Post 12.7 mm diam	Thorlabs	TR100/M (x4)
Post Holder	Post holder 12.7 mm diam 100 mm	Thorlabs	PH100/M (x4)
Post clamp	Clamping Fork, 1.24' Counterbored Slot	Thorlabs	CF125-P5 (x4)

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.48779.012>

Temporal separation means that the LEDs of the visual stimulator are turned off while collecting the fluorescence signal. In a 'standard' rectangular x-y image scan, the retrace period (when the scanners move to the beginning of the next scan line) can be used for turning the LEDs on to display the stimulus. We found a retrace period of 20% of a scan line (for 1 to 2 ms scan lines) a good compromise between maximising data collection time, avoiding mechanical artefacts from the retracing galvo scanners, and still having sufficient bright stimuli (Euler et al., 2019). If other scan patterns are used, LED-on periods (of similar duration as the retrace periods in x-y scans) need to be embedded for the temporal separation concept to work. An example for a more 'mechanical scanner friendly' scan pattern that includes such LED-on periods are the 'spiral' scans we describe elsewhere (Rogerson et al., 2019). In any case, the microscope's software has to signal these retrace (or LED-on) periods. Our custom-written microscope software (ScanM, see Materials and methods) generates a 'laser blanking signal' (=low during retrace), which allows turning down the excitation laser's intensity via a Pockels' cell during retrace to reduce the laser exposure of the tissue (Euler et al., 2019; Euler et al., 2009). Hence, a straightforward way to implement temporal separation between fluorescence detection and light stimulation is to invert this blanking signal and use it to turn on the LEDs during retrace (Figure 2—figure supplement 2).

Despite stimulation and data acquisition being temporally separated (see above), spectral separation is needed to protect the PMTs from the stimulus light. Even when the light reaching the PMTs is not bright enough to damage them, it often triggers the overcurrent protection circuit many PMTs are equipped with and shuts them off. Spectral separation is achieved by selecting LED and PMT filters with non-overlapping transmission bands (Figure 2—figure supplement 3). This is complemented by a dichroic mirror (DM_M Figure 2—figure supplements 1 and 3; DM_Z in Figure 2—figure supplement 3) with multiple transmission bands (Euler et al., 2019; Euler et al., 2009). In the TTO configuration, it transmits one narrow band of stimulation light for each spectral photoreceptor type while reflecting the excitation laser (>800 nm) and the fluorescence signals (detection bands; Figure 2—figure supplement 3). In addition, it passes stimulus light reflected back from the specimen. In the TTC configuration, the main role of DM_M is to reflect fluorescence from the specimen to the PMTs while preventing any stimulus light reflected back from the specimen going there by passing it. The same is true for DM_Z in the zebrafish stimulator with the teflon screen, where some of the

stimulus light is scattered in the specimen towards the objective lens. Note that both DMs are not only suitable for mouse and zebrafish but also for other model organisms like *Drosophila* (**Figure 2—figure supplement 4**). An option to further reduce stimulus artefacts that was not evaluated here are gated PMTs (*Euler et al., 2019*).

As explained above, the LCr encodes the brightness of an image pixel by its mirror's 'on' time, and colour sequentially by cycling through the LEDs while presenting the corresponding R-, G- or B-bitplanes in sync (cf. LCr User Guide; for link, see **Table 1**). In addition, the LCr allows setting the maximal intensity of each LED via pulse-width modulation (PWM). In the two-channel mouse stimulator, we power the LEDs in the external illumination unit (**Figure 2a** right) using the LCr's onboard LED drivers and therefore, these LEDs are driven as built-in ones would be – except that we interrupt power to the LEDs in sync with the inverted laser blanking signal using a simple custom circuit board (**Figure 2—figure supplement 5a–c**). To switch the necessary currents with sufficient speed, this circuit uses per LED channel three solid state relays connected in parallel. A downside of this simple solution is that the choice of LEDs is constrained by how much current the relays can pass (250 mA continuous current load per relay). The LCr is not limiting here, because its internal LED drivers can provide up to 4.3 A at 5 V in total. For the four-channel zebrafish stimulator, we devised a circuit (logic board, **Figure 2—figure supplement 5d–f**) that uses only the LCr's digital control signals for each LED (LED enable, LED PWM; for details, see **Figure 2—figure supplement 5g**). This board is also compatible with the two-channel mouse stimulator. It represents a more general solution, because it does not rely on power from the LCr. Instead, in combination with custom LED driver boards (**Figure 2—figure supplement 5f**), it can use arbitrary current supplies for the LEDs, making it possible to use any commercially available LED. The logic board supports up to three LED channels, such that for the zebrafish stimulator, two boards are needed (one per LCr) – plus one driver board per LED. For all solutions, printed circuit boards (PCB) designs created using KiCad (see Key Resources Table) and building instructions are provided (see link to repository in **Table 1**).

One potential issue of the described solution for temporal separation is that the frame (refresh) rate of the LCr (typically 60 Hz) and the laser blanking/LED-on signal (500 to 1,000 Hz) are not synchronised and therefore may cause slow aliasing-related fluctuations in stimulus brightness. In practice, however, we detected only small brightness modulations (**Figure 2—figure supplement 2b**).

Visual stimulation software

Our visual stimulation software (QDSpy) is completely written in Python3 and relies on OpenGL for stimulus rendering. It includes a GUI, which facilitates spatial stimulus alignment, LCr control and stimulus presentation. QDSpy stimuli are written as normal Python scripts that use the 'QDSpy library' to define stimulus objects, set colours, send trigger signals, display scenes etc. Stimulus objects range from simple shapes with basic shader support to videos (for a complete description of the software, see link in **Table 1**). Depending on the way a user implements a stimulus and whether or not the script contains lengthy calculations, it cannot be guaranteed that the script runs fast enough to reliably generate stimulus frames at 60 Hz. Hence, to ensure stimulus timing, the first time QDSpy runs a stimulus script it generates a 'compiled' version of the stimulus, which is stored in a separate file. When the user runs that stimulus again (and the source stimulus script has not been altered after compilation), QDSpy presents the stimulus from the compiled file. This compiled file contains the drawing instructions and timing for every stimulus element used in a very compact form. This strategy has the advantage that stimulus timing is very reliable, as potentially time-consuming sections of the Python stimulus script have already been executed during 'compilation'. The main disadvantage is that user interaction during stimulus presentation is (currently) not possible.

For stimulus presentation, QDSpy relies on the frame sync of the graphics card/driver for stimulus display. By measuring the time required to generate the next frame, the software can detect dropped frames and warn the user of timing inconsistencies, which cannot be altogether excluded on a non-real-time operating system like Windows. Such frame drops, including all other relevant events (e.g. which stimulus was started when, was it aborted etc.) as well as user comments are automatically logged into a file. To account for any gamma correction performed by the LCr firmware when in video mode and/or by non-linearities of the LEDs/LED drivers, we measured each LED's intensity curve separately to generate a lookup table (LUT) that is then used in QDSpy to linearise the colour channels (Materials and methods).

As default, the LCr runs in 'video mode', where it behaves like an HDMI-compatible display (60 Hz, 912 × 1,140 pixels). In this mode, each colour channel in an RGB frame (3 × 8 = 24 bitplanes) is assigned to one of the 3 LCr LEDs via the QDSpy software. It is possible (and supported by QDSpy) to reconfigure the LCr firmware and run it in the so-called 'pattern mode', which, for instance, allows trading bit depth for higher frame rates and assigning each of the 24 bitplanes of every frame to an arbitrary combination of LEDs (Discussion).

The stimulation software generates digital synchronisation markers to align presented stimuli with recorded data. In addition to digital I/O cards (e.g. PCI-DIO24, Measurement Computing, Bietigh-eim-Bissingen, Germany), QDSpy supports Arduino boards (<https://www.arduino.cc/>) as digital output device. While the software attempts generating the synchronisation marker at the same time as when presenting the stimulus frame that contains the marker, a temporal offset between these two events in the tens of millisecond range cannot be avoided. We found this offset to be constant for a given stimulation system, but dependent on the specific combination of PC hardware, digital I/O device, and graphic cards. Therefore, the offset must be measured (e.g. by comparing synchronisation marker signal and LCr output measured by a fast photodiode) and considered in the data analysis.

For up to three chromatic channels (e.g. the mouse stimulator, cf. **Figure 2a–c**), stimuli are presented in full-screen mode on the LCr, with the other screen displaying the GUI. When more chromatic channels are needed, as for the zebrafish stimulator, two LCRs are combined (see above; cf. **Figure 2d,e**). QDSpy then opens a large window that covers both LCR 'screens' and provides each LCr with 'its' chromatic version of the stimulus (screen overlay mode). To this end, the software accepts colour definitions with up to six chromatic values and assigns them to the six available LEDs (three per LCr). For example, the first LCr of the zebrafish stimulator provides the red, green and blue channels, whereas the second LCr adds the UV channel (**Figure 2d**). Here, QDSpy presents the stimulus' RGB-components on the half of the overlay window assigned to the first LCr and the stimulus' UV-component on the half of the overlay window assigned to the second LCr. The remaining LED channels are available for a different purpose, such as, for example, separate optogenetic stimulation.

LED selection and spectral calibration

Adequate chromatic stimulation requires adjusting the stimulator to the spectral sensitivities of the model organism. Ideally, one would choose LEDs that allow maximally separating the different opsins (**Figure 3**). In practice, however, these choices are limited by the substantial overlap of opsin sensitivity spectra (**Figure 3a,c**) and by technical constraints: For instance, commercially available projectors, including the LCr, barely transmit UV light (<385 nm), likely due to UV non-transmissive parts in the optical pathway and/or the reflectance properties of the DMD (Discussion). In addition, when imaging light-evoked neural activity, fluorescence signal detection and visual stimulation often compete for similar spectral bands, and need to be separated to avoid stimulus-related artefacts (**Figure 2—figure supplement 3**; discussed in **Euler et al., 2019**; **Euler et al., 2009**). Compared to projectors with built-in LEDs, the flexible LED complement of the light guide LCr presents a crucial advantage: Here, LEDs can be easily exchanged to avoid the spectral bands of the fluorescent probes, thereby allowing to maximally separate visual stimulation and fluorescence detection.

Table 4. Different commercially available UV-enabled projectors.

Part	Description (link)	Company
DPM-E4500UVBGMKII	DLP LightCrafter E4500 MKII with 3 LEDs: UV (385 or 405 nm), blue (460 nm), and green (520 nm)	EKB Technologies Ltd., Bat Yam, Israel https://www.ekbtechnologies.com/
3DLP9000 UV Light Engine	DLP-based light engine that can be equipped with one arbitrary LED, including UV (365, 385, or 405 nm)	DLi Digital Light innovations, Austin, TX https://www.dlinnovations.com
DLP660TE – 4K UHD	4K-enabled projector, with flexible light sources, using Texas Instruments' DLP660TE chipset	VISITECH Engineering GmbH Wetzlar, Germany https://visitech.no/

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.48779.018>

Figure 2. Visual stimulator design. (a) Schematic drawing of the dichromatic stimulator for in vitro recordings of mouse retinal explants. The stimulator is coupled into the two-photon (2P) microscope from below the recording chamber with the retinal tissue (through-the-condenser; for alternative light paths (through-the-objective), see **Figure 2—figure supplement 1**). DM, dichroic mirror; BP, band-pass filter; LCr, lightcrafter; LED, light-emitting diode. *Figure 2 continued on next page*

Figure 2 continued

diode. For components, including custom-made parts, see **Table 2**. (b) LCr unit and substage portion of the 2P microscope in side-view. (c) External LED illumination unit in top-view. For details on mechanical parts, see **Figure 2—figure supplement 6**. (d) Schematic drawing of the tetrachromatic stimulator for in vivo recordings in zebrafish larvae. The optical pathways of two LCRs are combined and the stimulus is projected onto a UV-transmissive teflon screen at one side of the miniature aquarium. For components, see **Table 3**. (e) Side-view of tetrachromatic stimulation setup. (f) RGB external LED illumination unit of tetrachromatic stimulation setup. Band-pass (BP) filters 03, 04 and 05 as well as lenses 01 are not indicated due to space constraints.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.48779.004>

The following figure supplements are available for figure 2:

Figure supplement 1. Optical pathway for a through-the-objective (TTO) mouse stimulator.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.48779.005>

Figure supplement 2. Intensity measurements of the LEDs of the mouse stimulator.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.48779.006>

Figure supplement 3. Spectral separation of visual stimulation and fluorescence detection.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.48779.007>

Figure supplement 4. Suggestion for LED/filter design for a *Drosophila* visual stimulator.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.48779.008>

Figure supplement 5. External LED control and temporal separation of stimulation and fluorescence detection.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.48779.009>

Figure supplement 6. Detailed description of external LED unit of the mouse stimulator.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.48779.010>

Because LED spectra can be quite broad, we combine each LED with an appropriate band-pass filter to facilitate arranging stimulation and detection bands.

As a consequence, the peak emissions of the selected LED/filter combinations usually do not match the opsins' sensitivity peaks. For our dichromatic mouse stimulator, we chose LED/filter combinations peaking for UV and green at approximately 385 and 576 nm, respectively (**Figure 3a**), which after calibration (**Figure 3d–f**; Materials and methods), are expected to differentially activate mouse M- and S-opsin (**Figure 3f**). Notably, because of its spectral shift towards shorter wavelengths (**Jacobs et al., 1991**), conventional TFT monitors routinely used in in vivo studies fail to activate mouse S-opsin (**Figure 3b**) and therefore are not able to provide adequate visual stimuli for the mouse visual system (Discussion). For the tetrachromatic zebrafish stimulator, we used LED/filter combinations with peak emissions at approx. 586, 480, 420, and 370 nm (**Figure 3c**). For a suggestion of LED/filter combinations matching the spectral sensitivity of *Drosophila*, see **Figure 2—figure supplement 4**.

To estimate the theoretically achievable chromatic separation of mouse cones with our stimulators, we measured the spectra of each LED/filter combination at different intensities (**Figure 3d**) and converted these data into cone photoisomerisation rates (**Nikonov et al., 2006**). To account for non-linearities in stimulator intensities, we apply gamma correction at the stimulus presentation software level (**Figure 3e**). For our functional recordings (cf. Figures 5 and 6), the photoisomerisation rate (in $P^*/\text{cone}/s \cdot 10^3$) normally ranges from ~ 0.6 (stimulator shows black image) to ~ 20 (stimulator shows white image; **Figure 3f**), corresponding to the low photopic regime. In contrast to most commercially available projectors, the current driving the LEDs can also be set to zero, allowing experiments in complete darkness. Further details on the calibration procedures and example calculations for mice and zebrafish are provided in the Methods and in supplemental iPython notebooks, respectively (**Table 1**). Importantly, the general layout of these calibration notebooks facilitates adapting them to other model organisms.

Spatial resolution

To measure the spatial resolution of our mouse stimulator, we used the 'through-the-objective' (TTO) configuration (**Figure 2—figure supplement 1**) (**Euler et al., 2009**) and projected UV and green checkerboards of varying checker sizes (from 2 to 100 μm ; Materials and methods) onto a camera chip positioned at the level of the recording chamber (**Figure 4a**). We found that contrast remained relatively constant for checker sizes down to 4 μm before it rapidly declined (**Figure 4b,c**).

Figure 3. Calibration of the mouse stimulator. (a) Sensitivity profiles of mouse S- and M-opsin (dotted black lines) and spectra of UV (magenta) and green LED/filter combinations used in the mouse stimulator. (b) Sensitivity profiles of mouse S- and M-opsin (dotted black line) and spectra of blue, green and red LED present in a standard TFT monitor. (c) Sensitivity profiles of zebrafish opsins (dotted black lines) and spectra of UV, blue, green and red LEDs used in the zebrafish stimulator. (d) Spectra (in nW) of UV and green LED obtained from measurements using increasing brightness levels; shown are spectra for 0, 9, 19, 29, 39, 49, 59, 68, 78, 88, and 98% brightness. (e) Non-linearised intensity curve ('raw') with sigmoidal fit (black), estimated gamma correction curve (black dotted line; 'Look-up table') and linearized intensity curve ('corrected') for green LED. (f) Photoisomerisation rates for maximal brightness of UV (19.2 and 3.8 photoisomerisations $\cdot 10^3$ P*/second/cone for S- and M-opsin, respectively) and green LED (0 and 19.5 $\cdot 10^3$ P*/second/cone for S- and M-opsin, respectively). Note that the UV LED also activates M-opsin due to its increased sensitivity in the short wavelength range (β -band, Discussion).

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.48779.013>

Similarly, transitions between bright and dark checkers started to blur for checker sizes below $10 \mu\text{m}$ (Figure 4d,e). For these measurements, we used a 5x objective (MPlan 5X/0.1, Olympus) to project the stimuli, ensuring that the spatial resolution of the camera (OVD5647 chip: $1.4 \mu\text{m}$ pixel pitch) was not the limiting factor. Hence, a $5 \times 5 \mu\text{m}$ checker stimulus appeared as a $20 \times 20 \mu\text{m}$ square on the camera chip, where it covered approximately $(14.3)^2$ pixels. However, for the scaling factor we use for our recordings ($1.9 \times 0.9 \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$), a $5 \times 5 \mu\text{m}$ checker consists only of 9.5×4.5 LCr pixels (DMD4500, chip area: $6,161 \times 9,855 \mu\text{m}$ with $1,140 \times 912$ pixels). Thus, the drop in spatial resolution observed for checkers $\leq 5 \mu\text{m}$ is likely related to the resolution of the DMD. For the 'through-the-condenser' (TTC) configuration, contrast and sharpness of transitions declined already for checker sizes between 5 and $10 \mu\text{m}$ (Figure 4c,e). That we measured a slightly lower spatial resolution for the TTC compared to the TTO configuration may be because we reached the camera resolution limit (see above), as for TTC we could not simply swap the condenser and, hence, the stimulus image was not magnified on the camera chip.

For the zebrafish stimulator, spatial resolution is less of a problem because, for our setup, checker sizes at the limit of the animal's spatial resolution (2° visual angle; Haug et al., 2010) are large (~ 1 mm on the teflon screen; cf. Figure 2d,e).

For the spatial resolution measurements, the UV and green images were each focussed on the camera chip and, therefore, the results do not reflect any effects of chromatic aberration on image quality. To estimate chromatic aberration for our TTO configuration, we next measured the offset between the focal planes of the chromatic channels. Here, we used the standard 20x objective that we also employ for functional recordings. We found that the difference in focal plane between UV and green of approx. $24 \mu\text{m}$ has little effect on the overall image quality (Figure 4—figure

Figure 4. Spatial calibration of the mouse stimulator. (a) Images of checkerboard stimuli with varying checker sizes projected through-the-objective (TTO) for illumination with green (top) and UV (bottom) LED, recorded by placing the sensor chip of a Raspberry Pi camera at the level of the recording chamber. Focus was adjusted for UV and green LED separately. Insets for 5 and 2 μm show zoomed in regions of the image. (b) Intensity profiles for five different checker sizes of green LED. (c) Contrasts ($I_{Max} - I_{Min}$) for checkerboards of varying checker sizes of the TTO (top) and through-the-condenser (TTC; bottom) configuration. (d) Peak-normalised intensity profiles of different checker sizes, scaled to the same half-maximum width. (e) $1/rate$ estimated from sigmoidal fits of normalised intensity curves like in (d) for varying checker sizes of the TTO (top) and TTC (bottom) configuration.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.48779.014>

The following figure supplement is available for figure 4:

Figure supplement 1. Chromatic aberration of the mouse stimulator.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.48779.015>

supplement 1) - at least for checker sizes we routinely use for receptive field mapping of retinal neurons (e.g. *Baden et al., 2016*; cf. also Discussion).

Visual stimulation in the explanted mouse retina

To confirm that our stimulator design can be used for adequate chromatic stimulation of the mouse retina, we directly recorded from cone axon terminals in retinal slices using 2P Ca^{2+} imaging (e.g.

Kemmler et al., 2014). To this end, we used the transgenic mouse line HR2.1:TN-XL, where the ratiometric Ca^{2+} sensor TN-XL is exclusively expressed in cones (*Figure 5a*) (*Wei et al., 2012*). To quantify the chromatic preference of recorded cones, we calculated spectral contrast (SC) based on the response strength to a 1 Hz sine-wave full-field stimulus of green and UV (Materials and methods). The SC values correspond to Michelson contrast, ranging from -1 to 1 for the cell responding solely to UV and green, respectively.

In line with the opsin distribution described in mice (*Applebury et al., 2000; Baden et al., 2013*), cones located in the ventral retina responded more strongly or even exclusively to UV (*Figure 5b*, bottom row), whereas central cones showed a strong response to both green and UV due to the more balanced co-expression of S- and M-opsin (*Figure 5b*, centre row). In contrast, dorsal cones

Figure 5. Cone-isolating stimulation of mouse cones. (a) Dorsal recording field in the outer plexiform layer (OPL; right) shows labelling of cone axon terminals with Ca^{2+} biosensor TN-XL in the HR2.1:TN-XL mouse line (*Wei et al., 2012*). Schematic on the left illustrates retinal location of recorded slice. (b) Ca^{2+} traces (mean traces in black, $n = 3$ trials in grey) of cone axon terminals located in dorsal (top; cone axon terminal from (a)), medial (middle) and ventral (bottom) retina in response to 1 Hz sine modulation of green and UV LED, with spectral contrast (SC) indicated below. Colour substitution protocol (right) estimated from calibration data (Materials and methods). (c) Distribution and comparison of SC for sine modulation stimulus with (top) and without (bottom) silent substitution protocol ($n = 55$ cells, $n = 12$ scan fields, $n = 1$ mouse; $p = 9.31 \times 10^{-9}$ for dorsal cells, $n = 30$; $p = 0.92$ for ventral cells, $n = 25$; Wilcoxon signed-rank test). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.48779.016>

exhibited a green-dominated response (**Figure 5b**, top row). Due to the cross-activation of M-opsin by the UV LED (see above), most dorsal cones showed an additional small response to UV.

We also tested a stimulus that used silent substitution (**Figure 5b**, right column; Materials and methods) (*Estévez and Spekreijse, 1982*). With this stimulus, we systematically found reduced UV responses in dorsal cones, resulting in a significant shift in SC towards more positive values (**Figure 5c**, right column; for statistics, see legend). In contrast, ventral cone responses were not altered by silent substitution.

These data demonstrate that our stimulator design enables obtaining cone-isolating responses in the mouse retina. Notably, the chromatic separation observed in the recordings nicely matches our predictions of cross-activation (see above and Materials and methods).

Tetrachromatic stimulation in in vivo zebrafish larvae

We recorded in vivo from bipolar cell (BC) axon terminals in zebrafish larvae using 2P Ca^{2+} imaging (**Figure 6a**). The transgenic line we used expressed SyGCaMP6f exclusively in BC axon terminals (*Rosa et al., 2016*). In these experiments, we presented full-field (90×120 degrees visual angle) steps or sine wave modulation of red, green, blue and UV light to the teflon screen in front of the immobilised animal (cf. **Figure 2d,e**). This revealed spectrally differential tuning of distinct BC terminals (**Figure 6b,c**), in line with a previous report (*Zimmermann et al., 2018*). For example, terminal one responded with a Ca^{2+} increase to a decrease in red light as well as to an increase in blue or UV light, yielding a 'red^{Off}/blue^{On},UV^{On}' response behaviour. In contrast, terminal four did not respond to red or green, but differentially responded to blue and UV ('blue^{Off}/UV^{On}'). Further differences were visible in the temporal profile of the BC responses. For example, terminal three responded more transiently to red and blue, but in a sustained fashion to UV. Similar to cone responses in the in vitro mouse retina, spectrally differential tuning of zebrafish BC terminals was also observed for a sine wave stimulus (**Figure 6c**). Taken together, tetrachromatic stimulation elicited clear differential responses across different wavelengths, thus highlighting that the stimulator's spectral isolation between the four LED channels was sufficient to drive the zebrafish's cone system differentially. To further improve spectral separation, a silent substitution protocol might be used (cf. **Figure 5**; see notebook on GitHub for details). However, as the sensitivity profiles of zebrafish cones substantially overlap (cf. **Figure 1d**), implementing a silent substitution protocol is more challenging than for the mouse.

Discussion

In this paper, we present a flexible, relatively low-cost stimulator solution for visual neuroscience and demonstrate its use for dichromatic stimulation in the in vitro mouse retina and tetrachromatic stimulation in the in vivo larval zebrafish. The core of the stimulator is an LCr with a light guide port that connects to an external LED array. We also provide detailed calibration protocols (as iPython notebooks) to estimate (cross-)activation in a species' complement of photoreceptor types, which facilitates planning of the LED/filter combinations required for selective chromatic stimulation. To drive the LEDs, we designed simple electronic circuits that make use of the LCr LED control signals and allow integrating an LED-on signal ('blinking signal') for synchronisation with data acquisition, which is critical, for example, for fluorescence imaging in the in vitro retina (*Euler et al., 2009*). By combining two LCRs, up to 6 LED channels are supported by our visual stimulation software (QDSpy). In addition, we describe three exemplary projection methods that allow tuning the system towards high spatial resolution ('through-the-objective') or a large field-of-stimulation ('through-the-condenser') for in vitro experiments, or presentation on a teflon screen for in vivo studies. All materials (electronics, optical design, software, parts lists etc.) are publically available and open source.

The need for 'correct' spectral stimulation

The spectral sensitivity markedly varies across common model organisms used in visual neuroscience (cf. Introduction). As a result, in most cases visual stimulation devices optimised for the human visual system do not allow 'correct' spectral stimulation, in the sense that the different photoreceptor types are not differentially activated by the stimulator LEDs. Instead, 'correct' spectral stimulation requires that the visual stimulator is well-adjusted to the specific spectral sensitivities of the model organism.

Figure 6. Chromatic responses in bipolar cells of in vivo zebrafish larvae. (a) Drawing illustrating the expression of the genetically encoded Ca^{2+} biosensor SyGCaMP6f in bipolar cell terminals (left) of *tg(1.8ctbp2:SyGCaMP6f)* zebrafish larvae and scan field of inner plexiform layer (IPL; right), with exemplary regions-of-interest (ROIs) marked by white circles. (b) Mean Ca^{2+} traces (black; $n = 6$ trials in grey) in response to red, green, blue and UV full-field flashes (90×120 degrees visual angle, presented to the fish's right side). (c) Mean Ca^{2+} traces (black; $n = 4$ trials in grey) in response to full-field sine modulation (at 1 Hz) of red, green, blue and UV LED.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.48779.017>

For example, while human S-opsin is blue-sensitive (reviewed in [Jacobs, 2008](#)), the S-opsin of mice shows its highest sensitivity in the UV range ([Figure 1a](#)) ([Jacobs et al., 1991](#)). As standard TFT monitors optimised for humans and routinely used in mouse in vivo studies do not emit in the UV range, they fail to activate mouse S-opsin (*cf.* [Figure 3b](#)). If then, due to space constraints, the stimulation monitors are positioned in the UV-sensitive upper visual field of the mouse (*cf.* [Figure 1b](#)), such a stimulator will mainly activate the rod pathway. As a result, the presentation of 'truly' mouse-relevant natural stimuli is hampered, if not impossible. In recent years, however, several studies used customised projectors that allow UV stimulation for investigating chromatic processing in, for example, dLGN ([Denman et al., 2017](#)) or V1 ([Tan et al., 2015](#)). Here, similar to the arrangement in our zebrafish stimulator (*cf.* [Figure 2d](#)), the image is either back-projected onto a UV-transmissive teflon

screen (Tan et al., 2015) or projected onto a visual dome coated with UV-reflective paint (Denman et al., 2017). Both solutions are compatible with the mouse stimulator described above.

Even when the stimulator is adjusted to the spectral sensitivity of the model organism, each stimulator LED typically activates more than one photoreceptor type due to overlapping sensitivity profiles of the different opsins (cf. Figure 1). In particular, the long sensitivity tail of opsins for shorter wavelengths (' β -band') contributes to cross-activation of photoreceptors by the stimulator LEDs. For example, the sensitivity of mouse M-opsin to our UV LED results in a cross-activation of ~19.5% (cf. Figure 3f). Such 'imperfect' spectral separation of cone types is sufficient to investigate many questions concerning chromatic processing in the visual system – especially as there rarely is photoreceptor type-isolating stimulation in natural scenes (Chiao et al., 2000). If needed, photoreceptor cross-activation can be ameliorated by using a silent substitution protocol (Estévez and Spekreijse, 1982; but see Kamar et al., 2019). Here, one type of photoreceptor is selectively stimulated by presenting a steady excitation to all other photoreceptor types using a counteracting stimulus (cf. Figure 5b). This allows, for instance, to investigate the role of individual photoreceptor types in visual processing.

Stimulation with UV light

Sensitivity to UV light is widespread across animal species (reviewed in Cronin and Bok, 2016). Sometimes UV sensitivity may represent a specialised sensory channel; for example many insects and potentially some fish use UV-sensitive photoreceptors to detect polarisation patterns in the sky for orientation (Parkyn and Hawryshyn, 1993; Seliger et al., 1994; Wehner, 2001). In most cases, however, UV sensitivity seems to be simply incorporated into colour vision, extending the spectral range accessible to the species. Here, UV sensitivity can play an important role in invertebrate and vertebrate behaviour, including navigation and orientation, predator and prey detection, as well as communication (reviewed in Cronin and Bok, 2016).

For instance, mice possess a UV-sensitive S-opsin, which is co-expressed by M-cones predominantly in the ventral retina (; Baden et al., 2013). As the ventral retina observes the sky, it was proposed that the ventral UV sensitivity promotes detection of predatory birds, which appear as dark silhouettes against the sky. As UV light dominates the (clear) sky due to increased Rayleigh scattering of short wavelengths, contrasts tend to be higher in the UV channel (discussed in Applebury et al., 2000; Baden et al., 2013; Cronin and Bok, 2016). In support of this, recordings from mouse cones suggest that ventral S/M-cones prefer dark contrasts, whereas dorsal M-cones encode bright and dark contrasts symmetrically (Applebury et al., 2000; Baden et al., 2013).

Zebrafish larvae express the UV-sensitive sws2 opsin in their UV-cones. UV-vision in zebrafish is likely used for several tasks, including prey detection, predator and obstacle avoidance as well as colour vision (Yoshimatsu et al., 2019; Zimmermann et al., 2018). Like in mice, the distribution of UV-cones is non-uniform across the retinal surface. UV-cone density is highest in the temporo-ventral retina which surveys the upper-frontal part of visual space. This UV-specific *area centralis* is likely a specialisation for prey capture: Larval zebrafish feed on small, water-borne microorganisms such as paramecia, which are largely translucent at long wavelengths of light but readily scatter UV (Johnsen and Widder, 2001; Novalés Flamarique, 2013). Next, unlike for most terrestrial animals, predators may appear in any part of visual space in the aquatic environment, and zebrafish invest in UV-dark detection of predator-silhouettes throughout visual space (Losey et al., 1999; Yoshimatsu et al., 2019; Zimmermann et al., 2018). Finally, UV-sensitivity is integrated into retinal circuits for colour vision to impact tetrachromatic vision, as originally demonstrated for goldfish (Neumeyer, 1992).

Taken together, to approach natural conditions when probing a UV-sensitive species' visual system, UV stimulation must be included. Nonetheless, there are some pitfalls specifically linked to UV light stimulation. One major issue is that, in our experience, the standard LCr barely transmits wavelengths <385 nm. As the reflectance of the micromirrors (aluminium) drops only <300 nm and the glass window covering the DMD transmits $\geq 90\%$ of the light down to 350 nm (see links in Table 1), one limiting factor appears to arise from the LCr optics. Therefore, if shorter wavelengths are required, replacing the internal optics of the projector is necessary (e.g. Tan et al., 2015). If the different stimulation wavelengths are spread across a large range (e.g. $\Delta\lambda = 191$ and 200 nm for zebrafish and mouse stimulator, respectively; cf. Figure 3a,c), chromatic aberration may become an issue, causing an offset between the focal planes of the different colour channels (cf. Figure 4—figure

supplement 1). For our TTO stimulator configuration, we found a focus difference between UV and green in the order of a few tens of micrometers. For a checker size that is commonly used for receptive field mapping of retinal neurons (e.g. 40 μm ; [Baden et al., 2016](#)), we observed only a slight image blurring due to chromatic aberration, that likely has a negligible effect on our experiments. If chromatic aberration becomes an issue, viable approaches may be to increase the depth-of-field (e.g. by decreasing the aperture size with a diaphragm in the stimulation pathway) and/or use appropriate achromatic lenses.

Potential issues and technical improvements

In this section, we discuss potential issues that may arise when adapting our stimulator design to other experimental situations, as well as possible technical improvements.

If too much stimulation light enters the PMTs, in addition to spectral separation also temporal separation of visual stimulation and data acquisition is needed. To address this problem, we presented here an electronic solution that allows the LEDs to be on only during the short retrace period of a scan line. However, if higher LED power and/or shorter LED-on intervals are needed, the design of the 'blanking' circuits becomes more challenging, because handling fast switching of high currents and voltages with short rise and decay times is difficult (e.g. see our 'driver' boards on GitHub). Here, an alternative is to use a mechanical chopper (see [Table 1](#) and [Alfonso-Garcia et al., 2019](#); [Yang et al., 2019](#)). Briefly, a custom 3D printed chopping blade is attached to the chopper and the system is mounted at an appropriate position in the light path such that the blade is able to block the stimulus during the system's scanning period. The blanking signal from the microscope software (see Results) is used to synchronise chopper rotation speed. The main advantage of this solution is that it works with any stimulator and without meddling with its electronics. Disadvantages include, however, (i) mechanical vibrations and spinning noise, (ii) that different scanning modes require different chopping blades, and (iii) the additional costs for the chopper.

For increased flexibility with respect to the LED complement of the visual stimulator, we here use an external LED unit coupled into the LCr via a light guide port (cf. [Figure 2](#)). One disadvantage with this LCr model is, however, that it passes only a relatively small fraction of the light entering the light guide port. While this is not problematic for small projection areas used in our mouse and zebrafish recordings or for relatively low light intensities, it may become an issue when projecting the stimulus onto a larger area like the inside of a dome (e.g. [Denman et al., 2017](#); [Schmidt-Hieber and Häusser, 2013](#)). Here, LCr models with built-in, high-power LEDs might be a better option ([Table 4](#); [Supplementary file 1](#)).

If high spatial resolution is not required, an interesting alternative to a projector-based stimulator is one built from arrays of LEDs (e.g. [Reiser and Dickinson, 2008](#); [Wang et al., 2019](#)). The main advantage of LED arrays is that they offer a more precise timing control compared to the combination of HDMI display and PC graphics card driven by software running on a desktop PC. Hence, LED arrays may allow refresh rates in the range of several hundreds of Hz ([Reiser and Dickinson, 2008](#)). However, apart from their lower spatial resolution, current LED arrays only support a low number of colour channels, making them less well suitable for chromatic processing studies. In addition, LED arrays typically require customised control electronics, whereas stimulators based on standard HDMI displays can be driven by the experimenter's software of choice.

For the experiments shown here, we run the LCr for simplicity in 'video mode', where it acts as a normal 60 Hz HDMI display. It is also possible to configure the LCr's firmware in 'pattern mode' without requiring changes to the stimulator hardware. In pattern mode, the user can precisely define how the incoming stream of RGB bitplanes is interpreted and displayed. For example, it is possible to assign multiple LEDs to individual bitplanes and combinations thereof. Moreover, if a lower bit depth is acceptable, much higher frame rates can be achieved. While QDSpy supports the pattern mode, stimulus design can be more challenging, because the LCr receives its video input as 24 bit RGB data frames at a rate of 60 Hz, no matter how pattern mode interprets these data. For example, when configuring the LCr for 120 Hz (at half the bit depth), two consecutive 'display frames' need to be encoded in one 24-bit data frame by the stimulation software. Hence, the user should have a thorough knowledge of the LCr's design, and studying the documentation of the LCr's programming interface provided by Texas Instruments is recommended (for further details, see links in [Table 1](#)).

Towards a common stimulator design for vision research

Visual neuroscientists fundamentally rely on accurate stimulation, which not only includes choosing the appropriate spatial and temporal resolution, but also free control over the spectral properties. However, unlike for other equipment, such as amplifiers for electrophysiology, there is no selection of ‘standardised’ stimulation devices. Due to the lack of standardised yet flexible visual stimulators, many vision researchers employ specialised, often incompletely described solutions that address the needs of a particular experiment. This, in turn, may yield substantial problems in reproducibility and interpretation when comparing physiological data between laboratories. Here, we provide a detailed description of a highly flexible visual stimulator solution that uses commercial hardware only where necessary and otherwise relies on open hard- and software components. As our design can be easily adapted to different species’ and the experimentalist’s needs, it is suitable for a wide range of applications, ranging from psychophysics to single-cell physiology. By combining two LCrs and running them in pattern mode, structured stimulation with up to six chromatic channels at high frame rates is possible, which is critical for species with more than three spectral photoreceptor types and higher flicker fusion rates, such as many insects.

With this paper, we intend to start a community effort of sharing and further developing a common stimulator design for vision science. As the programming interface of the used DLP engine is publicly available, our system can also serve as a useful starting point for further community developments. To foster interactions, we set up a public GitHub repository inviting other vision researchers to use, share, and improve our design. With this effort, we hope to increase comparability and reproducibility of data in the field of visual neuroscience across labs.

Materials and methods

Key resources table

Reagent type (species) or resource	Designation	Source or reference	Identifiers	Additional information
Genetic reagent (<i>Mus musculus</i>)	HR2.1:TN-XL	<i>Wei et al., 2012</i>		Dr. Bernd Wissinger (Tübingen University)
Genetic reagent (<i>Danio rerio</i>)	tg(1.8ctbp2:SyGCaMP6f)	<i>Rosa et al., 2016</i>		Dr. Leon Lagnado (Sussex University)
Software, algorithm	KiCad EDA	http://kicad-pcb.org/		Electronics design software
Software, algorithm	OpenSCAD	http://www.openscad.org		3D CAD software

Note that the general stimulator design, operation and performance testing is described in the Results section. The respective parts for the mouse and the zebrafish stimulator versions are listed in **Tables 2** and **3**, respectively. Hence, this section focuses on details about the calibration procedures, 2P imaging, animal procedures, and data analysis.

Intensity calibration and gamma correction

The purpose of the intensity calibration is to ensure that each LED evokes a similarly maximal photoisomerisation rate in its respective spectral cone type, whereas the gamma correction aims at linearising each LED’s intensity curve. All calibration procedures are described in detail in the iPython notebooks included in the open-visual-stimulator GitHub repository (for link, see **Table 1**).

In case of the **mouse stimulator**, we used a photo-spectrometer (USB2000, 350–1000 nm, Ocean Optics, Ostfildern, Germany) that can be controlled and read-out from the iPython notebooks. It was coupled by an optic fibre and a cosine corrector (FOV 180°, 3.9 mm aperture) to the bottom of the recording chamber of the 2P microscope and positioned approximately in the stimulator’s focal plane. For intensity calibration, we displayed a bright spot (1,000 μm in diameter, max. intensity) of green and UV light to obtain spectra of the respective LEDs. We used a long integration time (1 s) and fitted the average of several reads (n = 10 for green; n = 50 reads for UV) with a Gaussian to remove shot noise. This yielded reliable measurements also at low LED intensities, which was particularly critical for UV LEDs.

The spectrometer output (S_{meas}) was divided by the integration time (Δt , in s) to obtain counts/s and then converted into electrical power (P_{el} , in nW) using the calibration data (S_{Cal} , in $\mu\text{J}/\text{count}$) provided by Ocean Optics,

$$P_{el}(\lambda) = S_{Meas}(\lambda) / \Delta t \cdot S_{Cal}(\lambda) \cdot 10^3, \quad (1)$$

with wavelength λ . To obtain the photoisomerisation rate per photoreceptor type, we first converted from electrical power into energy flux (P_{eflux} , in eV/s),

$$P_{eflux}(\lambda) = P_{el}(\lambda) \cdot a \cdot 10^{-9}, \quad (2)$$

where $a = 6.242 \cdot 10^{18}$ eV/J. Next, we calculated the photon flux (P_{phi} , in photons/s) using the photon energy Q (P_Q , in eV),

$$P_Q(\lambda) = c \cdot h / (\lambda \cdot 10^{-9}), \quad (3)$$

$$P_{phi}(\lambda) = P_{eflux}(\lambda) / P_Q(\lambda), \quad (4)$$

with the speed of light, $c = 299,792,458$ m/s, and Planck's constant, $h = 4.135667 \cdot 10^{-15}$ eV·s. The photon flux density (P_E , [photons/s/ μm^2]) was then computed as

$$P_E(\lambda) = P_{phi}(\lambda) / A_{stim}, \quad (5)$$

where A_{stim} (in μm^2) corresponds to the light stimulus area. To convert P_E into photoisomerisation rate, we next determined the effective activation (S_{Act}) of mouse photoreceptor types by the LEDs as

$$S_{Act}(\lambda) = S_{Opsin}(\lambda) \cdot S_{LED}(\lambda) \quad (6)$$

with the peak-normalised spectra of the M- and S-opsins, S_{Opsin} , and the green and UV LEDs, S_{LED} . Sensitivity spectra of mouse opsins were derived from Equation 8 in **Stockman and Sharpe (2000)**.

For our LEDs (**Table 2**), the effective mouse M-opsin activation was 14.9% and 10.5% for the green and UV LED, respectively. The mouse S-opsin is only expected to be activated by the UV LED (52.9%) (**Figure 3a, f**). Next, we estimated the photon flux (R_{ph} , [photons/s]) for each photoreceptor as

$$R_{ph}(\lambda) = P_E(\lambda) \cdot A_{Collect} \quad (7)$$

where $A_{Collect} = 0.2 \mu\text{m}^2$ corresponds to the light collection area of cone outer segments (**Nikonov et al., 2006**). The photoisomerisation rate (R_{Iso} , P*/photoreceptor/s) for each combination of LED and photoreceptor type was estimated using

$$R_{Iso} = \sum R_{ph}(\lambda) \cdot S_{Act}(\lambda), \quad (8)$$

see **Nikonov et al. (2006)** for details. The intensities of the mouse stimulator LEDs were manually adjusted (**Figure 2—figure supplement 5b,c**) to an approximately equal photoisomerisation range from (in P*/cone/s $\cdot 10^3$) 0.6 and 0.7 (stimulator shows black image) to 19.5 and 19.2 (stimulator shows white image) for M- and S-opsins, respectively (cf. **Figure 3f**). This corresponds to the low photopic range. The M-opsin sensitivity spectrum displays a 'tail' in the short wavelength range (due to the opsin's β -band, see **Figure 1a** and **Stockman and Sharpe, 2000**), which means that it should be cross-activated by our UV LED. Specifically, while S-opsin should be solely activated by the UV LED (19.2 by UV vs. 0.1 by green; in P*/cone/s $\cdot 10^3$), we expect M-opsin to be activated by both LEDs (19.5 by green vs. 3.8 by UV). The effect of such cross-activation can be addressed, for instance, by silent substitution (see below).

To account for the non-linearity of the stimulator output using gamma correction, we recorded spectra for each LED for different intensities (1,000 μm spot diameter; pixel values from 0 to 254 in steps of 2) and estimated the photoisomerisation rates, as described above. From these data, we computed a lookup table (LUT) that allows the visual stimulus software (QDSpy) to linearise the intensity functions of each LED (cf. **Figure 3e**; for details, see iPython notebooks; **Table 1**).

In case of the **zebrafish stimulator**, to determine the LED spectra, we used a compact CCD Spectrometer (CCS200/M, Thorlabs, Dachau, Germany) in combination with the Thorlabs Optical Spectrum Analyzers (OSA) software, coupled to a linear fibre patch cable. To determine the electrical power (P_{el} , in nW), we used an optical energy power meter (PM100D, Thorlabs) in combination with the Thorlabs Optical Power Monitor (OPM) software, coupled to a photodiode power sensor (S130VC, Thorlabs). Both probes were positioned behind the teflon screen (0.15 mm, for details, see **Table 3**). Following the same procedure as described above, we determined the photoisomerisation rate (R_{Iso} , P*/photoreceptor/s) for each combination of LED and photoreceptor type (cf. iPython notebooks; **Table 1**).

Spatial resolution measurements

To measure the spatial resolution of the mouse stimulator, we removed the lens of a Raspberry Pi camera chip (OV5647, Eckstein GmbH, Clausthal-Zellerfeld, Germany) and positioned it at the level of the recording chamber. Then, we projected UV and green checkerboards of varying checker sizes (2, 3, 4, 5, 10, 20, 30, 40, 60, 80, and 100 μm) through an objective lens (MPL5XBD (5x), Olympus, Germany) or through the condenser onto the chip of the camera (**Figure 4a**). For each checker size and LED, we extracted intensity profiles using ImageJ (**Figure 4b**) and estimated the respective contrast as $I_{Max} - I_{Min}$ (**Figure 4c**). To quantify the steepness of the transition between bright and dark checkers, we peak-normalised the intensity profiles and normalised relative to half-width of the maximum (**Figure 4d**). Next, we fitted a sigmoid to the rising phase of the intensity profile

$$y = K_0 + K_1 / (1 + \exp(-(x - K_2)/K_3)) \quad (9)$$

and used $1/K_3$ as estimate of the rise time and as a proxy for 'sharpness' of the transitions between black and white pixels (**Figure 4e**).

To measure the difference in focal plane of UV and green LED due to chromatic aberration, we projected a 40 and 100 μm checkerboard through a 20x objective (W Plan-Apochromat 20x/1.0 DIC M27, Zeiss, Oberkochen, Germany) onto the Raspberry Pi camera (see above).

Fast intensity measurements

To verify temporal separation, we measured the time course of the green LED (mouse stimulator) with and without blanking using a PMT positioned at the level of the recording chamber (**Figure 2—figure supplement 2a**). Traces were recorded with pClamp at 250 kHz (Molecular Devices, Biberach an der Riss, Germany). To estimate the amount of intensity modulation due to aliasing (**Figure 2—figure supplement 2b**), we measured the intensity of both LEDs together ('white') driven by a chirp stimulus with blanking at the same position using a photodiode (Siemens silicon photodiode BPW 21, Reichelt, Sande, Germany; as light-dependent current source in a transimpedance amplifier circuit). Next, intensity traces were box-smoothed with a box width of 100 ms, which roughly corresponds to the integration time of mouse cone photoreceptors (**Umino et al., 2008**).

Silent substitution

For our measurements in mouse cones, we used a silent substitution protocol (**Estévez and Spek-reijse, 1982**) for generating opsin-isolating stimuli to account for the cross-activation of mouse M-opsin by the UV LED. Here, one opsin type is selectively stimulated by presenting a scaled, counterphase version of the stimulus to all other opsin types (cf. **Figure 5**). Specifically, we first used the ratio of activation (as photoisomerisation rate) of M-opsin by UV and green to estimate the amount of cross-activation ($S_{CrossAct}$). For our recordings, an activation of M-opsin of 19.5 and 3.8 P*/cone/s $\cdot 10^3$ for green and UV LED resulted in a cross-activation of $S_{CrossAct} = 0.195$. Then, $S_{CrossAct}$ was used to scale the intensity of the counterphase stimulus:

$$I_G = I - I_{UV} \cdot S_{CrossAct} \quad (10)$$

For our recordings in zebrafish larvae, we did not use silent substitution. However, we describe a possible approach for the zebrafish (or a comparable tetrachromatic species) in our online resources (**Table 1**).

Animals and tissue preparation

All animal procedures (mice) were approved by the governmental review board (Regierungspräsidium Tübingen, Baden-Württemberg, Konrad-Adenauer-Str. 20, 72072 Tübingen, Germany) and performed according to the laws governing animal experimentation issued by the German Government. All animal procedures (zebrafish) were performed in accordance with the UK Animals (Scientific Procedures) Act 1986 and approved by the animal welfare committee of the University of Sussex (zebrafish larvae).

For the **mouse** experiments, we used one 12-week-old HR2.1:TN-XL mouse; this mouse line expresses the ratiometric Ca^{2+} biosensor TN-XL under the cone-specific HR2.1 promoter and allows measuring light-evoked Ca^{2+} responses in cone synaptic terminals (Wei et al., 2012). Animals were housed under a standard 12 hr day-night rhythm. Before the recordings, the mouse was dark-adapted for ≥ 1 hr, then anaesthetized with isoflurane (Baxter, Unterschleißheim, Germany) and killed by cervical dislocation. The eyes were removed and hemisected in carboxygenated (95% O_2 , 5% CO_2) artificial cerebrospinal fluid (ACSF) solution containing (in mM): 125 NaCl, 2.5 KCl, 2 CaCl_2 , 1 MgCl_2 , 1.25 NaH_2PO_4 , 26 NaHCO_3 , 20 glucose, and 0.5 L-glutamine (pH 7.4). The retina was separated from the eye-cup, cut in half, flattened, and mounted photoreceptor side-up on a nitrocellulose membrane (0.8 mm pore size, Merck Millipore, Darmstadt, Germany). Using a custom-made slicer (Wei et al., 2012; Werblin, 1978), acute vertical slices (200 μm thick) were cut parallel to the naso-temporal axis. Slices attached to filter paper were transferred on individual glass coverslips, fixed using high-vacuum grease and kept in a storing chamber at room temperature for later use. For imaging, individual retinal slices were transferred to the recording chamber of the 2P microscope (see below), where they were continuously perfused with warmed (36°C), carboxygenated extracellular solution.

For the **zebrafish larvae** experiments, we used 7 day post fertilisation (dpf) larvae of the zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) line *tg(1.8ctbp2:SyGCaMP6f)*, which expresses the genetically encoded Ca^{2+} indicator GCaMP6f fused with synaptophysin under the RibeyeA promoter and allows measuring light-evoked Ca^{2+} responses in bipolar cell synaptic terminals (Dreosti et al., 2009; Johnston et al., 2019; Rosa et al., 2016; Zimmermann et al., 2018). Animals were grown from 10 hr post fertilisation (hpf) in 200 μM of 1-phenyl-2-thiourea (Sigma) to prevent melanogenesis (Karlsson et al., 2001). Animals were housed under a standard 14/10 hr day-night rhythm and fed 3x a day. Before the recordings, zebrafish larvae were immobilised in 2% low-melting-point agarose (Fischer Scientific, Loughborough, UK; Cat: BP1360-100), placed on a glass coverslip and submersed in fish water. To prevent eye movement during recordings, α -bungarotoxin (1 nl of 2 mg/ml; Tocris, Bristol, UK; Cat: 2133) was injected into the ocular muscles behind the eye.

Two-photon imaging

For all imaging experiments, we used MOM-type two-photon (2P) microscopes (designed by W. Denk, MPI, Heidelberg; purchased from Sutter Instruments/Science Products, Hofheim, Germany). For image acquisition, we used custom software (ScanM by M. Müller, MPI Neurobiology, Munich, and T.E.) running under IGOR Pro 6.3 for Windows (Wavemetrics, Lake Oswego, OR). The microscopes were equipped each with a mode-locked Ti:Sapphire laser (MaiTai-HP DeepSee, Newport Spectra-Physics, Darmstadt, Germany; or Chameleon Vision-S, Coherent; Ely, UK), two fluorescence detection channels for eCFP (FRET donor; HQ 483/32, AHF, Tübingen, Germany) and citrine (FRET acceptor; HQ 538/50, AHF) or GCaMP6f (ET 525/70 or ET 525/50, AHF), and a water immersion objective (W Plan-Apochromat 20 \times /1.0 DIC M27, Zeiss, Oberkochen, Germany). The excitation laser was tuned to 860 nm and 927 nm for TN-XL (eCFP) in mouse and GCaMP6f in zebrafish, respectively. Time-lapsed image series were recorded with 64 \times 16 pixels (at 31.25 Hz) or 128 \times 64 (at 15.625 Hz). Detailed descriptions of the setups for mouse (Euler et al., 2019; Euler et al., 2009; Franke et al., 2017) and zebrafish (Zimmermann et al., 2018) have been published elsewhere.

Data analysis

Data analysis was performed using IGOR Pro (Wavemetrics). Regions of interest (ROIs) of individual synaptic terminals (of mouse cones and zebrafish bipolar cells) were manually placed. Then, Ca^{2+} traces for each ROI were extracted for mouse cones as $\Delta R/R$, with the ratio $R = F_A/F_D$ of the FRET acceptor (citrine) and donor (eCFP) fluorescence, and resampled at 500 Hz. For zebrafish bipolar

cells, Ca^{2+} traces for each ROI were extracted and detrended by high-pass filtering above -0.1 Hz, followed by z-normalisation based on the time interval 1–6 s at the beginning of recordings using custom-written routines under IGOR Pro. A stimulus synchronisation marker that was generated by the visual stimulation software (Results) and embedded in the recordings served to align the Ca^{2+} traces relative to the stimulus with ≤ 2 ms precision (depending on the scan line duration, see Results and Euler et al., 2019). For this, the timing for each ROI was corrected for sub-frame time-offsets related to the scanning.

Response quality index. To measure how well a cell responded to the sine wave stimulus, we computed the signal-to-noise ratio

$$Qi = \frac{\text{Var}[(C)_r]_t}{(\text{Var}[C]_t)_r} \quad (11)$$

where C is the T by R response matrix (time samples by stimulus repetitions), while $(\cdot)_x$ and $\text{Var}[\cdot]_x$ denote the mean and variance across the indicated dimension, respectively (Baden et al., 2016; Franke et al., 2017). For further analysis, we used only cells that had a $Qi > 0.3$.

Spectral contrast. The mean trace in response to the green and UV sine wave stimulus was used to analyse the spectral sensitivity of the cones. For that, we computed the power spectrum of the trace and used the power (P) at the fundamental frequency (1 Hz) as a measure of response strength. Then, the spectral contrast (SC) was estimated as

$$SC = \frac{P_G - P_B}{P_G + P_B}, \quad (12)$$

where P_G and P_B correspond to the responses to green and UV, respectively. For statistical comparison of SC values with and without silent substitution (see above), we used the Wilcoxon signed-rank test for non-parametric, paired samples.

Acknowledgements

This study is part of the research program of the Bernstein Centre for Computational Neuroscience, Tübingen, and was funded by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research and the Max Planck Society (BMBF, FKZ: 01GQ1002, and MPG M.FE.A.KYBE0004 to KF), the European Research Council (ERC-StG 'NeuroVisEco' 677687 to TB) the EU's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 674901 ('switchBoard', to TB, TE), the UKRI (BBSRC, BB/R014817/1 and MRC, MC_PC_15071 to TB), the Leverhulme Trust (PLP-2017-005 to TB), the Lister Institute for Preventive Medicine (to TB), and the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation; Projektnummer 276693517 – SFB 1233 to TE).

Additional information

Funding

Funder	Grant reference number	Author
Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung	FKZ: 01GQ1002	Katrin Franke
Max-Planck-Gesellschaft	M.FE.A.KYBE0004	Katrin Franke
European Commission	ERC-StG 'NeuroVisEco' 677687	Tom Baden
Horizon 2020 Framework Programme	Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 674901	Tom Baden Thomas Euler
Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council	BB/R014817/1	Tom Baden
Leverhulme Trust	PLP-2017-005	Tom Baden
Lister Institute of Preventive Medicine		Tom Baden

Deutsche Forschungsge- meinschaft	Projektnummer 276693517 - Thomas Euler SFB 1233	
Medical Research Council	MC_PC_15071	Tom Baden

The funders had no role in study design, data collection and interpretation, or the decision to submit the work for publication.

Author contributions

Katrin Franke, Conceptualization, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Visualization, Methodology, Writing—original draft, Writing—review and editing; André Maia Chagas, Conceptualization, Validation, Methodology, Writing—review and editing; Zhijian Zhao, Conceptualization, Validation, Visualization, Methodology, Writing—review and editing; Maxime JY Zimmermann, Conceptualization, Validation, Investigation, Visualization, Writing—review and editing; Philipp Bartel, Yongrong Qiu, Klaudia P Szatko, Validation, Methodology; Tom Baden, Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Visualization, Writing—review and editing; Thomas Euler, Conceptualization, Software, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Visualization, Methodology, Writing—original draft, Writing—review and editing

Author ORCIDs

André Maia Chagas <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2609-3017>

Zhijian Zhao <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-3302-1495>

Maxime JY Zimmermann <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0885-9640>

Philipp Bartel <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7191-9511>

Tom Baden <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2808-4210>

Thomas Euler <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4567-6966>

Ethics

Animal experimentation: All animal procedures adhered to the laws governing animal experimentation issued by the German Government (mouse) or all procedures were performed in accordance with the UK Animals (Scientific Procedures) act 1986 and approved by the animal welfare committee of the University of Sussex (zebrafish larvae).

Decision letter and Author response

Decision letter <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.48779.023>

Author response <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.48779.024>

Additional files

Supplementary files

- Supplementary file 1. Parts list of the through-the-objective mouse stimulator (*cf. Figure 2—figure supplement 1*; entries in grey are not shown).

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.48779.019>

- Transparent reporting form

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.48779.020>

Data availability

Part lists are provided in Tables 1-3 and Supplementary file 1. Software scripts for stimulus calibration as well as design files for circuit boards and 3D-printed parts are provided at <https://github.com/eulerlab/open-visual-stimulator> (copy archived at <https://github.com/elifesciences-publications/open-visual-stimulator>). The visual stimulation software is provided at <https://github.com/eulerlab/QDSpy> (copy archived at <https://github.com/elifesciences-publications/QDSpy>).

References

- Ahrens MB, Orger MB, Robson DN, Li JM, Keller PJ. 2013. Whole-brain functional imaging at cellular resolution using light-sheet microscopy. *Nature Methods* **10**:413–420. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/nmeth.2434>, PMID: 23524393
- Alfonso-Garcia A, Li C, Bec J, Yankelevich D, Marcu L, Sherlock B. 2019. Fiber-based platform for synchronous imaging of endogenous and exogenous fluorescence of biological tissue. *Optics Letters* **44**:3350–3353. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1364/OL.44.003350>, PMID: 31259958
- Applebury ML, Antoch MP, Baxter LC, Chun LL, Falk JD, Farhangfar F, Kage K, Krzystolik MG, Lyass LA, Robbins JT. 2000. The murine cone photoreceptor: a single cone type expresses both S and M opsins with retinal spatial patterning. *Neuron* **27**:513–523. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0896-6273\(00\)00062-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0896-6273(00)00062-3), PMID: 11055434
- Baden T, Schubert T, Chang L, Wei T, Zaichuk M, Wissinger B, Euler T. 2013. A tale of two retinal domains: near-optimal sampling of achromatic contrasts in natural scenes through asymmetric photoreceptor distribution. *Neuron* **80**:1206–1217. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuron.2013.09.030>, PMID: 24314730
- Baden T, Berens P, Franke K, Román Rosón M, Bethge M, Euler T. 2016. The functional diversity of retinal ganglion cells in the mouse. *Nature* **529**:345–350. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature16468>, PMID: 26735013
- Baden T, Osorio D. 2019. The retinal basis of vertebrate color vision. *Annual Review of Vision Science* **5**:177–200. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-vision-091718-014926>, PMID: 31226010
- Boström JE, Dimitrova M, Canton C, Håstad O, Qvarnström A, Ödeen A. 2016. Ultra-Rapid vision in birds. *PLOS ONE* **11**:e0151099. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0151099>, PMID: 26990087
- Branchek T, Bremiller R. 1984. The development of photoreceptors in the zebrafish, *Brachydanio rerio*. I. structure. *The Journal of Comparative Neurology* **224**:107–115. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/cne.902240109>, PMID: 6715574
- Chiao C-C, Cronin TW, Osorio D. 2000. Color signals in natural scenes: characteristics of reflectance spectra and effects of natural illuminants. *Journal of the Optical Society of America A* **17**:218–224. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1364/JOSAA.17.000218>
- Chinen A, Hamaoka T, Yamada Y, Kawamura S. 2003. Gene duplication and spectral diversification of cone visual pigments of zebrafish. *Genetics* **163**:663–675. PMID: 12618404
- Cronin TW, Bok MJ. 2016. Photoreception and vision in the ultraviolet. *The Journal of Experimental Biology* **219**:2790–2801. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1242/jeb.128769>, PMID: 27655820
- Dartnall HJ, Bowmaker JK, Mollon JD. 1983. Human visual pigments: microspectrophotometric results from the eyes of seven persons. *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London. Series B, Biological Sciences* **220**:115–130. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.1983.0091>, PMID: 6140680
- Delmans M, Haseloff J. 2018. μ Cube: A framework for 3D printable optomechanics. *Journal of Open Hardware* **2**. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5334/joh.8>
- Denman DJ, Siegle JH, Koch C, Reid RC, Blanche TJ. 2017. Spatial organization of chromatic pathways in the mouse dorsal lateral geniculate nucleus. *The Journal of Neuroscience* **37**:1102–1116. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.1742-16.2016>, PMID: 27986926
- Dreosti E, Odermatt B, Dorostkar MM, Lagnado L. 2009. A genetically encoded reporter of synaptic activity in vivo. *Nature Methods* **6**:883–889. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/nmeth.1399>, PMID: 19898484
- Ebrey T, Koutalos Y. 2001. Vertebrate photoreceptors. *Progress in Retinal and Eye Research* **20**:49–94. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1350-9462\(00\)00014-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1350-9462(00)00014-8), PMID: 11070368
- Estévez O, Spekreijse H. 1982. The "silent substitution" method in visual research. *Vision Research* **22**:681–691. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0042-6989\(82\)90104-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0042-6989(82)90104-3), PMID: 7112962
- Euler T, Hausselt SE, Margolis DJ, Breuninger T, Castell X, Detwiler PB, Denk W. 2009. Eyecup scope—optical recordings of light stimulus-evoked fluorescence signals in the retina. *Pflügers Archiv - European Journal of Physiology* **457**:1393–1414. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00424-008-0603-5>
- Euler T, Franke K, Baden T. 2019. Studying a light sensor with light: multiphoton imaging in the retina. *Preprints*. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.20944/preprints201903.0244.v1>
- Euler T, Maia Chagas A, Zimmerman MJY, Baden T, Zhao Z, Franke K. 2019a. An arbitrary-spectrum spatial visual stimulator for vision research. *Open Visual Stimulator*. a2193e2. GitHub. <https://github.com/elifesciences-publications/open-visual-stimulator>
- Euler T. 2019b. A Python software for scripting and presenting stimuli for visual neuroscience. *QDSpy*. 4852fa1. GitHub. <https://github.com/eulerlab/QDSpy>
- Feuda R, Marlétaz F, Bentley MA, Holland PW. 2016. Conservation, duplication, and divergence of five opsin genes in insect evolution. *Genome Biology and Evolution* **8**:579–587. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1093/gbe/eww015>, PMID: 26865071
- Franke K, Berens P, Schubert T, Bethge M, Euler T, Baden T. 2017. Inhibition decorrelates visual feature representations in the inner retina. *Nature* **542**:439–444. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature21394>, PMID: 28178238
- Guggiana-Nilo DA, Engert F. 2016. Properties of the visible light phototaxis and UV avoidance behaviors in the larval zebrafish. *Frontiers in Behavioral Neuroscience* **10**:160. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnbeh.2016.00160>, PMID: 27594828
- Haber Kern H, Basnak MA, Ahanonu B, Schauder D, Cohen JD, Bolstad M, Bruns C, Jayaraman V. 2019. Visually guided behavior and optogenetically induced learning in Head-Fixed flies exploring a virtual landscape. *Current Biology* **29**:1647–1659. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2019.04.033>, PMID: 31056392

- Haug MF, Biehmaier O, Mueller KP, Neuhauss SC. 2010. Visual acuity in larval zebrafish: behavior and histology. *Frontiers in Zoology* **7**:8. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1186/1742-9994-7-8>, PMID: 20193078
- Haverkamp S, Wässle H, Duebel J, Kuner T, Augustine GJ, Feng G, Euler T. 2005. The primordial, blue-cone color system of the mouse retina. *Journal of Neuroscience* **25**:5438–5445. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.1117-05.2005>, PMID: 15930394
- Hecht S, Verrijp CD. 1933. Intermittent stimulation by light : iii. the relation between intensity and critical fusion frequency for different retinal locations. *The Journal of General Physiology* **17**:251–268. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1085/jgp.17.2.251>, PMID: 19872777
- Hollbach N, Tappeiner C, Jazwinska A, Enzmann V, Tschopp M. 2015. Photopic and scotopic spatiotemporal tuning of adult zebrafish vision. *Frontiers in Systems Neuroscience* **9**:20. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnsys.2015.00020>, PMID: 25788878
- Hornbeck LJ. 1996. Multi-level digital micromirror device. Texas Instruments Inc. US5583688A. <https://patents.google.com/patent/US5583688A/en>.
- Jacobs GH, Neitz J, Deegan JF. 1991. Retinal receptors in rodents maximally sensitive to ultraviolet light. *Nature* **353**:655–656. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/353655a0>, PMID: 1922382
- Jacobs GH. 2008. Primate color vision: a comparative perspective. *Visual Neuroscience* **25**:619–633. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0952523808080760>, PMID: 18983718
- Jeon CJ, Strettoi E, Masland RH. 1998. The major cell populations of the mouse retina. *The Journal of Neuroscience* **18**:8936–8946. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.18-21-08936.1998>, PMID: 9786999
- Johnsen S, Widder EA. 2001. Ultraviolet absorption in transparent zooplankton and its implications for depth distribution and visual predation. *Marine Biology* **138**:717–730. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s002270000499>
- Johnston J, Seibel SH, Darnet LSA, Renninger S, Orger M, Lagnado L. 2019. A retinal circuit generating a dynamic predictive code for oriented features. *Neuron* **102**:1211–1222. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuron.2019.04.002>, PMID: 31054873
- Jun JJ, Steinmetz NA, Siegle JH, Denman DJ, Bauza M, Barbarits B, Lee AK, Anastassiou CA, Andrei A, Aydin Ç, Barbic M, Blanche TJ, Bonin V, Couto J, Dutta B, Gratiy SL, Gutnisky DA, Häusser M, Karsh B, Ledochowitsch P, et al. 2017. Fully integrated silicon probes for high-density recording of neural activity. *Nature* **551**:232–236. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature24636>, PMID: 29120427
- Kamar S, Howlett MHC, Kamermans M. 2019. Silent-substitution stimuli silence the light responses of cones but not their output. *Journal of Vision* **19**:14. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1167/19.5.14>, PMID: 31100130
- Karlsson J, von Hofsten J, Olsson P-E. 2001. Generating transparent zebrafish: a refined method to improve detection of gene expression during embryonic development. *Marine Biotechnology* **3**:0522–0527. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s1012601-0053-4>
- Kemmler R, Schultz K, Dedek K, Euler T, Schubert T. 2014. Differential regulation of cone calcium signals by different horizontal cell feedback mechanisms in the mouse retina. *Journal of Neuroscience* **34**:11826–11843. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.0272-14.2014>, PMID: 25164677
- Li YN, Tsujimura T, Kawamura S, Dowling JE. 2012. Bipolar cell-photoreceptor connectivity in the zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) retina. *The Journal of Comparative Neurology* **520**:3786–3802. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/cne.23168>, PMID: 22907678
- Losey GS, Cronin TW, Goldsmith TH, Hyde D, Marshall NJ, McFarland WN. 1999. The UV visual world of fishes: a review. *Journal of Fish Biology* **54**:921–943. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1095-8649.1999.tb00848.x>
- Marshall J, Arikawa K. 2014. Unconventional colour vision. *Current Biology* **24**:R1150–R1154. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2014.10.025>, PMID: 25514002
- Miall RC. 1978. The flicker fusion frequencies of six laboratory insects, and the response of the compound eye to mains fluorescent 'ripple'. *Physiological Entomology* **3**:99–106. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-3032.1978.tb00139.x>
- Morris AC, Fadool JM. 2005. Studying rod photoreceptor development in zebrafish. *Physiology & Behavior* **86**:306–313. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physbeh.2005.08.020>, PMID: 16199068
- Nathans J, Thomas D, Hogness DS. 1986. Molecular genetics of human color vision: the genes encoding blue, green, and red pigments. *Science* **232**:193–202. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.2937147>, PMID: 2937147
- Neumeyer C. 1992. Tetrachromatic color vision in goldfish: evidence from color mixture experiments. *Journal of Comparative Physiology A* **171**:639–649. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00194111>
- Nikonov SS, Kholodenko R, Lem J, Pugh EN. 2006. Physiological features of the S- and M-cone photoreceptors of wild-type mice from single-cell recordings. *The Journal of General Physiology* **127**:359–374. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1085/jgp.200609490>, PMID: 16567464
- Novales Flamarique I. 2013. Opsin switch reveals function of the ultraviolet cone in fish foraging. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* **280**:20122490. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2012.2490>
- Parkyn DC, Hawryshyn CW. 1993. Polarized-light sensitivity in rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*): characterization from multi-unit responses in the optic nerve. *Journal of Comparative Physiology A* **172**:493–500. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00213531>
- Reiser MB, Dickinson MH. 2008. A modular display system for insect behavioral neuroscience. *Journal of Neuroscience Methods* **167**:127–139. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jneumeth.2007.07.019>, PMID: 17854905
- Rogerson LE, Zhao Z, Franke K, Euler T, Berens P. 2019. Bayesian hypothesis testing and experimental design for two-photon imaging data. *PLOS Computational Biology* **15**:e1007205. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1007205>, PMID: 31374071
- Röhlich P, van Veen T, Szél A. 1994. Two different visual pigments in one retinal cone cell. *Neuron* **13**:1159–1166. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0896-6273\(94\)90053-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0896-6273(94)90053-1), PMID: 7946352

- Rosa JM, Ruehle S, Ding H, Lagnado L. 2016. Crossover inhibition generates sustained visual responses in the inner retina. *Neuron* **90**:308–319. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuron.2016.03.015>, PMID: 27068790
- Salcedo E, Huber A, Henrich S, Chadwell LV, Chou WH, Paulsen R, Britt SG. 1999. Blue- and green-absorbing visual pigments of *Drosophila*: ectopic expression and physiological characterization of the R8 photoreceptor cell-specific Rh5 and Rh6 rhodopsins. *The Journal of Neuroscience* **19**:10716–10726. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.19-24-10716.1999>, PMID: 10594055
- Schmidt-Hieber C, Häusser M. 2013. Cellular mechanisms of spatial navigation in the medial entorhinal cortex. *Nature Neuroscience* **16**:325–331. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/nn.3340>, PMID: 23396102
- Schnaitmann C, Haikala V, Abraham E, Oberhauser V, Thestrup T, Griesbeck O, Reiff DF. 2018. Color processing in the early visual system of *Drosophila*. *Cell* **172**:318–330. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2017.12.018>, PMID: 29328919
- Seliger HH, Lall AB, Biggley WH. 1994. Blue through UV polarization sensitivities in insects. *Journal of Comparative Physiology A* **175**:475–486. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00199255>
- Stockman A, Sharpe LT. 2000. The spectral sensitivities of the middle- and long-wavelength-sensitive cones derived from measurements in observers of known genotype. *Vision Research* **40**:1711–1737. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0042-6989\(00\)00021-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0042-6989(00)00021-3), PMID: 10814758
- Stringer C, Pachitariu M, Steinmetz N, Reddy CB, Carandini M, Harris KD. 2019. Spontaneous behaviors drive multidimensional, brainwide activity. *Science* **364**:eaav7893. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aav7893>
- Surridge AK, Osorio D, Mundy NI. 2003. Evolution and selection of trichromatic vision in primates. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* **18**:198–205. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-5347\(03\)00012-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-5347(03)00012-0)
- Tan Z, Sun W, Chen TW, Kim D, Ji N. 2015. Neuronal representation of ultraviolet visual stimuli in mouse primary visual cortex. *Scientific Reports* **5**:12597. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep12597>, PMID: 26219604
- Umino Y, Solessio E, Barlow RB. 2008. Speed, spatial, and temporal tuning of rod and cone vision in mouse. *Journal of Neuroscience* **28**:189–198. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.3551-07.2008>, PMID: 18171936
- Wang K, Hinz J, Haikala V, Reiff DF, Arrenberg AB. 2019. Selective processing of all rotational and translational optic flow directions in the zebrafish pretectum and tectum. *BMC Biology* **17**:29. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12915-019-0648-2>, PMID: 30925897
- Wehner R. 2001. Polarization vision—a uniform sensory capacity? *The Journal of Experimental Biology* **204**:2589–2596. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5167/uzh-693>, PMID: 11511675
- Wei T, Schubert T, Paquet-Durand F, Tanimoto N, Chang L, Koeppen K, Ott T, Griesbeck O, Seeliger MW, Euler T, Wissinger B. 2012. Light-driven calcium signals in mouse cone photoreceptors. *Journal of Neuroscience* **32**:6981–6994. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.6432-11.2012>, PMID: 22593066
- Werblin FS. 1978. Transmission along and between rods in the tiger salamander retina. *The Journal of Physiology* **280**:449–470. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1113/jphysiol.1978.sp012394>, PMID: 211229
- Wikler KC, Rakic P. 1990. Distribution of photoreceptor subtypes in the retina of diurnal and nocturnal primates. *The Journal of Neuroscience* **10**:3390–3401. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.10-10-03390.1990>, PMID: 2145402
- Yang W, Srivastava PK, Han S, Jing L, Tu CC, Chen SL. 2019. Optomechanical Time-Gated fluorescence imaging using Long-Lived silicon quantum dot nanoparticles. *Analytical Chemistry* **91**:5499–5503. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.analchem.9b00517>, PMID: 30986341
- Yokoyama S. 2000. Molecular evolution of vertebrate visual pigments. *Progress in Retinal and Eye Research* **19**:385–419. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1350-9462\(00\)00002-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1350-9462(00)00002-1), PMID: 10785616
- Yoshimatsu T, Schröder C BP, Baden T. 2019. Cellular and molecular mechanisms of photoreceptor tuning for prey capture in larval zebrafish. *bioRxiv*. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1101/744615>
- Zimmermann MJY, Nevala NE, Yoshimatsu T, Osorio D, Nilsson DE, Berens P, Baden T. 2018. Zebrafish differentially process color across visual space to match natural scenes. *Current Biology* **28**:2018–2032. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2018.04.075>, PMID: 29937350